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Agri-food and Tourism
BIOATLAS 2016
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Biodiversity

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27-28 May 2016

6th BIOATLAS CONFERENCE

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Editor: Gruia R., Gaceu L.

EcoAgriTourism, in the light of its multidisciplinary character, is a wide-open journal which brings together the opinions of specialists from both academic and economic environment, fostering fruitful collaborations.

The journal's structure covers all aspects of the fields approached, the focus being on original and current researches with applications in agriculture, food industry and rural tourism. Collaborators may feel free to undertake biological and technical aspects as well as aspects with social, cultural and environmental impact. Information of general interest is also welcome for the agriecology-food-tourism axis.

Prof. Romulus Gruia Ph. D.

The Journal of EcoAgroTurism aims at approaching analyses, methodologies, options and references within the journal's framework.

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EDITORIAL

*On behalf of the Organizing Committee of the **BIOATLAS International Conference**, it is our great pleasure and privilege to invite you to join us in Brasov, Romania, between May 27 and 28, 2016.*

“BIOATLAS 2016” Conference provides a forum for food and tourism related professionals, professors, lecturers and PhD students to exchange information on education, research, applications and developments the Food and Tourism and publish the most recent results. The topics include aspects related to Biodiversity and Agriculture technologies, new tendencies in Tourism development, IT&C in Agriculture, Food and Tourism Industry, etc. Contributions from various countries will allow a broadened perspective for all attending.

*After the very successful meetings in **2006, 2008, 2010, 2012 and 2014**, **BIOATLAS 2016** offers us the opportunity to combine the beauty and hospitality of **Brasov** city with some of the outstanding works done on the important topics of food science and tourism, and to make easy contacts and relations among researchers from all around the world.*

Brasov is probably the most beautiful city from Romania and one of the most important cities of Transylvania region, surrounded by the Southern Carpathians. Our city provides a mix of wonderful mountain scenery in the nearby Poiana Brasov, and medieval history with German influences in the old town.

We work closely with the Scientific Committee to provide an unforgettable scientific experience as well as to offer a social program filled with opportunities to share the beauty of Transilvania with colleagues and friends from all around the world in a very familiar and warm atmosphere.

We look forward to meet together in the spring of 2016 for a great Conference in Brasov!

*Romulus Gruia, Liviu Gaceu
Chairs of the Organizing Committee*

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RESEARCH ON THE INFLUENCE OF THE USE OF ULTRASOUND IN THE MATURATION PROCESS OF NATURAL BEVERAGES WHICH ARE DISTILLED FROM FRUIT TO DIRECT FIRED BOILERS

I.R. ȘUGAR* L. GIURGIULESCU** I. VAGELAS*** M. BANICA*

Abstract: *The maturation process of distilled products has a great importance in the development of high quality products. Sometimes, the maturation process has almost equal importance as the production process itself. The use of ultrasounds could be a solution to shorten the maturation time.*

Keywords: *ultrasounds, maturation, distilled, products*

1. Introduction

The ultrasounds use on a larger scale in the food industry is due to some specific features like :their diffusion and absorption are much higher in comparison with those of sounds in the same propagation environment; they can be amplified, directed or targeted; they carry much higher energies than sounds; they realize the cavitation phenomenon.

They are those elastic waves with a frequency more than of 20 kHz.

The cavitation phenomenon occurs with the propagation of ultrasounds as a result of inflation and successive decrease of fluid pressure around an average value. In the occurring gaps gases and vapors gather and by remaining in the product they develop a subsequent compression pressure of thousands of atmospheres.

It can thus determine the maximum pressure in the liquid p in the ultrasonic liquid with the following relationship:

$$p = 0,163p_0 \frac{R_0}{R} \quad (1)$$

where:

p is the hydrostatic pressure of the liquid;
 R_0 - initial radius of the gas bubble;
 R - the radius of the final gas bubble.

The size of the cavity depends on the acoustic intensity and viscosity. The higher the viscosity , the higher the required pressure to create cavities [1].

2. Material and method

The title must be as short possible. If necessary, a subtitle is provided.

In our study we have used 5 types of distilled products from Zetea Private SRL: plum brandy in old oak casks for 2 years; Apricot brandy in old oak casks for 7 years; Pear brandy in old oak barrels for 7 years; Cherry brandy in old oak casks for 2 years; Disitilated wine aged in oak casks for 10 years.

Ten ml were taken from each sample and were introduced into the resistant to treatment with ultrasounds quartz tube.

All samples underwent through ultrasound treatment in order to view the color differences before and after the treatment.

In another determination the possibility of using ultrasound for aging fruit distillates was searched.

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The procedure consisted in introducing oak shavings in the analyzed samples. In each tube were introduced 10 ml of distilled product and 1 g of wood shavings.

The shavings were obtained from oak wood aged for one year through natural drying process. The samples were left to stand for 30 days.

The treatment with ultrasounds of the distilled products was realized in an ultrasound vat HM 1005 L from the image 1.

Fig. 1. The ultrasound vat HM 1005 L

Table 1 The characteristics of the ultrasound vat Hm1005

Nr. Crt.	Measure	
1	The capacity (volume) of the vat	20l
2	The size of the tank interior	495 x 290 x 150 [mm]
3	Overall dimensions of the machine	599 x 376 x 467 [mm]
4	Mass	11.8 Kg
5	Power consumption Normal / Warm	320/881 W
6	Ultrasound frequency	40 Khz
7	Supply voltage	220/240 V
8	Power frequency	50/60 Hz
9	Adjustable watch	yes

The temperature used for treating them was of 301K. Exposure time 20 min. The Control samples were sonicated and analyzed with a WTW Photolab Spektral spectrophotometer.

Absorbance spectra were drawn to the range of 330-850 nm wavelengths. The variants obtained are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The characteristics of the ultrasound vat HM 1005

Nr. Crt.	The controlled sample	Ultrasound treated sample without shavings	Ultrasound treated sample with oak shavings
1	V1 Plum brandy	V6 Plum brandy	V11 Plum brandy+oak shavings
2	V2 Apricot brandy	V7 Apricot brandy	V12 Apricot brandy + oak shavings
3	V3 Pear brandy	V8 Pear brandy	V13 Pear brandy + oak shavings
4	V4 Cherry brandy	V9 Cherry brandy	V14 Cherry brandy + oak shavings
5	V5 Distilled wine	V10 Distilled wine	V15 Distilled wine + oak shavings
6	The controlled sample	Ultrasound treated sample without shavings	Ultrasound treated sample with oak shavings
7	V1 Plum brandy	V6 Plum brandy	V11 Plum brandy+oak shavings

4. The results

As a result of the analyses realised we obtained the following spectra for the control samples:

Fig. 2 Spectrum for the plum brandy Control sample

Fig. 2. Spectrum for the apricot brandy Control sample

Fig. 3. Spectrum for the pear brandy Control sample

Fig. 4. Spectrum for the cherry brandy Control sample

Fig. 5. Spectrum for the distilled wine Control sample

From the first five spectrograms we can observe that all the distilled products, aged through natural methods, registered a decreasing evolution of absorbance on the 330-850 nm interval.

The only existing exception is at the sample of distilled wine where a cloud of absorbance occurred on the 330-350 nm interval. This absorbance is due to a more intensive extraction of colour compounds in the wood casks during aging and also due to a longer aging duration, of 10 years in comparison with the other samples.

Each of the five samples were treated with ultrasound to verify if there are differences in

comparison with the control samples. After the treatment we obtained the following spectrograms.

The ultrasound treatment leads to a slight reduction in colour compounds of plum brandy and a slight increase in the apricot brandy. In general, there were no major changes between the control samples and those treated with ultrasounds.

For the last 3 samples which underwent the ultrasound treatment the following results were registered; they were compared with the control samples. At the pear brandy was registered a decrease of color compounds. It also presents the most significant absorbance decrease in

comparison with the control sample from 1800nm to1500 nm.

For the cherry brandy an increase of color compounds was registered from 1200nm to 2000 nm. For the distilled wine the ultrasound treatment had no effect.

A special remark can be done after the treatment with ultrasound of the brandy samples

in which were introduced oak shavings to aging. For all the samples, significant changes in spectra were recorded.

All spectra have become similar to the spectrum for the distilled wine aged for 10 years in oak casks. The results are shown below

Fig. 6. Spectrum for the plum brandy
Ultrasound treated sample

Fig. 7. Spectrum for the apricot brandy
Ultrasound treated sample

Fig. 8. Spectrum for the pear brandy
Ultrasound treated sample

Fig. 9. Spectrum for the cherry brandy
Ultrasound treated sample

Fig. 10. Spectrum for the distilled wine
Ultrasound treated sample

Fig. 11. Spectrum for the plum brandy
Ultrasound treated sample + oak shavings

Fig. 12. Spectrum for the apricot brandy
Ultrasound treated sample + oak shavings

Fig. 13. Spectrum for the pear brandy
Ultrasound treated sample + oak shavings

Fig. 14. Spectrum for the cherry brandy
Ultrasound treated sample + oak shavings

Fig. 15. Spectrum for the distilled wine
Ultrasound treated sample + oak shavings

The results are in agreement with Monica Schwarz, 2014, who showed a similar method of aging wine distillates by treating with ultrasounds liquids in which oak chips were submerged. Based on the spectrograms obtained, it can be concluded that the treatment led to similar spectra for all the samples studied that measured both blank and sample without oak chips in wine distillate aged for 10 years[6].

Conclusions

The Based on the results obtained, this method can be used to rapidly aging fruit distillates, to

obtain similar results in terms of colorimetric samples aged for 10 years in oak barrels, but with significantly shorten the time of aging.

This method can lead to gains in efficiency, taking into account that with aging, especially over long periods of time, fruit distillates are lost on average 10-15%, depending on the length of aging.

The use of ultrasounds is a solution to shorten the maturation time.

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DETERMINATION OF UPTAKEN ELEMENT CONCENTRATIONS IN DIFFERENT PLANTS USING BY WEB BASED APPLICATION

L. VÁRALLYAI, J. THURI, B. KOVÁCS, SZ. BOTOS

Abstract: *The applied informatics undergone a significant development at the end of XXth century, which is allowed analyzing of soil pollution by computer controlled system. On account of opening of the pollution we can process the experimental data fast and exactly so we can get such a large number of new information. The environmental pollutant effect of the molybdenum was studied by elements load experiment in Nagyhorcsök Experimental Station. The relation was analyzed between the uptake of molybdenum and other micro-elements and its effect on plant organs (loaf, seed) using by different statistical methods. The aim of our investigations to search for answers on how to arable crops respond to a possible soil contamination. It is also important to determine the extent of mobilized elements from the soil into the plants, which type of effect on them, and how leach the harmful substances into deeper layers (groundwater). A computer programme based on Visual C# was developed to process of the large amount of data. The MySQL was applied to prepare the database, since we want to allow access to the newly developed database via internet technology. The data was filled up to the data tables mainly from the Excel tables. Data in internet-based databases must be properly protected. The program can provide access for two types of users at present: the database administrator who is authorised to do everything in connection with the database, and the user who is authorised to make queries only.*

Keywords: *Multidisciplinary science, Micro-elements, Pollution, Food chain, Data-processing, Hungary.*

1. Introduction

The informatics - especially applied informatics - undergone a significant development at the end of XXth century. This is allowed analyzing of soil pollution by computer controlled system. The importance of this explains the soil is polluted especially by pesticides, wastes, nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizer (Bramryd, 2013), which through plants get into our food direct and indirect way (Brännval et al., 2014). In this way polluted foods can cause ill (Liu et al., 2013) in our vitally important organs (Patócs, 1990).

On account of opening of the mentioned pollution we can process the experimental data fast and exactly so we can get such a large number of new information (Pais, 1990, Fuzesi et al., 2010). Being aware of this valuable information we can make indispensable arrangements and we can hinder the impairing micro-elements – other elements as well – segregate in food chain (Marschner, 2012). The environmental pollutant affect (Rodrigues et al., 2012a & 2012b) of the molybdenum was studied by elements load experiment in Nagyhorcsök Experimental Station. The relation was analyzed between the uptake of molybdenum and other

micro-elements (Raguža et al., 2013) and its effect on plant organs (loaf, seed) using by different statistical methods (Adamo et al., 2014).

2. Experiment Description in Nagyhorcsök Experimental Station

The trial was set up in Nagyhorcsök (Hungary) in 1991 on a calcareous chernozem soil formed on loess, containing 5% CaCO₃ and 3% humus in average in the ploughed layer. Soil texture is loamy with 20% clay and 40% fine fraction (Németh & Kádár, 2005).

Soil characteristics of the ploughed layer are: pH (KCl): 7.3, Al-P₂O₅ (ammonium lactate-soluble P₂O₅): 80-100, Al-K₂O (ammonium lactate-soluble K₂O): 140-160, KCl-Mg: 150-180, and KCl + EDTA soluble Mn, Cu and Zn are 80-150, 2-3 and 1-2 mg/kg, respectively (Jan et al., 2013). The soil is well supplied with Mn, sufficiently supplied with Mg and Cu, moderately supplied with N and K, and weakly supplied with P and Zn. The water table is at a depth of 13-15 m, which practically excludes its contamination by leaching. The climate is dry and the area is drought sensitive with 500-550 mm annual precipitation and negative water balance.

The applied treatments simulate soil contamination conditions that may occur in industrial areas, near highways, settlements and in city gardens. The 4 load levels (0, 90, 270 and 810 kg element/ha) were applied as a single dose in the spring of 1991 in the form of AlCl_3 , NaAsO_2 , BaCl_2 , CdSO_4 , K_2CrO_4 , CuSO_4 , HgCl_2 , $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24}$, NiSO_4 , $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, Na_2SeO_3 , SrSO_4 , and ZnSO_4 (Kádár, 1995).

Fertilization was done yearly with 100-100-100 kg/ha N, P_2O_5 and K_2O active agents, in the form of ammonium nitrate, superphosphate, and potash fertilizers. The $13 \times 4 = 52$ treatments with 2 replications were arranged in a split-plot design in altogether 104 plots.

Soils were sampled in 1993, 1996 and 2000 at the maximal depths of 60, 90 and 290 cm, respectively. In all cases the control and the maximal rate (810 kg/ha) treatments were analyzed.

The samples were dried at 40°C, homogenized and the ammonium acetate + EDTA-soluble element contents were analyzed by the method of Lakanen and Erviö (Lakanen & Erviö, 1971).

3. Materials and methods

The aims of the study were the determining the optimum measurement conditions for the content of elements for plant and soil samples and finding multi-element measurement method to analyze the following elements (i.e: As, Cd, Mo, Pb, and Se) and investigate (Månsson et al., 2012) the theoretical detection limit (approximately 1 ng/kg), which is nowadays the best available value (Alloway, 2012). However, the measurement of real samples which showed an unexpected factor is greatly influenced the size of the intensity on the detector.

At the time of analytical measurements could figure out that the carbon content of samples significantly depends on the size of the intensity of the same concentration. Therefore the signals is investigated on the various mass peaks (interferences). (Filep & Rékási, 2011). The investigations are carried out by different alcohols, such as C-containing solvents, this can be the reason of the above phenomenon.

Wet destruction sample preparation methods ($\text{HNO}_3\text{-H}_2\text{O}_2$) are used (Kovács et al., 2000) for the total element concentration determination of the plant and soil samples in the Central Laboratory of University of Debrecen. In case of higher concentrations - an Optima 3300 DV inductively coupled plasma optical emission

spectrometer, in case of relatively lower concentrations, an inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS) (Thermo Elemental manufactured X7-type) are used to the analytical determination (O'Sullivan et al., 2013). The analyzed elements are 45.

ICP-MS technique was used to analyze the trace element contents (As, Cd, Mo, Pb and Se) of the plants (Filep & Rékási, 2012). Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS) was used for analyses for microelements due to ppb concentrations (ug/kg). During analysis, collision and reaction gas (CCT = collisional cell technique) was applied in order to reach the lower limit of detection of elements analyzed.

The ICP-OES/MS instrument averages the measured data and calculates the deviation for each element. The measured data have to be converted, rounded and placed into a table on the basis of a certain aspect for further processing. This process takes a long time in spite of the fact that a fixed Excel macro (<http://www.excel-easy.com/vba.html>) was available at the department. Processing of the databases takes at least one hour depending on the number of measured elements and samples.

That is why new features are introduced in Visual Studio 2012 C# that improve Microsoft Office programming (Heljsberg et al., 2010). Many computer users live in the Microsoft Office suite, using Excel as the core tools to perform the majority of their daily computer tasks. Enhancements in the .NET Framework 4 and Visual Studio 2012 make Office automation solutions easier than ever to write and deploy, in either Visual C#. Visual Studio 2012 offers a number of Office templates. Choosing the Excel 2010 or 2013 Workbook template opens a blank Excel workbook template that is the spreadsheet shown when the solution is run. The Excel programming can be started from this point in Visual Studio C# environment (http://visualstudiomagazine.com/articles/2011/06/20/wcovb_automate-excel.aspx).

The MySQL (<http://www.mysql.com>) was applied to prepare the database, since we want to allow access to the newly developed database via internet technology. The data was filled up to the data tables mainly from the Excel tables. Data in internet-based databases must be properly protected. The program can provide access for two types of users at present: the database administrator who is authorised to do everything in connection with the database, and the user who

is authorised to make queries only (Szilágyi & Herdon, 2013).

4. Structure of the database

The central table is the "Meresi_adat" (measurement data)", where the "elem_id" (element_id) and the "ertek" (measured microelement concentrations) of the plant and plant part, "kezeles_tipusa" (how much dose the soil were treated), where the plant was grown are stored (Fig. 1.). It is important to store "mintavetel_ideje" (the year of the sampling).

The different plants, plant parts are stored in the other tables.

The major plants, which are investigated, the followings: carrot, maize, pea winter wheat, potato (Szilágyi & Tóth, 2015).

The plant parts are the followings: root, stem, leaf, bloom, and seed.

A stable relational database is also needed which will handle data and also provide data for the query system. Since the aims were applying standard solutions, we needed an SQL-based system and finally chose the MySQL database server (<http://www.mysql.com>), because it is free of charge, portable, compact and fast in case of bigger record numbers. Another gain, if we want to access these data through the Internet by a browser program, we can use this database system with the PHP server-side language efficiently, no need any conversion (Hu et al., 2014).

Through the authorisation system, the authorisation level of each user can easily be determined. In case of database administrator authorisation, almost any kind of query can be made in connection with the database through the general query module (Tuya et al., 2007).

Fig. 1. Database structure of the application

5. The web-based application

One of the main functions of the web application is searching measurement results. In this case we have an opportunity to configure through a wizard those features which are

necessary for getting information / data from the database. According to the Fig 2. we can give date interval to the query as filter criteria. We have to select that experiment which would like to query because the full set of data are belong to

different experiments. Therefore we have to pay attention to correct usage of data.

Query wizard

Choose the options below

Query date range

Experiment: Nagyhörcsök

Chemical: K | 213.232

Sample type: Corn

Sample type part: Leaf

Treatment type: As(III)

Treatment concentration: 30 mg/kg

[See query details](#)

Fig. 2. Query wizard of the application

Fig. 3. Query details page after the settings of query wizard

The chemical element must be chosen in which you are interested. Those elements may be chosen which are actually stored in the database related with the experiment previously selected in

order to prevent the creation of queries which do not match any records of the database.

From further selections the type of sample can be selected which can be which can be a plant or a soil sample from different depths. In the case of

the selected feature is a soil type, the options of the sample type part obviously can't be used. The same happens if the selected plant doesn't have any defined parts in the database because of the type of experiment. However the query is generally characterized by the combination of the sample type and the sample type part, but certain experiments may differ from this method.

The final step is the selection of type and concentration of the treatment. After we set the five previous options we can select from those options that belongs to that kind of data that meet the previous selection requirements such as date range, sample type etc. To finish our query settings some kind of treatment type and concentration combination must be selected.

After we set options the system checks the fulfillment of the conditions, if so, we will be redirected to the page, which contain the details of the queried results as shown in Fig. 3.

The system enables to upload such data into the database which are not closely linked to a given sample data but they may facilitate their analysis and promote the understanding of these data from a different angle.

This could be for instance the weather data. These data could be collected in two ways. Firstly by placing weather stations on areas used for experimental purposes which provides us direct access to reliable and accurate data. The other way is the use of weather APIs. Regarding the latter, although API service providers allow approximately 200 queries downloadable free of charge per day, additional costs may be involved if the sampling rate is over of it. Furthermore they are less accurate than the local weather stations since the most of these data can be measured to within kilometers, so it doesn't meet the needs of every experiment.

In the cases where such data are needed the usage of both possibilities can be considered. To upload these data into the database is optional, but if for the system data like temperature, precipitation or humidity on the basis of GPS coordinates and the specified time intervals are available, the system will also construct these diagrams on the query page.

Further data can be uploaded in addition of the sample and weather data. There are some kind of experiments which lay a greater emphasis on the analysis of soil samples. In this case we have an opportunity to place probes and sensors into or onto the soil and these pieces of equipment help researchers in collecting some further data and

we can store them in our database. These data also have spatial and time-related dimension which support us to store more data about the soil like soil moisture, soil temperature and soil pH.

The „query details” function allows us to show all charts in the same time on one page. Any combination of them can be chosen, depending on which we need. This function can be reached by buttons with different titles and glyphicons on them at the top of the page. Every button is clickable and we can easily toggle the charts with these elements. The dashed line means that the chart will be hidden by clicking on the button but will be shown by clicking again. The location and the display of our diagrams can be set easily by this function.

Usually there is a demand by researchers to have access also to usable data series from the results of queries besides the displayed charts. The chart export function – shown in Fig. 4. – is intended to satisfy this requirement and in this way researchers can put data into statistic software in order to reach more complex conclusions about them. The data can be exported in several forms such as image files (JPG, PNG), text files (XLS, CSV) or PDF format. An advantage of this function is that we can easily use these images and files to publish our results without further correction, and we can quickly analyze the exported data series in any statistical software. The function is available for each diagram separately so after the selection we can extract easily data from the queries by clicking the button in the top-right corner of the chart and in the context menu we can choose among the different file formats, but the traditional paper-based printing is also enabled.

In addition the program allows us to save query as an extra function because the data of a given query may be needed in further analysis or we would like to reuse the same queries supplemented by data since last update. In this case we can update our queries by run them again instead of creating always the same queries with setting again the same options on the wizard page. Our saved items can be reached on our profile page. By clicking on the panel header, all of previously set parameters are displayed. The quick identification of them is supported by color codes and glyphicons. Our saved query can be modified or deleted as well (Fig. 4.).

The screenshot displays a web interface for reviewing saved queries. At the top, there are tabs for 'Saved queries' and 'Personal'. Below this, two query cards are shown:

- Query 1: 2010.04.01. - 2011.04.01. | Nagyhörcsök | Corn | Root | K | 404,7210
- Query 2: 2005.11.02. - 2006.10.02. | Nagyhörcsök | Corn | Leaf | K | 766,4900

The 'Query properties' section for the second query is detailed below:

From	2005.11.02.	
To	2006.10.02.	
Experiment	Nagyhörcsök	
Sample type	Corn	
Sample type part	Leaf	
Chemical	K 766,4900	
Treatment type	Mind As(II)	
Treatment concentration	90 mg/kg	

A 'See query details' link with a bar chart icon is located to the right of the 'Query properties' section.

Fig. 4. Review saved queries page

One of the most important functions of the web application is the Data Upload function by which we have opportunity to input new data into the database after setting the properties required which are also found in the query wizard –First of all, we have to choose the experiment from the list and set the treatment and sample conditions, and we can download the pre-prepared Excel file which contains the data scheme required for uploading. We can fill it manually or by importing data from another source and in the last step of the wizard we can upload the completed file.

Users have the possibility to show preview of the uploaded Excel file for reasons of clarity and checking the data. After the verification we can click the “Done” button to finish the upload procedure (Fig. 5.) and the data will be effectively transferred to the database.

6. Summary

On the whole web application offers an opportunity to get complex information from any kind of long-term experiments. The goal of it was that we can upload various types of experiments data to the database with different parameters and properties. The web application have this kind of surface after the data inserted, which provides extensive range of searching opportunities, and we can upload measurements data one by one or in bigger series by own opinion. It allows to use of user roles which can help to handle user’s access to different functions. Additional information - like weather - can be come from third party services, like weather API’s, which will be managed by the system as it is own data. It also supports the exporting or the importing

process of the database, or the part of the database, so who has access can add or retrieve big set of data from the database if necessary.

These experimental investigates shall be carried out in several crops and elements, having regard to the interactions that each element response to changes of other elements. It is also important to better understand the mechanisms of action in the food chain and the given data has to be accurate information content.

The data are processed in a single database, perform a variety of statistical analyzes, which are extremely important for the time-series analysis in the future (Kirby et al., 2012). These long-term conclusions can be drawn in the case of soil contamination in the environment. It is important to find an effective solution for resolve the problem.

4. Upload Excel file

Please choose a file and press the "Update" button. After press the "Save" and the file upload will done!

Mérés idője	Érték	Szélesség	Hosszúság
2010.03.30	159,74	46.893972	18.644046
2010.04.03	175,32	46.893973	18.644047
2010.04.07	133,38	46.893974	18.644048
2010.04.11	106,12	46.893975	18.644049
2010.04.15	265,38	46.893976	18.644050
2010.04.19	103,56	46.893977	18.644051
2010.04.23	246,95	46.893978	18.644052
2010.04.27	168,00	46.893979	18.644053
2010.05.01	246,01	46.893980	18.644054
2010.05.05	197,71	46.893981	18.644055
2010.05.09	137,59	46.893982	18.644056
2010.05.13	256,69	46.893983	18.644057
2010.05.17	248,37	46.893984	18.644058
2010.05.21	208,25	46.893985	18.644059
2010.05.25	183,06	46.893986	18.644060
2010.05.29	242,63	46.893987	18.644061
2010.06.02	154,49	46.893988	18.644062
2010.06.06	216,59	46.893989	18.644063
2010.06.10	186,58	46.893990	18.644064
2010.06.14	162,17	46.893991	18.644065
2010.06.18	156,55	46.893992	18.644066
2010.06.22	177,48	46.893993	18.644067
2010.06.26	223,91	46.893994	18.644068
2010.06.30	199,15	46.893995	18.644069
2010.07.04	257,78	46.893996	18.644070
2010.07.08	184,18	46.893997	18.644071

Fig. 5. Upload data wizard last step

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A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF ZINC, COPPER AND HEAVY METALS CONTENT IN DIFFERENT PLANT ORGANS

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Abstract: *The purpose of this study is to realize a comparative study, especially about of content in zinc, copper and heavy metals (lead, cadmium, chromium, mercury) in various organs of vegetable plant (root, stem, leaves, flowers) like: marigold (*Calendula officinalis*), french marigold (*Tagetes patula*), nettle (*Urtica dioica*), echinacea (*Echinacea angustifolia*) using the flame atomic absorption spectrometry.*

The experimental study showed different distribution of zinc and copper depending on the plant organ and the total absence of heavy metals.

These parts of the studied plants from organic sources will be used as raw materials for making food supplements and cosmetics with good bioavailability with effect in the prevention of certain diseases.

Keywords: *flame atomic spectrometry, heavy metals, plant organs.*

1. Introduction

Mineral salts present in culture soils can be accumulate in different plant organs (roots, stems, leaves, flowers), in greater or lesser amount, being necessary for all vital forms.

Plants draw their mineral salts from the environment, for which there is interdependence between the chemical composition of soil and plant material.

Biological factors can affect the bioavailability of mineral salts, and their absorption in plants. The interference of the heavy metals with other metals can occur both in soil and in the plant, even in a differentiated way in different organs of plants. Heavy metals and other nutrients participate in materials plant to specific interactions. Although heavy metals are naturally present in the soil and increase the concentration of these elements to amounts that are harmful to both plants and animals because can be bio accumulate and they are assimilated and stocked with greater speed than are metabolized or eliminated.

Zinc is vital for the human body having a role in cell regeneration, skin and connective tissue, wound healing, immune system and not the least antioxidant free radical scavenging. Protective function of the body depends largely on the levels of zinc in the body.

Copper called "emotional" mineral is essential for physical and mental health of human body. Body's immune response depends on the balance zinc-copper. In the case of various undergoes imbalances of the human body can occur digestive or respiratory infections.

The study aims to determine the comparative content in mineral salts based on zinc and copper, as well as heavy metals (lead, cadmium, chromium, mercury) using various organs of plants (roots, stems, leaves, flowers) from organic crops by Marigold (*Calendula officinalis*), French Marigold (*Tagetes patula*), Nettle (*Urtica dioica*), Echinacea (*Echinacea angustifolia*).

The various organs of plants will be used as raw materials for the achievement of food supplements and cosmetic formulations with good bioavailability, effective in the prevention and improvement of some diseases.

2. Materials and methods

Selected plant organs are coming from organic farming, dried under spared conditions, chopped, crushed and analyzed by atomic absorption spectrometry in flame technique using a spectrophotometer GBS Avanta PM equipped with computer and cathode lamp specific at each element.

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The analyzed samples were processed by mineralization with nitric acid, hydrogen peroxide and hydrochloric acid using a Berghof MWS-2 microwave digestion system pressure.

3. Results and discussion

Plant materials (roots, stems, leaves and flowers) selected for studying the composition in Zn, Cu, and heavy metals (lead, chromium, cadmium, mercury) were characterized using absorption spectrometry in air-acetylene flame technology. The results for all the organs of plant

material (Marigold, French marigold, Nettle and Echinacea) are shown in Figure 1. To witness the absorption of minerals in the different organs of plants and soil was analyzed and the results on mineral content of culture soil from Hofigal greenhouses are shown in table 1.

In order to observe absorption of minerals in various plant organs, the organic soil from Hofigal greenhouses was analyzed to determine mineral content and the results were shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Mineral content of the crop soil

	Zn [mg/100g]	Cu [mg/100g]	Pb [mg/100g]	Cr [mg/100g]	Cd [mg/100g]	Hg [mg/100g]
Culture soil (Hofigal greenhouses)	30.0	11.0	7.0	2.0	0.0	0.0

Fig. 1 The content of Zn, Cu and heavy metals from Marigold, French Marigold, Nettle and Echinacea (root, stem, leaves, flowers)

From the graphs reproduced in Figure 1 can be noticed that the greatest amount of zinc for all studied plants is found in flowers (4.2 - 7.6), followed by leaves (3.5-4.5), root (2.3-4.1) and strain (1.1-2.8). Largest zinc accumulation is in

Marigold flowers and Nettle. As we can see the copper content is missing in all plant organs of Marigold and Nettle leaves and stems of French Marigold and Echinacea. The copper content was highlighted in the roots and flowers of French

Marigold and Echinacea (<1 in flowers and <2 root).

As shown in Table 1, the soil analyzed shows besides Zn and Cu, there are quantities of heavy metals below the allowed limit. The plants studied have not accumulated in their root, stem, leaves and flowers heavy metals which gives them the quality of organic plant material.

3. Conclusions

In order to obtain food supplements and cosmetics products with high bioavailability were selected organs of plants (root, stem, leaves, flowers) from Marigold, French marigold, Echinacea and Nettle.

A comparative study was realized to determine the composition in beneficial minerals (zinc, copper) and heavy metals (lead, chromium, cadmium, mercury) using the atomic absorption technique flame spectrometry.

Experimental study showed different distribution of zinc and copper (minerals beneficial to human body) depending on body plant and the total absence of heavy metals knowing the fact that they have an effect harmful to the body by blocking the enzymatic reactions and accelerate the oxidation of vitamins A and E from food.

These parts of the studied plants will be used as raw materials for making bio-available food supplements in preventing and improvement

effect of prostate diseases and their use for obtaining a range of cosmetic-acting anti acne.

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BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS FROM MUSHROOMS: POTENTIAL TO DEVELOP FUNCTIONAL FOOD PRODUCTS

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Abstract: For centuries mushrooms have been used not only for their nutritional value but also for healing potential. At present there are at least 300 species of mushroom that are known to have various therapeutic properties, which can be used as dietary supplements or for fortification of food with functional compounds. Besides well known immune modulating and anti-cancer properties, mushrooms possess other valuable properties including antioxidant, anti-hypertensive, cholesterol-lowering, liver protection, anti-obesity, anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, anti-microbial and some others. Mushrooms also can be a source of various enzymes useful for food industry.

Keywords: Mushrooms, bioactive components, immunomodulators, antimicrobial hypocholesterolic, antidiabetic, hepatoprotective, antioxidant activity, milk-clotting.

1. Introduction

Mushrooms contain a large variety of bioactive compounds that are greatly under researched. Potential contribution of mushrooms in various fields, including the food industry are considerably untapped.

Bioactive compounds of mushroom origin with immune modulating, antibacterial and antioxidant activities can be used as functional and anti-microbial food and animal feed supplements. As functional food supplements can be used mushroom derived substances with hypocholesterolic, hypolipidemic hepatoprotective, antidiabetic, and some other activities, while alcohol dehydrogenase could be used for wine and beer production, milk-clotting enzymes can find utilization in cheese making to substitute animal rennin.

Mushrooms are not a taxonomic group, but include about 14000 species which have macroscopic fruit-bodies, seen by the naked eye. They are highly evaluated for their nutritional value and many are viewed as functional foods.

The protein content in mushrooms is much higher than in most vegetables and somewhat less than in meat and milk. Mushrooms contain all essential amino acids, but the content of methionine and cysteine can be not sufficient. They are rich in dietary fiber, and therefore, calorific value of most of mushrooms is low. They are also a good source of vitamins, especially thiamine (B₁), riboflavin (B₂), niacin,

biotin and ascorbic acid. Certainly, edible mushrooms represent a nutritious and tasteful source of food and can be important dietary component for vegetarians.

However, long ago people recognized that mushrooms could have important health benefits. The most of traditional knowledge on mushrooms bioactive properties comes from the Far East Asia.

Historically, mushrooms were collected from the wild for eating and for medicinal use. China has been the source of many of mushrooms early cultivations, since 600 AD (*Auricularia auricular* - the "Jelly ear"). White button mushroom (*Agaricus bisporus*) was first cultivated in France in 17th century while Oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) was first grown in US in 20th. While mushroom cultivation now spans many centuries, it is only over the last 4-5 decades that there have been major expansions in basic research and practical knowledge leading to the formation of a major global industry.

In the second half of 20th century technologies for mushroom cultivation were strongly developed, and at the beginning of 21st century the overall value of the world's mushroom production was estimated to be over \$ 45 billion (1).

An even more promising method of mushroom production is submerge cultivation of mycelia, which is a more efficient way to attain the biomass of basidiomycetes that possess almost same valuable properties as the fruit bodies.

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Native liquid of mushroom cultivation is rich with extracellular enzymes, vitamins, polysaccharides and other valuable substances and could be a source of bioactive compounds.

At the present, there are more than 300 mushroom species that are known to have various bioactive properties. Today, on the world pharmaceutical and food markets large amount arsenal of mushroom products and compounds exist, which are representing so called "nutriceutics" or "functional food additives." When used for a curative means, mushrooms are normally consumed as powdered concentrates or extracts in hot water. The extracts can be used as a drink, freeze-dried, or spray-dried to form granular powders, which allow for easier handling, packaging, transportation and consumption (2). These liquid concentrates or dried powdered mushroom extracts can be placed in capsule and then can be considered as dietary supplements or mushroom nutriceuticals with potential health benefits (3). And many of these bioactive substances can be used to fortify common food products to give them functional properties.

While there is a great deal of attention focused on the various immunological and anti-cancer properties of mushrooms (2,4), they can also offer other potentially important therapeutic properties including antioxidants, anti-hypertensive, cholesterol-lowering, liver protection, anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, antiviral, anti-microbial and others (5-8).

Immune modulating and anti-tumor effect

The main anti-tumor compounds currently isolated from mushrooms have been identified as either water soluble β -D-glucans, β -D-glucans with heterosaccharide chains of xylose, mannose, galactose or uronic acid or β -D-glucan-protein complexes – proteoglycans, which can induce immune modulatory and therapeutic effect in animals and humans.

The main chain of basic β -D-glucan is either β 1-3, β 1-4 or mixed β 1-3, β 1-4 with β 1-6 side chains of different sizes occurring at various intervals (9). Levels of activity of these compounds can be related to their size, degree of branching, molecular weight and solubility in water. Some of this compounds, referred to as biological response modifiers.

These mushroom substances are able to influence non-specific and specific immune responses of an organism and activate different types of immune competent cells, such as monocytes, neutrophils, cytotoxic macrophages,

natural killer cells, dendritic cells, cytokins, interferons, and lymphocytes.

Immune stimulation during cancer can be beneficial in terms of tumor regression and patients' survival (10).

Results published by N. Kodama et al. suggest a mechanism of action a low-molecular-weight protein fraction from the fruiting body of the maitake mushroom *Grifola frondosa* in which NK cells are activated through cytokines produced by antigen-presenting cells (11).

Ganoderma. lucidum modulates the immune system, including, for example, antigen-presenting cells, natural killer (NK) cells, and the T and B lymphocytes. It also promoted phagocytosis by macrophage from peripheral blood mononuclear cell (PBMC) and it also promoted natural killer cell activity. It decreased the percentage of leukemia cells in the spleens of mice before they were injected with WEHI-3 cells. Apparently, *G. lucidum* affects murine leukemia WEHI-3 cells in vivo (12).

Research, conducted in City of Hope National Medical Center and Beckman Research Institute, Duarte California suggests adding about one serving of white button mushrooms (*Agaricus bisporus*) a day to the diet of men with previously diagnosed with prostate cancer can decrease PSA levels, a key indicator of tumor growth (13).

Oral administration of mushroom extracts were significantly increasing the survival rates of mice with very malignant tumors of Melanoma-B16 and Ehrlich's ascid carcinoma (14).

Research into underlying mechanisms of mushrooms will continue to help in devising new strategies for treating cancer, preventing its long-term complications, and increasing survival (15).

Cardiovascular and Cholesterol-lowering effect

Hypercholesterolemia increases the risk of cardiovascular diseases and is among the major risk factors for human health in developed countries. Elevated levels of circulating cholesterol cause deposits to form inside blood vessels. These deposits can result in a disease process called arteriosclerosis.

Cholesterol has been divided into two major categories: low-density lipoprotein (LDL) and very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL), the so-called "bad" cholesterol, and high-density lipoprotein (HDL), the so-called "good" cholesterol.

The first steps in the prevention and treatment of hypercholesterolemia and related

cardiovascular diseases is the development of the nutritional regime with a diet low in fats and saturated fatty acids and rich in crude fibers. Mushrooms, due to their high fiber content and low calorific value, are suitable for diets designed to prevent cardiovascular diseases.

Being rich in dietary fiber, some mushrooms also can produce substances, inhibiting cholesterol syntheses. A major rate-limiting step in the biosynthetic pathway for cholesterol formation is at the level of the microsomal enzyme 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl-coenzyme A reductase (HMG-CoA reductase) that catalyses the reductions of HMG-CoA into mevalonate.

Some species from the genus *Pleurotus* are capable to produce mevinolin (lovastatin), which was the first specific inhibitor of the HMG-CoA reductase to receive approval for the treatment of hypocholesteremia.

Eritadenine, a compound extracted from *Lentinus edodes* is also able to lower blood serum cholesterol. Probably, eritadenine lowers cholesterol by decreasing the ratio of phosphatidylcholine to phosphatidylethanolamine in liver microsomes.

The addition of dried fruit bodies or submerge mycellium of some other mushrooms to a high cholesterol diet effectively reduced cholesterol accumulation in the serum and liver of experimental rats redistributing cholesterol in favor of HDL, reduced production of VLDL and LDL cholesterol, reduced cholesterol absorption and reduced HMG-CoA reductase activity in the liver and triglyceride level in blood serum. (16-18).

Hepatoprotective effects

Mushrooms are considered to be beneficial for a wide range of hepato disorders, including hepatitis. Several compounds isolated fruit body, mycelia and spores of *Ganoderma lucidum*, such as, Ganoderic acids, ganosporic acid A were shown to have strong antihepatotoxic activity.

A polysaccharide fraction from *Lentinus edodes* showed liver protective action in animals together with improved liver function and an increased production of antibodies to hepatitis B (2). There have been other interesting medical reports concerning to distinct improvement with patients suffering from cirrhosis of the liver and chronic hepatitis B with extracts or polysaccharides from *Dendropolyporus umbellatus*, *Schizophyllum commune*, *Trametes versicolor*, *Poria cocos*, *Tremella fuciformis* and others.

Metabolic syndrome, which comprises a cluster of metabolic abnormalities, such as hyperlipidemia, diabetes mellitus, and hypertension, is a widespread and increasingly prevalent disease in industrialized countries and contributes to the increase in cardiovascular morbidity and mortality (19, 20). Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is often associated with features of metabolic syndrome and is emerging as the most common liver disease worldwide (21, 22). Research conducted by Japanese scientists showed that Mukitake mushroom (*Panellus serotinus*) supplementation is beneficial for the alleviation of NAFLD and dyslipidemia in obese, diabetic ob/ob mice (23).

Antidiabetic effect

Extracts of several higher fungi, including *Tremella aurantia*, *Cordyceps sinensis*, *Ganoderma lucidum*, *Auricularia auricula-judae*, *Lentinus edodes*, *Pleurotus ostreatus*, *Phellinus linteus* and others have been shown to lower blood glucose triglyceride levels. Such results strongly suggest that these mushrooms have potential preventive and therapeutic action in diabetes mellitus (type I and II).

Antidiabetic activity of *Grifola frondosa* is related to the process of metabolism of adsorbed glucose. The blood glucose lowering effect is thought to be a result of a high molecular weight glycoprotein.

The consumption of *P. ostreatus* produced a significant hypoglycemic effect in diabetic mice (24) and it is capable of improving hyperlipidemia and the impaired kidney functions in alloxan-induced diabetic mice (25).. Ethanolic extract of *P. ostreatus* showed a significant decrease in serum glucose level Thus, indicating that the ethanolic extract of *P. ostreatus* could be added in the list of medicinal preparations beneficial in diabetes mellitus. (25).

In other study *Ganoderma lucidum* extract exhibited good dose-dependent inhibitory activity against α -glycosidase with and also exhibited aldose reductase inhibitory potential. *Tremella fuciformis* demonstrated high aldose reductase inhibitory activity (26).

Anti-obesity effects

Obesity is currently associated with low-grade chronic inflammation and intestinal dysbacteriosis. It was shown, that a water extract of *Ganoderma lucidum* mycelium reduces body weight, inflammation and insulin resistance in mice fed a high-fat diet (27). Obtained results indicate that *G. lucidum* and its high molecular weight polysaccharides may be used as prebiotic

agents to prevent gut dysbacteriosis and obesity-related metabolic disorders in obese individuals (27).

Anti-obesity and triglyceride lowering effect has been reported for fermented milk product containing edible mushroom water extracts (mushroom yogurt) (28). The anti-obesity activity of maitake mushroom (*Grifola frondosa*) has been demonstrated in both animals and humans (29).

A group of Korean scientists investigated the anti-obesity effects of *Lentinus edodes* water extract powder in mice fed a high fat diet. Consumption of high fat diet caused increases in body weight, serum lipid profiles, and adipose tissue weights. Serum total cholesterol and total triglyceride levels in the mushroom extract powder-supplemented groups were lower than those in the Control group. Supplementation with 5% mushroom extract significantly suppressed body weight gain and reduced the weight of subcutaneous adipose tissue compared to the high fat diet group. High fat diet ingestion resulted in higher lipid content and increased lipid peroxidation in the liver. However, *Lentinus edodes* water extract powder supplementation inhibited accumulation of hepatic lipids induced by high fat diet, considerably decreased malondialdehyde levels, and elevated total antioxidant activity in the livers of mice. Histopathological analysis indicated that the livers of mice fed high fat diet developed hepatic steatosis, whereas mushroom extract-treated groups showed small fat droplets. These results suggest that long-term supplementation with *L. edodes* water extract powder may also have an ameliorating effect on high fat diet-induced obesity (30).

Anti-obesity activity effect of polysaccharides in the water-soluble fraction from edible mushroom Hinmogi (*Tremella fuciformis*) demonstrated inhibitory effects on 3T3-L1 adipocyte differentiation, peroxisome proliferators-activated receptor γ translation in 3T3-L1 cells was. In addition, treatment of polysaccharides to 3T3-L1 cells significantly inhibited the triglyceride accumulation, Oil Red-O staining, and mRNA expression of PPAR γ , C/EBP α , and leptin in a dose-dependent manner. Based upon these results, it is possible to resume, that studied polysaccharides can be used as a potential anti-obesity material (31).

Antimicrobial effects

Various antitumour polysaccharides from medicinal mushrooms would be expected to

function by mobilising the body's humoral immunity to protect from viral, bacterial, fungal and protozoal infections resistant to current antibiotics.

Several mushroom polysaccharides have shown antiviral activity against ectromelia virus and cytomegalovirus infections (4). Lentinan, commercial β -D-glucan preparation from *L. edodes*, has shown antiviral activity in mice against vesicular stomatitis virus, encephalitis virus, Abelson virus, an adenovirus type 12, stimulated non-specific resistance against respiratory viral infection in mice, conferred complete protection against an LD75 challenge dose of virulent mouse influenza A/SW15, increased resistance to the protozoal parasites, exhibited activity against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* bacilli resistant to antituberculosis drugs, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Candida albicans* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, increased host resistance to infections with potentially lethal *Listeria monocytogenes* (16).

Sulfated Schizophyllan polysaccharide (*Schizophyllum commune*) displayed strong anti-HIV activity while the anti-tumour effect was reduced or lost. Schizophyllan has also been reported to enhance protection against *Staphylococcus* sp. infection.

Extensive examination of over 200 species of Basidiomycetes in Spain demonstrated that almost 50% had significant direct antibiotic activity against a range of test organisms. It is interesting to note that the bracket polypore *Piptoporus betulinus* carried by the historic Iceman displayed a high broad spectrum antibiotic activity.

Lentinus edodes extracts can improve the beneficial intestinal flora of the gut, the effective factor in the extract is considered to be the trehalose, and reduce the harmful effects of certain bacterial enzymes such as α -glucosidase, α -glucuronidase and tryptophanase as well as reducing colon cancer formation (16).

Antioxidant activity

Antioxidants play a very important role in protecting the body from the formation of free radicals. Therefore, it becomes very important for many to supplement their diet with compounds rich of antioxidants.

It was shown that mushroom extracts and polysaccharides can decrease the production of oxygen free radicals. Significant superoxide and hydroxyl radical scavenging activities have been demonstrated for several mushroom antitumour

polysaccharides (16). Methanolic extracts of various edible mushrooms also show various kinds of antioxidant activities (32).

Recent studies of Serbian scientists show, that *Agaricus* species can be a source of antioxidant, antimicrobial and anti-quorum sensing compounds (33).

Nerve tonic activity

Nerve growth factors (NGF) called Erinacins (series of diterpenoids) and hericenones (a class of benzyl alcohol) were isolated from the fruit bodies, mycelia and culture broth of *Hericium erinaceum* and were stimulating nerve growth factor synthesis. The erinacines are the most powerful inducers of NGF synthesis among all currently identified natural compounds.

ENZYMES USEFUL IN FOOD INDUSTRY

Higher basidial mushrooms can represent an interest for the food industry, not only as a source of biologically active supplements, but also as a source of useful enzymes.

Milk clotting enzymes from higher basidiomycetes are a promising source to substitute rennin in cheese making.

The quality of cheese significantly depends from enzyme preparations which are used for milk clotting. Mostly animal enzymes extracted from rennet are used for these purposes. Requirements for the substitutes of the rennet are strict and specific - their enzymatic properties must maximally approach those of accepted as the standard natural rennin, i.e. together with the high milk-clotting activity they must possess the insignificant general proteolytic activity, which leads to the unspecific proteolysis of the proteins of casein.

Highly active proteases of rennet action are discovered in the higher basidiomycetes and some of them found practical use.

In 1970th M. Kawai and N. Mukai reported, that *Irpex lacteus* and *Flamulina velutipes* mushrooms could be a promising rennet substitute for cheese-making (34).

In later studies these results were confirmed by other researchers (35,36).

A peptidase of *Piptoporus soloniensis* showed a milk clotting activity similar to chymosin from milk calves (37). Promising results were reported also for several other mushroom species (38-40).

Some genera of mushrooms produce alcohol dehydrogenase, and made wine, beer and sake using mushrooms in place of *S. cerevisiae*. The highest alcohol concentrations in the wine, beer and sake were achieved with *Pleurotus ostreatus*, *Tricholoma matsutake* and *Agaricus blazei*. In

the case of wine made using *A. blazei*, the same alcohol concentration was produced under both aerobic and anaerobic conditions. This wine produced by *A. blazei* contained about 0.68% β -D-glucan, which is known to have preventive effects against cancer. The wine made using *F. velutipes* showed thrombosis-preventing activity, giving a prolonged thrombin clotting time 2.2-fold that of the control. Thus, alcoholic beverages made using mushrooms seem to be a functional food source which can be expected to have preventive effects against cancer and thrombosis (41).

Conclusions

Mushrooms are a promising source for the food industry, but their full potential is not yet unlocked. Their possibilities and utilization are tremendous, especially, for those products taken from submerge cultivation of higher mushrooms as bioactive food supplements and as a source of valuable enzymes.

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ICT IN AGRICULTURE IN ASPECT OF REGIONAL DIFFERENCES

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Abstract: *The new ICT technologies are not only fast developed but, in addition, are giving birth to newer systems and tools. The agriculture has some speciality in information technology. The ICT adoption in the agriculture and main drivers has been examined. To get a draft overview of Hungarian position there is part about it. In this part there are data about household communication devices the individuals ICT usage. The region differences in information technologies can be seen also. The final part of the paper there are some technology examples. Cloud Computing provides better resource management and effective cost control. However, the business assessment of these technologies must not be done only on the basis of the technology and taken out of its environment randomly since the whole area is very complex.*

Keywords: *ICT, agriculture, regions, ICT adoption.*

1. Introduction

The development of information technology has had a considerable influence on the agriculture of highly industrialised nations as well. There have emerged a number of new industry-specific technologies and applications over the past few years, including the ever-widening agricultural application of mobile communications devices and technologies.

Further considerable improvement is expected in the use of the Tablets as well as other mobile devices. Providing high broadband and mobile Internet access for every individual, especially for those living in rural areas (e-Rural), is among the first priorities of the European Union's research and development programme for Information Society Technologies (IST).

According to research-developmental and application trends, as well as forecasts and expectations, these technologies and services are to become widely applied tools in enhancing business innovations and supporting business management. The focus of this research was those Internet applications based on mobile devices and the assessment of their effects on agriculture. Due to the fact that the development of applications and user applications require wide-ranging condition and effect systems, the investigation of several condition and effect mechanisms and research tasks were carried out.

1.1. The aim of the research

The subject of this paper to answer what is the up to date ICT drivers and condition in the field of agriculture. The other subject is to draft the possible social and "digital gap" condition in the agriculture. In this paper, the ICT is taken as a possible management support tool, and we are looking for the answer of what factors and drivers are important in the agriculture. The following issues could be examined here:

- what are the drivers of ICT in agriculture,
- what are the key lessons related to ICT in agriculture,
- what is the possible ICT condition (devices, services) in Hungary,
- what trends can be observed in the mobile devices.

The aim of this research is as the ICT means a management support in the agriculture, and the new ICT solutions can be observed in the agriculture.

1.2. The methods of the research

The examination of the subject is interdisciplinary. It has social and scientific references, so a complex approach was needed. The main research method was the analytical way, several analytical methods and approaches were selected. The data collection were relied on the available Hungarian related reports from the

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Hungarian Central Statistical Office, and the international data from Statistical Office of the European Communities, and the OECD. We are managed to process the ICT market reports and the international scientific works.

2. The ICT in Hungary.

This data was relied on the available Hungarian Central Statistical Office ICT report (KSH, 2015).

There are some kind of computer devices (desktop PC, laptop, handheld) near half of Hungarian households. There are desktop PC-s in the 56% and laptop in the 40% of the households. In Hungary the Internet is available in 70% of the households (Fig. 1).

The most of household Internet connection are cable, broadband mobile and ADSL.

Fig. 1. The Hungarian households ICT device proportion (KSH, 2014)

2.1. The ICT usage of the individuals related to the regional difference

In 2014 78.9% of the population are used computer ever. 76.0 % of the population are used computer within 3 months.

The computer users are mainly secondary and higher educated, but the elementary educated users number is increasing. The figure shows that the ICT usage is related to the level of personal education, but the difference in years before were bigger.

Fig. 2. The computer user's rate related to the region population (KSH, 2015)

The Central Hungary region's computer users rate is higher than others, but the lowest regions computer users rate is higher the two-third of the regional population.

2.2. The regional difference on ICT

The regions difference on ICT can be seen on Table 1. The rank number is counted by the mobile phone, computer, Internet and broadband

Internet access. The first in the list is Central Hungary, the second is Western Transdanubia and the third is Central Transdanubia. The Southern Great Plain and Northern Great Plain are the last on the list. If we count the number of agricultural worker, the list is the following Table 2. In those region where the rate of agricultural worker is relatively high (except Central Hungary) the ICT usage is lower.

Table 1. The Hungarian regions rank in ICT (KSH, 2015)

ICT device	Northern Hungary	Northern Great Plain	Southern Great Plain	Central Hungary	Central Transdanubia	Western Transdanubia	Southern Transdanubia
Mobile phone	7	5	4	1	3	2	6
Computer	4	5	7	2	3	1	6
Internet access	5	7	6	1	2	3	4
Broadband Internet	4	7	6	1	2	3	5

Table 2. The Hungarian regions rank by agricultural workers (KSH, 2015)

Region name	Rate of agricultural worker	Rank
Northern Hungary	2,93%	6
Northern Great Plain	5,19%	3
Southern Great Plain	6,42%	1
Central Hungary	0,75%	7
Central Transdanubia	3,86%	4
Western Transdanubia	3,33%	5
Southern Transdanubia	6,35%	2

Table 3. Region's Internet subscribers data (TEIR, 2015)

Name of the region	Number of Internet subscribers	Internet subscribers / Population	
	Rank	Ratio	Rank
Southern Great Plain	4	28,20%	7
Southern Transdanubia	7	30,25%	4
Northern Great Plain	2	28,94%	6
Northern Hungary	5	29,93%	5
Central Transdanubia	3	37,06%	2
Central Hungary	1	41,17%	1
Western Transdanubia	6	35,64%	3

In those region where the rate of agricultural worker is relatively high (except Central Hungary) the ICT usage is lower.

It is quite interesting to examine the regions Internet subscriber's number shown by Table 3. It is not surprise that Central Hungary has the highest subscriber number. The Southern Transdanubia and Western Transdanubia have the lowest subscribers. If we divide the subscribers number with the region's population

number the rank of the regions change. Central Hungary still the first, but Southern and Northern Great Plain are the last in the list.

3. New technology possibilities

Certainly education, training and e-services play a very important role for ICT adoption by Agriculture and related areas (Herdon and Lengyel, 2008). The easy access of the

information, knowledge and e-services is a key factor in agricultural.

To refer to a few examples of these innovations affecting Agriculture and Environmental Sciences: Cloud Computing provides equality in resources management and exploitability.

The use of cloud computing is getting more and more popular in agriculture. The five universal values of cloud computing are the following:

- Reduction of initial costs,
- Allocation of resources on demand without limit,
- Maintenance and upgrades performed in the back-end,
- Easy rapid development including collaboration with other system in the cloud,
- More possibilities for global service development.

4. ICT adoption in the agriculture

The information and communication technologies (ICTs) in the extension services and rural development projects takes an important role. The ICT usable for long term (for example electronic education for rural areas) and as well as short term (for example local market price and weather information) cases. The ICT can be used for help to collect and share the existing human capital. The usage of mobile phones can improve the private and the public information share. The mobile technology can provide better agricultural information services at lower cost and higher quality. (Dethier and Effenberger, 2012). The Hungarian practice seem to be similar to the international practice (Botos et al, 2015; Varallyai, Herdon, 2013).

4.1. The key lessons related to ICT in agriculture

The following key lessons are important for the successful ICT adaptation (World Bank, 2011):

- **Concentrate on the demand, not on the technology** - The new technologies in any project require the farmer's active contribution from the start.
- **Use appropriate technologies** - Sometimes the newest ICT not the best possible solution, maybe the mixture of several existing technologies is better.

- **Focus on affordable access and use, not ownership** - In agriculture the accessibility and useable technology are preferred.
- **Be aware of differential impacts, including gender and social differences in access and use** - The wrong use of ICT can worsen the economic, social, and political inequalities.
- **Create an enabling environment for innovation in infrastructure investment, business models, services, and applications** - The effective design and transparent implementation of policies and regulations for ICT infrastructure, tools, and services is key to enabling ICT development.
- **Develop sustainable business and investment models through partnerships** - Public and private partnerships are essential to the long-term viability of ICT in agriculture.

4.2. Key pillars of national digital economy strategies

The following list reflects the key pillars of many present national digital strategies, with the majority emphasising demand-side objectives (OECD, 2015):

- **Further develop telecommunications infrastructure and preserve the open internet.**
- **Promote the ICT sector including its internationalisation.**
- **Strengthen e-government services including enhanced access to public sector information) and data.**
- **Advance e-inclusion with a focus on the aging population and disadvantaged social groups.**
- **Promote ICT-related skills and competences including basic ICT skills and ICT specialist skills.**

5. Conclusion

Communication technologies and broadband Internet are increasingly perceived as a critical factor in social and economic development. They provide their connectivity for a range of innovative applications in areas like electronic health services, e-government, and of course in the agriculture. Focusing on ITC the key drivers and the main factors of it there are special

applications and requirements in this area, and sometimes the social factors are more important than technology. Giving a brief overview about the Hungarian ICT position and the differences in personal usage and regions.

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RESEARCH OF MICROBIOLOGICAL EXPERTISE OF DRINKING WATER BY COUNTING E. COLI AND COLIFORM BACTERIA USING MEMBRANE FILTRATION METHOD

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Abstract: For drinking water microbiological expertise we performed laboratory analysis in accordance with ISO 9308-1: 2014, which refers to the method of counting *Escherichia coli* and coliform bacteria in samples with low bacterial flora, based on membrane filtration technique, further culturing membranes on chromogenic agar for coliforms (CCA) and counting microorganisms in the sample target. Coliforms and *Escherichia coli*, are present in large quantities in human and animals feces, being considered an indicator for the integrity and cleanliness of the distribution systems and for the potential presence of biofilms, their presence indicating an inadequate treatment, the formation of biofilm through the intrusion of foreign material (soil, plants) in the distribution system and water tanks. The presence of *Escherichia coli* / coliform thermotolerants involves investigative actions of potential sources such as inadequate water treatment or distribution system breaches existence. The results interpretation was done using special formulas for calculation, and the results were reported to the Law. 311/2004 amending and supplementing Law no. 458/2002 on drinking water quality.

Keywords: drinking water, coliform bacteria, *Escherichia coli*

1. Introduction

The Drinking water for human consumption is any kind of water, naturally occurred or after treatment, used for drinking, food preparation, or for other domestic purposes, regardless of its origin and whether it is supplied through distribution network, tank or it is distributed in bottles or other containers.

Drinking water also is represented by all the water used in the food industry as a source for the manufacturing, processing, preservation or marketing of products or substances intended for human consumption, and water coming from local sources (wells, springs, etc.) used for drinking, cooking or other domestic purposes.

Regardless of origin, the water is never sterile. Water sources, due to negligence, may be contaminated with sewage or water from sewerage systems, in human or animal agglomerations and, the presence of pathogens is almost a rule. (8,9,10,11)

Most important pathogenic microorganisms that can contaminate water and entails a modification of food sanitation status are from the family of *Enterobacteriaceae* bacteria (*Salmonella spp.*, *Campylobacter jejuni*, *Yersinia enterocolitica*, *Escherichia coli*, coliforms), fecal

streptococci, *Listeria monocytogenes*, some viruses (*Hepatitis A*), etc.

Coliform bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Citrobacter*, *Klebsiella*, *Arizona*, *Enterobacter*) - members of *Enterobacteraceae* Family, including a wide range of aerobic and facultative anaerobic bacteria; are β -D-galactosidase-positive, have the form of bacilli and coccobacillus, are Gram-negative, bipolar, ensporulate, oxidase negative, capable of growth under aerobic conditions and facultative anaerobes in the presence of bile salts, which ferment lactose with the production of acid and aldehyde after 24-48 hours of incubation at 36 ± 2 °C.

Bacteria of the genus *Escherichia*, *Citrobacter*, *Klebsiella*, *Enterobacter*, *Serratia*, *Hafnia* - fecal origin species (human and animal) and from the environment (capable of multiplying in soil and ground water) are an indicator of the cleanliness and integrity of distribution systems and the potential presence of biofilms. (1)

Escherichia coli - is different from other thermotolerant coliforms by: the ability to produce indole from tryptophan and β -glucuronidase enzyme production after incubation at 44 ± 0.5 ° in 21 ± 3 hours. It is present in large amounts in human and animal feces and rarely in tropical soils. It is considered the best indicator of faecal

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contamination. Therefore in case of doubt, for further confirmation, it can be done by checking the indole test, lactose fermentation, using citrate as sole carbon source. (2,3,4,5,6,7).

In our country the monitoring of drinking water quality is based on two types of monitoring programs: one of control and another of audit. (8)

By the manufacturer monitoring control is checked periodically the organoleptic and microbiological quality of drinking water produced and distributed, and the effectiveness of treatment processes, focusing on technology disinfection in order to determine if drinking water is adequate or not, in terms of relevant parameters, by the items of Law No.458 / 2002 as amended by Law no.311 / 2004.

By audit monitoring is verified that drinking water meets quality requirements and specifications for all parameters stipulated in the Law No.458 / 2002 as amended by Law 311/2004, including additional parameters imposed in sanitary authorization.(12)

2. Material and method

For the detection of coliforms and *E.coli* in drinking water we have conducted laboratory tests in accordance with ISO 9308-1: 2014 which refers to the method of counting *E.coli* and coliform bacteria in drinking water, based on membrane filtration technique, further membrane culturing on chromogenic agar for coliforms (CCA) and counting of target microorganisms in the sample.

Due to the low selectivity of the used culture environment, flora association can interfere with target bacteria (*E. coli* and coliform bacteria), which is why this method is suitable for waters with low bacterial flora, whose load does not exceed about 100 cfu total bacterial flora, such as drinking water or decontaminated water in pools or the finished product of water purification stations.

The principle of the method consists in filtering a known amount quantity of the sample through a bacteria-retaining membrane and its location on the surface of the agar CCA; incubating the plates at 36 ± 2 ° C for 21 ± 3 hours; counting the β -D- galactosidase positive colonies (pink-red), considered presumptive coliforms, which are not considered as *E. coli*. To avoid false positive results, caused by positive oxidase bacteria (*Aeromonas spp.*, for example), the presumptive colonies must be confirmed by oxidase test, which must be negative. Counting of colonies β -D-galactosidase and β -D-glucuronidase positive (dark blue, to purple) considered *E. coli*. Total coliform bacteria are the sum of colonies pink or red, oxidase negative and dark blue or purple.

Equipment and supplies that we used to make the diagnosis were: required autoclave for wet sterilization; thermostat set at 36 ± 2 ° C; pH-meter with accuracy of $\pm 0,1$ at 20-25 °C; membrane filtration equipment - membrane filtration system consisting of three filtration posts with metal filters and funnels of 100 ml capacity, used for water membrane filtration; individual sterile filtration membranes from cellulose esters, with a diameter between 47- 50 mm and having pores with a diameter of 0,45 mm, provided with grids; test tube racks; stainless steel tweezers with rounded ends, smooth edge without streaking for handling membranes; filter paper, protective equipment (gown, gloves); decontaminant solution.

Inside workspaces we have secured an ambient temperature of 20-22°C (by turning the warm climate). We conducted the work operations in the hood and in the gas flame. We introduced in the the hood the needed materials: glassware, sterile filtration membranes, sterile Petri dishes, glassware flask with decontaminant. Before work starting we proceeded to hood cleaning with alcohol, then sterilization by UV for 30 minutes. (Fig. 1 and 2).

Fig. 1. Filtration equipment located in

Fig. 2. Membrane filter the hood

Use Culture media and reagents used were: agar chromogenic for coliforms (CCA), distributed in Petri dishes in a layer of at least 4 mm, agar tryptone soy (TSA), oxidase reagent, tryptophan broth, Kovacs reagent.

To ensure the quality of the results we used positive and negative controls to optimize the accuracy of the results. We also checked the performance of CCA agar according to ISO

11133 as follows: the environment productivity testing using reference strains of *E. coli* that must form dark blue or purple colonies and *C. freundii* and *E. aerogenes*, which is to form pink or red colonies; environmental selectivity by using a reference strain of *E. faecalis* whose growth is completely inhibited; specific environment by using a reference strain of *P. aeruginosa*, which form colorless colonies.

Fig. 3. CCA Culture mediu

The work stages were: sample preparation for analysis within 24 hours under refrigeration ($5 \pm 3^\circ \text{C}$); filtering using the system, we filtered 100 or 250 ml of bottled water, through the membrane previously located on the membrane filtering support; incubation and differentiation - after filtration, the membrane is set on chromogenic agar plate for coliforms (CCA),

ensuring that no air bubbles is formed under it, incubation at $36 \pm 2^\circ \text{C}$ for 21 ± 3 hours; examination of membrane separation and counting the colonies giving a positive β - D - galactosidase reaction (pink to red), as presumptive coliform bacteria, wich are not *E. coli*. (Fig. No. 4,5,6,7).

Fig. 4,5. The location of the filtermembrane on the support

Fig. 6. Pouring water samples to be filtered

Fig. 7. The location of the membranes culture medium surface

3. Results and discussions

To expertise by laboratory testing by counting *E. coli* and coliforms using membrane filtration method in the period 01.01.2015 - 04.30.2016, we proceeded to examine a number of 347

samples taken from processing, extracting and bottling units, from the counties of Braşov, Prahova, Covasna and Mureş, as follows: (Table. 1 and Chart no. 1)

Table 1. Number of water samples analyzed

Number of examined samples								Total samples		
Braşov		Prahova		Covasna		Mureş		Total	From wich	
P*	Î*	P	Î	P	Î	P	Î		P	Î
246	21	-	23	42	5	10	-	347	298	49

Chart 1. Number of water samples analyzed

Harvesting, preservation, identification, transportation and storage of water samples were carried out under Law No 458/2002 as amended by Law no.311 / 2004 and 2852/1993 STAS acquis.

When determining the frequency of sampling, processing units and the extraction and bottling units took into account the following: the amount of inadequate samples in the past 12 months; raw water quality; the number of water sources; the effectiveness of the treatment methods and the ability of the water treatment plant; the risks of source contamination and network distribution; the size and complexity of the distribution network; the number of outbreaks in the last 12 months and the risks of epidemics spread.

Identification of water samples was done by making a clear, sustainable, visible and durable marking of the containers containing samples. On analysis applications have been mentioned the harvest time, date, the nature and quantity of added preservatives etc. Transporting water samples was made in packaging that protects recipients, while refrigerated. Keeping water samples in the laboratory was done under refrigeration and protected from light.

In laboratory tests, consecutive to the diagnostic steps set out by ISO 9308-1: 2014, non-compliance on the surface of the culture medium developed CCA mixed colony of *E. coli* violet and colonies of coliforms red (Fig. 9 and 10) or separate colonies of *E. coli* and coliform colonies (Fig. 11 and 12).

Fig. 8, 9. *E. coli* colonies (purple) and coliform bacteria (red) agar CCA

Fig. 10. *Coliform* colonies

Fig. 11. *E. coli* colonies

For counting, we considered as *E. coli* all the colonies with a positive reaction β - D - galactosidase and β - D - glucuronidase positive (from dark blue to purple). Presumptive coliform bacteria which are not *E. coli*, we confirmed using oxidase test and indole test. If on the membrane filter test were not sufficient colonies, or they were too small or were not sufficiently isolated, we proceeded to the tested colonies transplantation on agar TSA, which we incubated at 36 ± 2 ° C for $21 \pm 3:00$, a necessary operation because the investigation of the enzymatic equipment is always done on pure cultures of bacteria.

Oxidase test - for the confirmation that the presumptive coliform bacteria are not *E. coli*, we tested all or in some cases at least 10 colonies of color from pink to red, selected in accordance with ISO 8199. We used commercial oxidase appropriate tests or have proceeded to the addition of two to three drops of the oxidase on a fresh filter paper in a petri dish. Colonies that must be confirmed, we transferred on filter paper pretreated with an inoculation loop of plastic or platinum. The oxidase test is positive, if the dark blue color developed within 30 seconds. It can not be observed coliform bacteria as they have - negative oxidase reaction.

Fig. 12. *Oxidase* reaction positive

Fig. 13. *Oxidase* negative reaction

Indole test – for the test of the indole, the tryptophan broth cultures were incubated at $44 \pm 0.5 \text{ } ^\circ \text{C}$ for 21 ± 3 hours, after which we examined the metabolism of tryptophan to indole production by adding 0.2 to 0,3 ml Kovacs

reagent. The emergence of a film or ring, red signifies the positive reaction to the culture surface. Indole-positive colonies *Escherichia coli*.

Fig. 14. Test positive indole

Fig.15. Test indole negative

Calculation and expression of results: we considered that coliform bacteria is the sum of all oxidase negative colonies, pink-red and blue-violet colonies and the sum of all *E. coli* colonies blue-violet.

When the total number of colonies obtained was between 10 and 100, calculation of the results was performed using the formula

$$C_s = (Z / V_{tot}) \times V_s$$

- C_s = estimated number of colonies in the reference volume (V_s) of the sample (100 or 250 ml);
- Z = sum of colonies counted on the membrane, resulting in dilution or separate volumes;
- V_s = the benchmark chosen to express the concentration of microorganisms in the sample used (100 or 250 ml);
- V_{tot} = total calculated from sample plates counted. It is calculated according to the formula

$$V_{tot} = (n_1 V_1 d_1) + (n_2 V_2 d_2) + \dots + (n_i V_i d_i)$$

- n_1, n_2, \dots, n_i = number plates counted at each dilution;
- V_1, V_2, \dots, V_i = volume used / dilution;
- d_1, d_2, \dots, d_i = the dilutions used.

When the number of colonies was located between 9 and 4, we have done the calculation and expression of results using the formula of the general case. If the number of colonies was between 3 and 1, then the result was expressed as "microorganisms present in the analyzed volume." If no plate did not contain at least one colony, the result has been expressed as ' $<1 \text{ ufc} / V_{tot}$ '.

Interpretation of results: permissible values - Coliform bacteria ml = 0/100, 0/250 ml respectively, *Escherichia coli* ml = 0/100, 0/250 ml respectively for bottled water, according to Law no. 311/2004 amending and supplementing Law no. 458/2002 on drinking water quality. The results obtained were as follows:

Processing units, the number of non-compliant samples was 28. The highest number of non-compliant sample evidence recorded from Brasov county (9.75%), where the number of analyzed samples was higher, namely 82.6 % of total samples analyzed. Non-compliant results were obtained from samples of jud. Covasna (9.5%). There were no noncompliance evidence from Mures County. (Table no. 2 and Chart no. 2)

Table 2. The number of non-compliant samples processing units

Obtained results																Total			
Braşov				Prahova				Covasna				Mureş							
+		-		+		-		+		-		+		-		+		-	
No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
24	9,75	222	90,25	-	-	-	-	4	9,5	38	90,5	-	-	10	100	28	9,4	270	90,6

Chart 2. The number of non-compliant samples processing

Extraction and bottling units, there were no non-compliant samples with results, all samples showing values of 0 cfu / 250 ml. (Table no. 3 and Graph no. 3)

Table 3. The number of non-compliant samples processing units

Obtained results																Total			
Braşov				Prahova				Covasna				Mureş							
+		-		+		-		+		-		+		-		+		-	
No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
-	-	21	100	-	-	23	100	-	-	5	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	49	100

Chart 3. The number of non-compliant samples processing units

Values obtained by applying the calculation formulas were as follows: (Table no. 4 and Chart no. 4).

Table 4. *The values of non-compliant samples*

Irregular values obtained (cfu/100ml)	Number of samples	
	Nr.	%
1	2	4,3
2	4	13,0
3	6	21,7
5	3	8,7
15	2	4,3
21	1	4,3
22	1	4,3
33	1	4,3
46	1	4,3
49	1	4,3
52	1	4,3
63	2	8,7
103	1	4,3
124	1	4,3
127	1	4,3
Total	28	100

Chart 4. *The values of non-compliant samples*

It is noted that the values presented inconsistent values between 1 and 127 cfu / 100 ml, with a greater number of noncompliance samples 3, 2 and 5 cfu / 100ml.

4. Conclusions

Expertise by laboratory testing by counting *E. coli* and coliforms using membrane filtration method in the period 01/01/2015 - 04/30/2016 they were examined 347 samples from processing plants, the extraction and bottling units from the counties of Brasov, Prahova, Covasna and Mures.

Non-compliant samples were recorded only in the processing units, their number is 28. The highest percentage of non-compliant samples was

recorded from Brasov county (9.75%) and jud. Covasna (9.5%). There were no non-compliant samples in the extraction and bottling units.

The values showed irregular values between 1 and 127 cfu / 100 ml, with a larger number of samples noncompliance with 3, 2 and 5 cfu / 100ml.

The presence of *Escherichia coli* / coliform termotolerants in processing units indicate the gaps in the distribution system followed by the entry of foreign material in the distribution system and water tanks.

The results of examination of water through laboratory tests that we performed led to the outbreak of internal audits processing units in order to identify cases of non-compliance and the implementation of remedies

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12. Law no. 311 of 28 June 2004 amending and supplementing Law no. 458/2002 on drinking water quality. Issued by the Parliament of Romania, published in the Official Gazette no. 582 of 30 June 2004 values of non-compliant samples.

OBTAINING OF HYDROPHOBIN-TYPE PROTEINS FROM MYCELIA BIOMASS OF ASPERGILLUS NIGER

B. KOLESNIKOV, N. KHRAPATOV, M. SHAMTSYAN

Abstract: *Mycelia biomass of Aspergillus niger, a waste from citric acid production was used to obtain hydrophobin-type surfactant proteins. Obtained protein has a molecular weight of about 7 kDa and possess high surface-active properties.*

Keywords: *Fungi, surfactant, hydrophobin.*

1. Introduction

In the mid-80s, during the search for genes expressed in the formation of aerial hyphae on the mycelium of the fungus *Schizophyllum commune* special proteins were found, which later were called hydrophobins (Wessels, et al., 1991b). These proteins possess unique physical properties and can find application in various fields. Hydrophobins self-assemble into amphipathic membranes, converting the properties of contact surfaces. One of the most promising applications of hydrophobins is their use as stabilizers for edible foams and emulsions (Green, et al., 2013).

Despite the fact that hydrophobins have significant potential for application, the possibility of their use is currently limited, due to their insufficient output for testing of their wide use, and lack of large scale production of hydrophobins. In this regard, an actual issue is to find novel producers of hydrophobins, and development of more efficient production process for these compounds. One of the possibilities to increase the efficiency of the production of these proteins is to develop an integrated process for their preparation together with other valuable products.

Aspergillus niger is one of traditionally used producers for industrial production of citric acid (Belén Max, at all, 2010). The production of citric acid by *Aspergillus niger* is one of the most commercially utilized examples of fungal overflow metabolism. Many microorganisms such as fungi and bacteria can produce citric acid. The various fungi, which have been found to accumulate citric acid in their culture media, include strains of *Aspergillus niger*, *A. awamori*, *Penicillium restrictum*, *Trichoderma viride*, *Mucor piriformis* and *Yarrowia lipolytica* (Arzumanov et al. 2000). But *Aspergillus niger* remained the organism of

choice for the production of citric acid. The mutant strains might show several fold increase in citrate production as compared to wild-type cultures (Mattey and Allan, 1990; Ali et al. 2001).

Citric acid is obtained from the native liquid of cultivation and remaining after separation of culture broth fungal mycelia biomass is a waste product of citric acid production and in many cases is used just as fertilizer.

The aim of our work was to study the the possibility of utilization of mycelia biomass of *Aspergillus niger* as a source of hydrophobin-type surfactant proteins, as well as to develop a comprehensive method for their isolation and purification.

2. Materials and methods

The object of our study was mycelia biomass of fungi *Aspergillus niger* remained from citric acid production, kindly provided by the all-Russian institute of food additives (St. Petersburg).

Extraction of surfactant proteins

Mycelia biomass obtained was processed using ultrasonic disintegrator (Prointeh - Bio, Russia) in order to break the cell walls to achieve higher yield of the studied proteins. The homogenate was centrifuged at 6000 rotations / min to separate excreted due to the destruction of the fungal cell wall intracellular fluid from the biomass.

The resulting solution was foamed using an aerator, and then separated and the resulting foam was dissolved in 60% ethanol solution. Not dissolved or precipitated particles were removed by centrifugation at 6000 rev / min. Thereafter, ethyl alcohol was evaporated from the solution on a rotary evaporator at 40°C. Remains of water from the extract were removed by freeze-drying.

Analysis of the extracts

Chromatographic methods were used for the analysis and purification of the resulting extract. Since in our work we deal with surfactant proteins, inverted-phase HPLC has been used for their separation.

For protein analysis a 5-micron SupelcoSil C8 (SGE Analytical Science (Australia)) column of 250 x 4.6 mm size was used. As the stationary phase used was silica grafted with groups C8.

Injected sample volume was 20 μL , and the mobile phase consisted of 0.1% trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) and 50% (by volume) acetonitrile, pH = 3.0. Flow rate 0.8 ml / min-1. UV absorption of the eluant was observed at 280 nm and 254 nm. According to the obtained chromatograms the presence of peaks and their compliance with those described in the literature for the desired surfactant proteins were defined.

To determine the molecular weight of the protein was used disc electrophoresis method in polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (PAGE) according to the method of Laemmli (Laemmli, 1970).

Stacking gel contained 4% polyacrylamide and the separating gel - 7.5%. The gel was polymerized in the glass tubes from the kit "Apparatus for electrophoresis" model 73 production Reanal (Hungary). As an indicator front mobility during electrophoresis, 0.1% bromophenol blue dye solution was used, which was applied together with the samples in each tube with gel in an amount of 0.01 ml.

The procedure of the first half hour of electrophoresis was carried out at a current - 0.5 mA per one tube, then - at 2 mA per tube until the end of the separation process. The amount of protein per one tube does not exceed 250 mg. - The insulin, which has a molecular weight of about 6 kD was used as a standard protein. After electrophoresis the samples were compared with the control and the molecular weight of the surfactant protein was determined.

Assessing the impact of the resulting product to foam stability.

To evaluate surface activity of obtained extracts we tested the effects of obtained proteins on the foam stability. It is known that hydrophobins cause high foam stability, even at extremely low concentrations. For comparison, as a control Sodium caseinate and Tween 80 were used (Cox, et al., 2009). As a solution thickener, xanthan was used.

To 20 ml of a 0.5% solution of xanthan gum dried protein preparation obtained after removal

of the extractant (ethyl alcohol) was added. As a control, 20 ml 0.5% xanthan gum solutions containing 0.5% sodium caseinate and Tween 80 were taken. The test and control samples were foamed for 20 seconds in a rotary foamer. Further, the resulting foam volume was measured immediately after foaming and weekly for 2 months.

In order to evaluate the surface activity of obtained protein wetting contact angles of solid surfaces by different concentrations of protein solutions were determined.

Wetting contact angle is a characteristic of hydrophilicity (hydrophobicity) of the surface. It is defined as the angle between the tangent to the surface of the wetting liquid and solid surface wetted. Tangent is always carried out through the point of contact of three phases: the solid, liquid and gas (Laboratory works..., 1986).

Wetting contact angle is determined by the main dimensions of a liquid droplet, applied to solid surfaces: a height h and diameter of a base d .

Measurement of these parameters was carried out using the apparatus which main assemblies are cathetometer, measuring cell and a lighting device providing contrast images of drops and the surface under study.

The value of wetting contact angle was determined using equation:

$$\cos \theta = \frac{(d/2)^2 - h^2}{(d/2)^2 + h^2}.$$

It is known that hydrophobins can change the nature of the surface, changing the hydrophobic surface into a hydrophilic and vice versa. Fluoroplastic plate was used as a solid substrate for the application of drops.

The study was performed with protein solutions with a concentration of 0.01%, 0.1% and 1%. Distilled water and 1% solution of Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) were used as controls. After application of test solutions to the surface of fluoroplastic plate, droplets were kept for 20 minutes. This is due to the slow formation of the adsorption layers at interfaces.

3. Results and discussion

Analysis of the extracts were performed by HPLC method. Matching of the peaks in the chromatogram to those of hydrophobins was determined based on literature data (Armenante, 2008). Obtained extract shows

peaks with match the reference peaks for hydrophobin proteins.

In order to determine the molecular weight of the obtained surfactant protein an analysis of extracts by disc electrophoresis method was conducted. As a control, insulin was used ($M = 6$ kDa). From the results of electrophoresis it was determined that the molecular weight of the protein contained in the extract was about 7 kDa, corresponding approximately to a known from the literature

molecular weight of hydrophobins, (7-14 kDa).

It is known that the presence of hydrophobins in the foamed solution even at very low concentrations, enables very high foam stability. To estimate the surface activity of the obtained extracts their foam-stabilizing ability was tested. The sodium caseinate was used as a control for comparison. The volume of the resulting foam was measured one hour after foaming and further for 2 months every week. The results are shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 - The volume of the foam stabilized extract from *Aspergillus niger*

The diagram shows that the extracts allow to obtain stable foams. Air phase losses in the samples with addition of extract were about 50% at 8 weeks, while in the control sample with sodium caseinate there was a complete loss of air phase after 2 weeks. The results indicate that the properties of the foam-stabilizing surfactant protein were significantly higher than those of sodium caseinate, commonly used in manufacturing.

Evaluation of extracts on wetting contact angle.

Hydrophobins have very high surface activity. Self-assembling into stable agglomerates at the interface of the hydrophilic and hydrophobic phases, they are able to change the nature of the substances with which they come into contact, making them hydrophobic or hydrophilic properties. They are also able to change the surface tension of water.

The results of the influence of different concentrations of hydrophobin-type protein solutions from *Aspergillus niger* biomass on change in wetting contact angle of fluoroplastic plate are shown in Table.

Table – The influence of hydrophobin type proteins from *Aspergillus niger* biomass and μ SDS on the value of wetting contact angle.

Wetting contact angle, °				
water	0,01% protein solution	0,1% protein solution	1% protein solution	1% SDS solution
93±2	61±3	36±2	30±2	34±2

The results indicated that the studied proteins, even in extremely low concentrations, are capable of reducing the surface tension of water as well as to pass hydrophilic properties to hydrophobic materials. Caused effect is comparable with the effect of popular synthetic surfactants.

Based on the carried out experiments and obtained results a method of obtaining of surface-active proteins from the mycelia biomass of *Aspergillus niger*, a waste product of citric acid production is proposed (fig. 2).

Fig. 2 - Method of obtaining surface-active proteins from the mycelia biomass of *Aspergillus niger*, a waste product of citric acid production

Conclusions

As a result of carried out experiments, it was determined that the studied mushroom *Aspergillus niger* mycelia biomass, which is a waste product of citric acid production, could be a promising source of surfactant proteins. Obtained protein extracts have high foam-stabilizing ability not inferior to industrial foam stabilizers and high surface activity, compatible with activity of synthetic surfactants.

The proposed method for obtaining of a surfactant protein from waste products can significantly reduce the cost of its production making possible their utilization in food industry.

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MARKOVIAN DECISION PROCESSES APPLICATION IN FOOD INVENTORY MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: *Markovian Decision Processes is a powerful technique for formulating models and finding the optimal policies for controlling a large class of systems. This technique is applicable to the solution of problems in such areas as queuing theory, food inventory management, maintenance, and etc. An application of Markovian decision processes for optimal inventory management is considered in this paper. The demand level is represented as a stochastic process with Poisson distribution. An appropriate cost structure is introduced. The following algorithms will be explored: the linear programming formulation and the full enumeration technique. These methods are applied for optimal policy determination of food inventory management problem in a service system. Optimal policy is obtained in accordance with the proposed methods and is accomplished in MATLAB[®] software package.*

Keywords: *Markovian decision processes, optimal food inventory management.*

1. Introduction

The Markovian decision processes in a stochastic system have a wide application in food inventory, manufacturing, transportation, organizational and etc. areas [1, 2, 5, 6]. The Markov process is defined as a stochastic process which satisfies the Markov property – the conditional probability distribution of future states of the process depends only upon the present state, not on the sequence of events that preceded it, which could be referred as memory less [1, 2]. Some approaches to investigate the Markovian decision process are *full enumeration technique and linear programming algorithm* [1, 2]. A simulation-based optimization of inventory models is presented in [3, 4].

The paper is aimed at applying Markovian decision processes for optimal management of food inventory in a service system.

2. Markovian decision processes in management science

A stochastic process is defined to be a collection of random variables X_t , where t denotes particular points of time, $t=0, 1, 2, \dots$. At given points of time t (spaced equally or not) the system is found in exactly one of a finite number of states labeled $0, 1, \dots, M$. Each state that the process reaches is given a label that denotes the

physical state of the system. With $p_{ij}^{(n)}$ we denote the conditional probability that the random variable X , starting in state i , will be in state j after exactly n steps (time units). This probability must satisfy the properties:

$$p_{ij}^{(n)} \geq 0, \forall i, j, \text{ and } n=0, 1, 2$$

$$\sum_{j=0}^M p_{ij}^{(n)} = 1, \text{ and } n = 0, 1, 2 \quad (1)$$

The transition probabilities are usually represented in matrix form:

State	0	1	...	M
0	$p_{00}^{(n)}$	$p_{01}^{(n)}$		$p_{0M}^{(n)}$
1	$p_{10}^{(n)}$	$p_{11}^{(n)}$		$p_{1M}^{(n)}$
⋮				
M	$p_{M0}^{(n)}$	$p_{M1}^{(n)}$		$p_{MM}^{(n)}$

It can be shown that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} p_{ij}^{(n)}$ exists and is independent of i . Furthermore

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} p_{ij}^{(n)} = \pi_j, \quad (2)$$

where the π_j satisfy the following steady-state equations:

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$$\sum_{i=0}^M p_{ij} \pi_i = \pi_j, \quad j = \overline{0, M} \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{j=0}^M \pi_j = 1, \quad (4)$$

The π_j are called the *steady-state probabilities*.

The term steady-state probability means that the probability of finding the process in a certain state j after a large number of transitions tends to the value π_j , independent of the initial probability distribution defined over the state.

After each observation, one of K possible decisions (actions), labeled $1, 2, \dots, K$ is undertaken. A policy denoted by R is a rule for making decisions at each point in time.

Hence a policy R can be viewed as a rule that prescribes decision $d_i(R)$ when the system is in state i , $i = \overline{0, M}$. Thus, R is characterized by the values:

$$\{d_0(R), d_1(R), \dots, d_M(R)\}. \quad (5)$$

We assume that whenever the system is in state i , the decision to be made is the same for all values of t . Such policies are called *stationary policies*. If a given policy R is followed then a resultant stochastic process follows with a known transition matrix and this matrix depends upon the policy chosen. The described situation results in a sequence of observed states X_0, X_1, X_2, \dots and corresponding decisions made $\Delta_0, \Delta_1, \Delta_2, \dots$. This sequence of observed states and sequence of decisions made is called a *Markovian decision process*.

To answer the question “*which one of the policies is the best*” it is necessary to introduce a cost structure. When the system is in state i and decision $d_i(R) = k$ is made following policy R , a known (expected) cost C_{ik} is incurred.

To compare policies, we must settle on an *appropriate cost measure*. One such measure associated with a policy is the (*long-run*) *expected average cost per unit time* $E\{C\}$. It can be calculated from the expression:

$$E(C) = \sum_{i=0}^M C_{ik} \pi_i, \quad (6)$$

where $d_i(R) = k$ for each i , and $\pi_0, \pi_1, \dots, \pi_M$ represents the steady-state distribution of the state of the system under the policy R being evaluated. Thus the policy that minimizes $E\{C\}$ is sought. Now it is necessary to solve for $\pi_0, \pi_1, \dots, \pi_M$ using the equations corresponding to each of the considered policies and then use these results to compute $E\{C\}$.

The described technique is called an exhaustive enumeration of a given set of possible policies.

The *linear programming formulation* is best expressed in term of a variable y_{ik} , which is related to D_{ik} as shown below. Let y_{ik} be the steady-state unconditional probability that the system is in state i and decision k is made:

$$y_{ik} = P\{k/i\}.P\{i\} = D_{ik}\pi_i, \quad (7)$$

where

$$\pi_i = \sum_{k=1}^K y_{ik}, \quad D_{ik} = \frac{y_{ik}}{\sum_{k=1}^K y_{ik}}. \quad (8)$$

The long run expected average cost per unit time is given by

$$E(C) = \sum_{i=0}^M \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_i C_{ik} D_{ik} = \sum_{i=0}^M \sum_{k=1}^K C_{ik} y_{ik}, \quad (9)$$

where

$$\sum_{k=1}^K y_{jk} - \sum_{i=0}^M \sum_{k=1}^K y_{ik} p_{ij}(k) = 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^M \sum_{k=1}^K y_{ik} = 1, \quad (11)$$

and $y_{ik} \geq 0, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, M$

This formulation is clearly a linear programming problem that can be solved by simplex method. Once y_{ik} are obtained then D_{ik} are easily found from (8).

3. Application of Markovian decision processes in food inventory management

In this section we consider an optimal food inventory management in a service system. First we apply the exhaustive enumeration method to find the optimal management policy for the

service system using the theory presented in Section 2. Then we use the linear programming approach as described in Section 2.

Problem. A service system keeps in an inventory a certain type of food commodity in lots, which can be ordered weekly. Each lot contains 100 items of food commodity. Let D_1, D_2, D_3, \dots represent the demand for a lot during the first week, the second week, etc. It is assumed that D_i are independent and identically distributed random variables having a Poisson distribution with parameter λ . Let X_0 represents the number of food commodity in lots on hand at the start period, X_1 , the number of lots on hand at the end of week one, and so on. On Saturday night the inventory places an order that is delivered in time for the opening of the inventory on Monday. The loss structure requires penalty cost of 550 euro for a unit lot of unsatisfied demand to be considered. If a number of z lots of food commodity are ordered then the costs are $30+250z$ euro (ordering cost). If there are no orders then there is no ordering cost. The holding costs to keep the food commodity in the inventory amounts to 20 euro per lot. We assume that four /4/ lots of food commodity is the maximal number of items that the service systems can store. All computations presented in this section are done using MATLAB[®].

Let X_t represents the state of the system, i.e., the number of lots on hand at the end of week t (before ordering), then $X_t = 0,1,2,3,4$. Similarly, there are five possible decisions, presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Decision	Action
0	Do not order
1	Order 1 lot
2	Order 2 lots
3	Order 3 lots
4	Order 4 lots

Then it is necessary to make a relation between the states and the possible decisions, this is shown in Tables 2-6.

Table 2

Decision 0					
State	0	1	2	3	4
0	1	0	0	0	0
1	$P\{D_i \geq 1\}$	$P\{D_i = 0\}$	0	0	0
2	$P\{D_i \geq 2\}$	$P\{D_i = 1\}$	$P\{D_i = 0\}$	0	0
3	$P\{D_i \geq 3\}$	$P\{D_i = 2\}$	$P\{D_i = 1\}$	$P\{D_i = 0\}$	0
4	$P\{D_i \geq 4\}$	$P\{D_i = 3\}$	$P\{D_i = 2\}$	$P\{D_i = 1\}$	$P\{D_i = 0\}$

Table 3

Decision 1					
State	0	1	2	3	4
0	$P\{D_i \geq 1\}$	$P\{D_i = 0\}$	0	0	0
1	$P\{D_i \geq 2\}$	$P\{D_i = 1\}$	$P\{D_i = 0\}$	0	0
2	$P\{D_i \geq 3\}$	$P\{D_i = 2\}$	$P\{D_i = 1\}$	$P\{D_i = 0\}$	0
3	$P\{D_i \geq 4\}$	$P\{D_i = 3\}$	$P\{D_i = 2\}$	$P\{D_i = 1\}$	$P\{D_i = 0\}$
4	Not allowed				

For state 4 (four lots of food commodity in the inventory) decision 1 is not allowed because the maximum storage limit should not be exceeded.

Table 4

Decision 2					
State	0	1	2	3	4
0	$P\{D_i \geq 2\}$	$P\{D_i = 1\}$	$P\{D_i = 0\}$	0	0
1	$P\{D_i \geq 3\}$	$P\{D_i = 2\}$	$P\{D_i = 1\}$	$P\{D_i = 0\}$	0
2	$P\{D_i \geq 4\}$	$P\{D_i = 3\}$	$P\{D_i = 2\}$	$P\{D_i = 1\}$	$P\{D_i = 0\}$
3	Not allowed				
4	Not allowed				

Table 5

Decision 3					
State	0	1	2	3	4
0	$P\{D_i \geq 3\}$	$P\{D_i = 2\}$	$P\{D_i = 1\}$	$P\{D_i = 0\}$	0
1	$P\{D_i \geq 4\}$	$P\{D_i = 3\}$	$P\{D_i = 2\}$	$P\{D_i = 1\}$	$P\{D_i = 0\}$
2	Not allowed				
3	Not allowed				
4	Not allowed				

Table 6

Decision 4					
State	0	1	2	3	4
0	$P\{D_i \geq 4\}$	$P\{D_i = 3\}$	$P\{D_i = 2\}$	$P\{D_i = 1\}$	$P\{D_i = 0\}$
1	Not allowed				
2	Not allowed				
3	Not allowed				
4	Not allowed				

Now we consider three ordering policies, which have to be compared.

$$\text{Ordering policy } R_1 = [4 \ 3 \ 2 \ 1 \ 0]$$

For this policy in states 0, 1, 2, 3, 4 it is necessary to order 4, 3, 2, 1, 0 lots, i.e. the food inventory is full in every state. The transition probabilities matrix has the following Table 7: We suppose that the demand has a Poisson distribution with probability density function

$$P_n(t) = \frac{(\lambda t)^n e^{-\lambda t}}{n!}, \quad n = 0, 1, 2, \dots,$$

here $\lambda=2$ is the average number of entities to serve for unit time.

Table 7

State	0	1	2	3	4
0	$P\{D_t \geq 4\}$	$P\{D_t = 3\}$	$P\{D_t = 2\}$	$P\{D_t = 1\}$	$P\{D_t = 0\}$
1	$P\{D_t \geq 4\}$	$P\{D_t = 3\}$	$P\{D_t = 2\}$	$P\{D_t = 1\}$	$P\{D_t = 0\}$
2	$P\{D_t \geq 4\}$	$P\{D_t = 3\}$	$P\{D_t = 2\}$	$P\{D_t = 1\}$	$P\{D_t = 0\}$
3	$P\{D_t \geq 4\}$	$P\{D_t = 3\}$	$P\{D_t = 2\}$	$P\{D_t = 1\}$	$P\{D_t = 0\}$
4	$P\{D_t \geq 4\}$	$P\{D_t = 3\}$	$P\{D_t = 2\}$	$P\{D_t = 1\}$	$P\{D_t = 0\}$

Therefore the computation of the transition probabilities is done in the following way:

$$P\{D_t \geq 4\} = 1 - P\{D_t = 3\} - P\{D_t = 2\} - P\{D_t = 1\} - P\{D_t = 0\},$$

$$P\{D_t = 0\} = P_0(1) = \frac{(2.1)^0 e^{-2.1}}{1} = e^{-3} = 0.135,$$

$$P\{D_t = 1\} = P_1(1) = \frac{(2.1)^1 e^{-2.1}}{1} = 0.271,$$

$$P\{D_t = 2\} = P_2(1) = \frac{(2.1)^2 e^{-2.1}}{2} = 0.271$$

$$P\{D_t = 3\} = P_3(1) = \frac{(2.1)^3 e^{-2.1}}{6} = 0.180$$

$$P\{D_t \geq 4\} = 1 - P\{D_t = 3\} - P\{D_t = 2\} - P\{D_t = 1\} - P\{D_t = 0\} = 1 - (0.180 + 0.271 + 0.271 + 0.135) = 0.143$$

Then the transition matrix for the first policy can be obtained and it is shown in Table 8.

Table 8

		π_0	π_1	π_2	π_3	π_4
	State	0	1	2	3	4
π_0	0	0.143	0.180	0.271	0.271	0.135
π_1	1	0.143	0.180	0.271	0.271	0.135
π_2	2	0.143	0.180	0.271	0.271	0.135
π_3	3	0.143	0.180	0.271	0.271	0.135
π_4	4	0.143	0.180	0.271	0.271	0.135

For the considered policy the expected costs resulting from a single transition step are calculated as follows:

$$C_{04} = 1030 + 550 * [1P\{D_t = 5\} + 2P\{D_t = 6\} + \dots + 5P\{D_t = 9\}] + 20 * [1P\{D_t = 3\} + 2P\{D_t = 2\} + \dots + 4P\{D_t = 0\}] = 1112.7$$

$$C_{13} = 780 + 550 * [1P\{D_t = 5\} + 2P\{D_t = 6\} + \dots + 5P\{D_t = 9\}] + 20 * [1P\{D_t = 3\} + 2P\{D_t = 2\} + \dots + 4P\{D_t = 0\}] = 862.7$$

$$C_{22} = 530 + 550 * [1P\{D_t = 5\} + 2P\{D_t = 6\} + \dots + 5P\{D_t = 9\}] + 20 * [1P\{D_t = 3\} + 2P\{D_t = 2\} + \dots + 4P\{D_t = 0\}] = 612.7$$

$$C_{31} = 280 + 550 * [1P\{D_t = 5\} + 2P\{D_t = 6\} + \dots + 5P\{D_t = 9\}] + 20 * [1P\{D_t = 3\} + 2P\{D_t = 2\} + \dots + 4P\{D_t = 0\}] = 362.7$$

$$C_{40} = 550 * [1P\{D_t = 5\} + 2P\{D_t = 6\} + \dots + 5P\{D_t = 9\}] + 20 * [1P\{D_t = 3\} + 2P\{D_t = 2\} + \dots + 4P\{D_t = 0\}] = 82.7$$

Here the maximum value of n (demand) is nine lots, because all coefficients

$P(D_t > 9)$ are smaller than the machine precision $2.2204e-016$, that's why they are neglected.

In order to obtain the steady-state probabilities the following linear algebraic system of Eq. (3) - Eq. (4) have to be solved:

$$\pi_0 = \pi_0 p_{00} + \pi_1 p_{10} + \pi_2 p_{20} + \pi_3 p_{30} + \pi_4 p_{40}$$

$$\pi_1 = \pi_0 p_{01} + \pi_1 p_{11} + \pi_2 p_{21} + \pi_3 p_{31} + \pi_4 p_{41}$$

$$\pi_2 = \pi_0 p_{02} + \pi_1 p_{12} + \pi_2 p_{22} + \pi_3 p_{32} + \pi_4 p_{42}$$

$$\pi_3 = \pi_0 p_{03} + \pi_1 p_{13} + \pi_2 p_{23} + \pi_3 p_{33} + \pi_4 p_{43}$$

$$\pi_4 = \pi_0 p_{04} + \pi_1 p_{14} + \pi_2 p_{24} + \pi_3 p_{34} + \pi_4 p_{44}$$

$$\pi_0 + \pi_1 + \pi_2 + \pi_3 + \pi_4 = 1.$$

The solution is

$$\pi_0 = 0.143, \pi_1 = 0.180, \pi_2 = 0.271, \pi_3 = 0.271, \pi_4 = 0.135.$$

The expected cost for the ordering policy1 using expression (6) is calculated below

$$EC(R_1) = \sum_{i=0}^4 C_{ik} \pi_i = C_{04} \pi_0 + C_{13} \pi_1 + C_{22} \pi_2 + C_{31} \pi_3 + C_{40} \pi_4 = 1112.7 \times 0.143 + 862.7 \times 0.180 + 612.7 \times 0.271 + 362.7 \times 0.271 + 82.7 \times 0.135 = 589.83.$$

Ordering policy 2 $R_2 = [4 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]$

Using the same calculation procedure as shown above the transition matrix P_2 for the second policy can be obtained in Table 9.

Table 9

		π_0	π_1	π_2	π_3	π_4
	State	0	1	2	3	4
π_0	0	0.143	0.180	0.271	0.271	0.135
π_1	1	0.865	0.135	0	0	0
π_2	2	0.594	0.271	0.135	0	0
π_3	3	0.323	0.271	0.271	0.353	0
π_4	4	0.143	0.180	0.271	0.271	0.135

For the considered policy the expected costs resulting from a single transition step are calculated as follows

$$C_{10} = 550 * [1P\{D=2\} + 2P\{D=3\} + 3P\{D=4\} + 4P\{D=5\} + 5P\{D=6\}] + 20 * [1P\{D=0\}] = 611.4$$

$$C_{20} = 550 * [1P\{D=3\} + 2P\{D=4\} + \dots + 5P\{D=7\}] + 20 * [1P\{D=1\} + 2P\{D=0\}] = 304.8$$

$$C_{30} = 550 * [1P\{D=4\} + 2P\{D=5\} + \dots + 5P\{D=8\}] + 20 * [1P\{D=2\} + 2P\{D=1\} + 3P\{D=0\}] = 143.5$$

The expected costs

$$C_{04} = 1112.7, C_{40} = 82.7.$$

are already calculated above.

The values of the steady-state probabilities according to Eq. (3) - Eq. (4) are

$$\pi_0 = 0.400, \pi_1 = 0.202, \pi_2 = 0.190, \pi_3 = 0.145, \pi_4 = 0.063.$$

The expected cost for ordering policy 2 using Eq. (6) is

$$EC(R_2) = \sum_{i=0}^4 C_{ik} \pi_i = C_{04} \pi_0 + C_{10} \pi_1 + C_{20} \pi_2 + C_{30} \pi_3 + C_{40} \pi_4 = 1112.7 \times 0.400 + 611.4 \times 0.202 + 304.8 \times 0.190 + 143.5 \times 0.145 + 82.7 \times 0.063 = 652.79$$

Ordering policy 3 $R_3 = [4 \ 3 \ 2 \ 0 \ 0]$

The transition matrix P_3 for the third policy is shown in Table 10.

For the considered policy the expected costs resulting from a single transition step are calculated already above

$$C_{13} = 862.7, C_{22} = 612.7, C_{30} = 143.5, C_{04} = 1112.7, C_{40} = 82.7.$$

The values of the steady-state probabilities are calculated according to Eq. (3) – Eq. (4):

$$\pi_0 = 0.186, \pi_1 = 0.202, \pi_2 = 0.271, \pi_3 = 0.238, \pi_4 = 0.103.$$

Table 10

		π_0	π_1	π_2	π_3	π_4
	State	0	1	2	3	4
π_0	0	0.143	0.180	0.271	0.271	0.135
π_1	1	0.143	0.180	0.271	0.271	0.135
π_2	2	0.143	0.180	0.271	0.271	0.135
π_3	3	0.323	0.271	0.271	0.135	0
π_4	4	0.143	0.180	0.271	0.271	0.135

The expected cost for the ordering policy 3 using expression Eq. (6) is

$$EC(R_1) = \sum_{i=0}^4 C_{ik} \pi_i = C_{04} \pi_0 + C_{13} \pi_1 + C_{22} \pi_2 + C_{31} \pi_3 + C_{40} \pi_4 = 1112.7 \times 0.186 + 862.7 \times 0.202 + 612.7 \times 0.271 + 143.5 \times 0.238 + 82.7 \times 0.103 = 589.62$$

Finally we have to compare the expected costs for the considered ordering policies

$$EC(R_1) = 589.83; EC(R_2) = 652.79; EC(R_3) = 589.62$$

According to the results, the most appropriate ordering policy, with minimum expected costs, for this food inventory is:

$$EC(R_3) = 589.62$$

This means that the optimal policy to perform management of the inventory lots with food commodity in the service system is R_3 .

The optimal ordering policy can be determined by *linear programming formulation*. In

accordance with Eq. (9) the objective function of the linear programming model is

$$E(C) = \sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{k=1}^4 C_{ik} y_{ik} \quad (12)$$

The expected costs for one time period C_{ik} for each state over all possible decisions are represented in the following matrix form:

Table 11

$i \backslash k$	0	1	2	3	4
0	1042.1	891.4	834.8	923.5	1112.7
1	611.4	584.8	673.5	862.7	∞
2	304.8	423.5	612.7	∞	∞
3	143.5	362.7	∞	∞	∞
4	82.7	∞	∞	∞	∞

The problem is to choose the variables value y_{ik} that minimize the objective function subject to the following constraints:

$$\sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{k=0}^4 y_{ik} = 1 \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^4 y_{jk} - \sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{k=0}^4 y_{ik} p_{ij}(k) = 0 \text{ for } j = \overline{0,4}, \quad (14)$$

$$y_{ik} \geq 0, \quad i = \overline{0,4}, \quad k = \overline{0,4}$$

Linear programming formulation requires information about the probabilities $p_{ij}(k)$, $j = \overline{0,4}$, $k = \overline{0,4}$. The probabilities over all possible decisions k are given below

$$\|p_{ij}(k=0)\| = \begin{matrix} & & k=0 \\ & & 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ \begin{matrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 2 \\ 3 \\ 4 \end{matrix} & \left[\begin{matrix} p_{00} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ p_{10} & p_{11} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ p_{20} & p_{21} & p_{22} & 0 & 0 \\ p_{30} & p_{31} & p_{32} & p_{33} & 0 \\ p_{40} & p_{41} & p_{42} & p_{43} & p_{44} \end{matrix} \right] \end{matrix}$$

$$\|p_{ij}(k=1)\| = \begin{matrix} & & k=1 \\ & & 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ \begin{matrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 2 \\ 3 \\ 4 \end{matrix} & \left[\begin{matrix} p_{10} & p_{11} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ p_{20} & p_{21} & p_{22} & 0 & 0 \\ p_{30} & p_{31} & p_{32} & p_{33} & 0 \\ p_{40} & p_{41} & p_{42} & p_{43} & p_{44} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{matrix} \right] \end{matrix}$$

$$\|p_{ij}(k=2)\| = \begin{matrix} & & k=2 \\ & & 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ \begin{matrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 2 \\ 3 \\ 4 \end{matrix} & \left[\begin{matrix} p_{20} & p_{21} & p_{22} & 0 & 0 \\ p_{30} & p_{31} & p_{32} & p_{33} & 0 \\ p_{40} & p_{41} & p_{42} & p_{43} & p_{44} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{matrix} \right] \end{matrix}$$

$$\|p_{ij}(k=3)\| = \begin{matrix} & & k=3 \\ & & 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ \begin{matrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 2 \\ 3 \\ 4 \end{matrix} & \left[\begin{matrix} p_{30} & p_{31} & p_{32} & p_{33} & 0 \\ p_{40} & p_{41} & p_{42} & p_{43} & p_{44} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{matrix} \right] \end{matrix}$$

$$\|p_{ij}(k=4)\| = \begin{matrix} & & k=4 \\ & & 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ \begin{matrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 2 \\ 3 \\ 4 \end{matrix} & \left[\begin{matrix} p_{40} & p_{41} & p_{42} & p_{43} & p_{44} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{matrix} \right] \end{matrix}$$

The constraints Eq. (14) can be presented in the following form:

$$\sum_{k=0}^4 y_{0k} - \sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{k=0}^4 y_{ik} p_{i0}(k) = 0, j=0 \quad (16)$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^4 y_{1k} - \sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{k=0}^4 y_{ik} p_{i1}(k) = 0, j=1 \quad (17)$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^4 y_{2k} - \sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{k=0}^4 y_{ik} p_{i2}(k) = 0, j=2 \quad (18)$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^4 y_{3k} - \sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{k=0}^4 y_{ik} p_{i3}(k) = 0, j=3 \quad (19)$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^4 y_{4k} - \sum_{i=0}^4 \sum_{k=0}^4 y_{ik} p_{i4}(k) = 0, j=4 \quad (20)$$

$$y_{ik} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0000 & 0.0000 & 0.0000 & 0.0000 & 0.1859 \\ 0.0000 & 0.0000 & 0.0000 & 0.2020 & 0.0000 \\ 0.0000 & 0.0000 & 0.2707 & 0.0000 & 0.0000 \\ 0.2384 & 0.0000 & 0.0000 & 0.0000 & 0.0000 \\ 0.1031 & 0.0000 & 0.0000 & 0.0000 & 0.0000 \end{bmatrix}$$

The linear programming problem, described by the objective function (12) and six constraints presented by Eq. (13) and Eq. (16)-Eq. (20) can be solved by using the simplex method.

The optimal policy based on Linear programming formulation is accomplished by using of Optimization Toolbox of MATLAB. For solving LP problems we need to use the MATLAB command “*linprog*”. The syntax is as follows:

$$x = \text{linprog}(f, [], [], A_{eq}, b_{eq}, lb, ub) \quad (21)$$

where the vector of the variables is

$$x = [y_{00}, \dots, y_{04}, y_{10}, \dots, y_{14}, \dots, y_{40}, \dots, y_{44}]$$

There are 25 unknown variables and six constraints. In the function *linprog*

A_{eq} is a matrix that contains the left-hand site coefficients of linear equality constraints,

B_{eq} is a vector column that contains the right-hand site coefficients of linear equality constraints;

lb is a vector of the lower bounds of the variables;

ub is a vector of the upper bounds of the variables.

The optimal solution of the optimization problem is $J^* = 589.6175$ obtained for

$$x^* = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.1859 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.2020 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.2707 & 0 & 0 & 0.2384 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.1031 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The values of x^* yield to the optimal solution presented in the matrix form

In accordance with Eq. (8) the matrix form of the deterministic optimal policy can be obtained

$$D_{ik} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

It can be noticed the resulting policy is identical to the one obtained by using the full enumeration method. It calls for ordering up to four lots of food whenever there is 0, 1 or 2 lots of food in the stock; otherwise, no ordering is done.

$$R^* = [4 \ 3 \ 2 \ 0 \ 0]$$

The optimal value of the objective function is $J^* = 589.6175$. It has the same value as the cost rate of the third policy.

4. Conclusion

In this paper powerful tools formulating models and finding the optimal policy for a large class of systems control which are Markovian decision processes. These techniques are applicable to the solution of problems in such areas as queuing theory, inventory, maintenance, and probabilistic dynamic programming in general. The paper involves application of this theory to inventory control. An application of Markovian decision processes for inventory control of foods is considered. The demand model is described as a stochastic process with Poisson distribution. An appropriate cost structure is introduced. The stochastic behavior of the system is presented as an irreducible Markovian chain associated with the transition probability matrix. Two criteria for optimal policy determination are considered: the full enumeration method – based on criterion of long-run expected average cost per unit time and Linear programming formulation. These methods are applied for optimal policy determination of food inventory control problem. Optimal policy

determination in accordance with the proposed methods is accomplished in MATLAB software package. Future investigations will be focused on the sensitivity analysis of the optimal policy with respect to the cost structure parameters.

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INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON HOLIDAY TRAVEL PLANNING

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Abstract: Rapid development of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) have revolutionized all industries in the World and presents challenges and great opportunities for tourism industry too. Widespread of the Internet, the Web 2.0 environment and the mobile communication have huge impact on tourism. Platform of tourism increasingly get to the Internet nowadays which is vitally important because tourism is an information-based and information-intensive industry. Web 2.0 internet technologies have allowed for the tourists to interact with each other online and have changed the way tourist plan and consume travel. User-Generated Contents (UGC) on different types of social media websites and travel related websites assist consumers in sharing their travel related experiences, which opinions and comments serve as information for others. Derive from the characteristic, decisions connected with travelling have high risk for the travellers therefore they try to collect more detailed and more reliable information in order to decrease uncertainty.

In this article an online questionnaire was made in order to investigate the influence of social media on Hungarian travelers throughout the travel process (before, during and after travel). We can conclude that the respondents are using the social media pages during the whole planning process of travel but for various reasons and with various extent.

Keywords: ICT, social media, user generated content, tourism

1. Introduction

Information and Communication Technologies have changed the tourism industry, and playing a central role in its increase and development. One of the most important changes was that the Internet became a powerful communication and distribution channel for travel suppliers, fulfilling the gap between consumers and suppliers (Amaro and Duarte, 2015).

Derive from the characteristic, decisions connected with travelling have high risk for the travelers therefore they try to collect more detailed and reliable information in order to decrease uncertainty. Platform of tourism increasingly get to the Internet nowadays which is vitally important because tourism is an information-based and information-intensive industry.

Web 2.0 applications enables the two-way information communications for Internet users which generates incredible number of online

UGC on different travel-related websites (Sigala, 2007). UGC on different types of social media websites and travel related websites assist consumers in sharing their travel related experiences, which opinions and comments serve as information for others during the travel planning process.

The main objective of this paper is to examine the used information sources during leisure travels focusing especially the analysis of the role of social media (user generated contents).

2. Literature review

Web 2.0 has enabled tourist to create their own travel-related content, and share it easily through different social media platform.

Derive from the characteristics of Web 2.0 – several academic literatures, blogs articles attempted to define – it is a complex phenomenon. Its' complexity shows that Web 2.0 has got different dimensions of use such as

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technological, business philosophical and sociological. Web 2.0 is a concept originally coined during a conference brainstorming session between O'Reilly and MediaLive International in 2004 who described it as "an attitude rather than a technology" (O'Reilly 2005). The key difference between traditional websites (Web 1.0) and Web 2.0 is the participation of the users. Web 2.0 sites have the ability to be the platform for users to interact and collaborate with each other, in contrast to other websites (Web 1.0) where users are limited to the passive viewing of content that was created for them (Cormode and Krishnamurthy 2008).

Milano et al., (2011) have similar opinion with O'Reilly (2005) about Web 2.0: Web 2.0 is "not really a technological advancement ... rather identifies the changes occurred in the ways software developers and people make and use the web". More detailed definition have been created by Turban et al. (2011) whom determined Web 2.0 as "the second-generation of Internet-based services that let people collaborate and share information online in perceived new ways such as social networking sites, blogs, wikis, video sharing sites, web applications, and communication tools". From different point of view but with the similar conception, Sigala (2007) interpreted Web 2.0 which realise and exploit the full potential of the original concept and role of the Internet. The researcher in her article also added that Web 2.0 is the "tools of mass collaboration", when internet users actively participate and simultaneously collaborate with other users in order to create, use and share information.

Web 2.0 and UGC have increasingly changed the way that people search, find, read, gather, share, develop and consume information (Ye et al., 2011). One of the most important online user-generated content, the travel reviews (about hotel, destination, restaurants etc.) on different websites have become important sources of information for travelers (Gretzel and Yoo, 2008; Ye et al., 2011).

Diffusion of the Internet and development of the ICTs contributed to the process that social media started replacing traditional sources of information. Consumers have changed they are becoming more sophisticated so they require more specialized information. Although social media is very important all over the World there is still no agreed definition in the academic literature and it can be interpreted in many ways as we can find in the article written by Fotis et

al., (2012): social media regularly identify as social software, social web sites, consumer-generated media, user-generated media, user-generated content websites, or even Web 2.0.

In my opinion Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) give a compact definition for this term involved most of the previously mentioned different interpretations: social media is "a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0, and that allow the creation and exchange of user-generated content" (videos, photos, texts etc.). "Web 2.0 has made available some technologies that...offer new and more efficient ways of communication by enabling users to make their ideas and opinions available to a potential audience of millions of people. This information is called User- Generated Content" (Chaves et al. 2012).

In tourism, consumers' behaviour has always been influenced by development of ICTs, but Web 2.0 has completely changed how consumers design and consume travel related products (Buhalis and Law 2008). During the travel planning process social media get an important role, because it gives access to other travellers' experiences as an ultimate information source (Chung and Buhalis 2008; Yoo et al. 2011).

However, there is not yet an agreed term to describe social media, the academic literature also evidences a disagreement on the classification of social media according to Fotis et al., (2012).

3. Research methods

An online questionnaire survey, about the usage of social media during travel planning process, was conducted in 2014. The query of the questionnaire was preceded by small sample screen (N=75) in 2014 spring, among university students with the aim of finalizing questions, correcting mistakes and for higher validity.

For the query of the finally questionnaire (December 2015) CAWI method (online questionnaire) was used. The representative query was ensured by the online surface of a market research company. The research did not want to examine the whole population only focused on the internet users, they gave the base multitude. The questionnaire was filled precisely by 636 people, this multitude represented the internet user population over 18 according to genre, age and region. The data thanks to the online research did not need manual input,

coding was realized with the cooperation of the market research company. The statistical analyses were fulfilled with SPSS 22.0 software.

The questionnaire included measures to provide sociodemographic characteristics, usage of the internet and social media behaviour. Several instances were used for explaining types of websites in order to increase the reliability of the responses. The questionnaire used not only the most famous social media examples from all over the world but also websites operating exclusively in Hungary.

The used methods during the evaluation of the questionnaire due to their wide reputation will not be presented in my dissertation. During the process of research results the following statistical analyses were used (Sajtos – Mitev, 2007):

- Mean, standard deviation, frequency;
- Pearson's chi-square test;
- Analysis of variance.

4. Results

A demographic summary of survey participants is summarized in Table 1. The age group with the most significant number of responses was the group 18-29, with 28.8% of the total of responses, while only approximately 19% are aged between 40 and 49.

In terms of gender, of the 636 respondents, 51% were females and 49% were males.

The aim of this chapter was to find out that the importance of mediums primarily based on user generated content is how large comparing with the situation of traditional media sources in Hungarian adult internet users.

The available online user generated contents related to tourism are more important than the

traditional advertising tools (travel agencies, official web pages).

First, we analyzed how respondents plan their travel and holiday. 93.4% of respondents answered that they plan their travel by their own and only 18.1% uses the services of travel agencies. The second question was if the respondents use the Internet during the organization of their travel. 91.2% of the respondents answered that they are searching on the Internet and 8.8% does not use this possibility. This data also represents that the main information source during travel planning is Internet (KSH, 2013).

The importance of the various information sources during the planning phase of travel is very diverse. In my dissertation the use of Internet and social media next to traditional information sources is emphasized. The respondents had to evaluate each medium according to their importance during travel planning in a 1-5 scale Likert-scale.

The results confirm that the role of traditional information sources is still deterministic but the importance of social media pages and user generated content has increased during recent years. Primary source is the information of family members and friends but printed media, such as travel magazines, brochures, travel books, is still an important information source. However the second most important source is the widely used form of user generated content - user reviews and opinions, social media pages and travel blogs could not squeeze out official travel pages and travel magazines. Online photo and video sharing pages and traditional media sources are the least important information sources during leisure travel planning (Table 1.).

Table 1: Importance order of used information sources during travel planning

Information sources	Average	Standard deviation
Information of friends and family members	4,09	0,93
Reviews of other travellers (e.g. Tripadvisor)	3,50	1,05
Official travel pages	3,39	1,16
Travel books, brochures, travel magazines	3,35	1,12
Social media pages (e.g. Facebook)	3,29	1,14
Blogs, travel blogs (e.g. Origo travel head)	3,01	1,20
Travel agency	3,00	1,24
Online photo sharing sites (e.g. Instagram travel photos)	2,80	1,24
TV, radio, newspaper	2,78	1,06
Online video sharing sites (e.g. Youtube travel videos)	2,78	1,18

Source: Own edition

Summarizing we can conclude my hypothesis partly realized. From the table it turned out that the use of traditional information sources is still deterministic during travel organizing. In the same time, the importance of travel agencies and mass media is lower than the social media pages and blogs. Only one form of the user generated content, the travel related reviews received higher evaluation score than the traditional information sources.

The detailed analysis of these results is very important which indicates the data analysis with variance analysis (KIM et al., 2007).

Primarily I was curious if there was any difference between the importance of various information sources in the case of representative demography data (especially genre and age).

There was no difference between genres but considering the age there was significant difference in the case of several information sources. It is worth to analyse the differences in each age group. To realize this from the post hoc analyses I used Tukey HSD and Tamhane method. From the results we can conclude that there was significant difference in the age group 18-29 and older than 50 (except travel agencies).

- Online photo sharing pages (<0,05, F= 3,105)
- Blogs, travel blogs (<0,05, F= 5,477)
- Travel agencies (<0,05, F= 2,704)

Travel agencies as information sources during organizing leisure travel are more important for age group 30-39 than for age group 18-29.

After this I examined what are the differences during inland and foreign travel planning. There were significant differences during inland and

foreign travel planning in the case of following elements:

- Reviews of other travellers ($p < 0,05$, $F = 12,656$)
- Online photo sharing pages (<0,05, $F = 4,560$)
- Blogs, travel blogs (<0,05, $F = 7,534$)
- Travel agencies (<0,05, $F = 7,531$)

Examining average values and the answers of respondents, we can conclude that these information sources are more important during organizing foreign travels.

Next I examine the role of social media during the whole process of travel (Table 2.).

On the whole, we can conclude that the respondents are using social media pages during all process of travel planning but for various reasons and in various extents. In the planning phase before travel most of the respondents use social media pages to collect ideas but there is a large part who visit these contents during the selection of accommodation. Only tierce part of users visit social media pages to confirm if they chose the right destination for holiday.

During the travel the respondents collect information of a certain sight or certain program on the social media pages and use as a tool for contact and communicate. Only a few writes about his experience on forums and there were also a few who visited the social media pages with a different reason than their travel. After travel every fourth respondent visits social media pages for example to share photos or experience or write online reviews. These results lag behind the international trends where most of travellers used that opportunity to write their opinion about

their experience (for example write a review of the accommodation).

As a part of my earlier research (in 2012, population with 221 elements) I used a questionnaire in young university students (18-29). According to the results we can conclude that primarily the respondents visit social media pages during the selection of destination (59%).

During holiday 56% of the respondents used social media for contacting (Ráthonyi, 2013).

Cox et al. (2009) concluded that social media pages are primarily visited before travel which confirms my results but it also confirms the continuous spread of the use of these contents. Fotis et al., (2012) received reverse results who says these pages are visited after the travel to share their experience and photos.

Table 2: Use of social media during travel

Travel period	Statement	Percentage of respondents
Before travel/holiday	Collecting ideas where to travel	67,8%
	Selecting possible travel destinations	46,5%
	If it has to be confirmed that good destination was selected	32,3%
	Collecting ideas and information during search for accommodation	62,3%
	Collecting ideas and information during search for various leisure programmes	49,5%
During travel/holiday	During travel collect information about a e.g. sight of programme	52,6%
	During travel share my experience on various forums	9,3%
	During travel share my photos or videos with others (other travellers, friends, acquaintances)	29,6%
	Contacting with friends/family members	47,3%
	Use these pages not related to my travel	12,3%
After travel/holiday	After travel, share photos/videos taken during travel with others (other travellers, friends, acquaintances)	25,9%
	Write a review about the accommodation or other services	25,8%

Source: Own edition, adapted from COX et al., 2009; FOTIS et al., 2012

I examined if there was any significant difference between various stages considering genre and age as well. Considering genre it is interesting that it is a characteristic of women to share photos, videos on social media pages after travel. Search for various leisure programs on social media pages is a characteristic of men.

Considering age there was difference in the case of sharing photos and videos after travel which is typical in the age group 18-29.

As a summary we can conclude that the results justified the role of social media during the first phase of travel.

4. Conclusion

We can conclude that the respondents are using the social media pages during the whole planning process of travel but for various reasons and with various extent. In the planning phase before travel most of the consumers visit these social media sites to collect information but there is a

large number of users who use these sites during the selection of accommodation. Only third of users visit social media sites to confirm the correct selection of holiday destination. During travel the respondents collect information about a certain sight or programme and use social media sites for contacting. After travel every fourth user visits social media pages for example to share their experience and photos or write reviews. These results mean lower numbers comparing with the international trends where most of the users make the best of sharing their opinion and experience (e.g. phrasing critics related to the accommodation).

As far as organizations are concerned it can be said that information and communication technologies mainly affect the levels of operation, structure and strategy and decrease the cost of communication and other processes and increase effectiveness, productivity and competitiveness in the same time. The role of innovative ICT devices considering the decision

making of consumers during the whole process of travel is obvious because the availability of adequate qualitative and quantitative information is required for the new type of sophisticated consumers to make their decisions.

Tourism companies have to aspire for being aware of the latest technological trends and changes. There are several new technological innovation in the tourism industry which

appeared or going to appear in the near future such as new mobile technologies, tracking technologies, new smart devices, new social media tools, new sensors (NFC, RFID). In the following years "Smart World" (smart cities, smart destinations, smart hotels), "Internet of Things" and different cloud-based solutions (cloud computing) more and more come to the front.

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COMPARATIVE STUDY OF CERTAIN BENEFICIAL MINERAL CONTENT IN VARIOUS PLANT ORGANS

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Abstract: *The study aims to characterize the comparative content of beneficial minerals (iron, calcium, magnesium, manganese) in various organs of plants (root, stem, leaves, flowers) present in plant materials native: marigold (*Calendula officinalis*), french marigold (*Tagetes patula*), nettle (*Urtica dioica*), echinacea (*Echinacea angustifolia*), using the atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) technique.*

The experimental study showed different distribution of the minerals studied, preferential, depending on the plant organs.

Plants studied, from organic sources will be used as raw materials for making food supplements with effect in the prevention of certain diseases.

Keywords: *flame atomic spectrometry, heavy metals, plant organs.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Culture soils rich in minerals determine their accumulation in cultivated vegetable materials, preferentially in different plants organs (root, stem, leaves and flower). Mineral salts present in greater or lesser amounts in plants are needed for the biological activity of plants and other vital forms of environment.

To operate at full human body capacity, needs a daily intake of vitamins and minerals.

Iron occurs in the normal formation of red blood cells, which carry oxygen and various enzymes in the blood. Also the iron contributes to normal energy metabolism and optimal functioning of the immune system, reduce fatigue. Iron deficiency or malabsorption caused by deficient intake causes a deficiency anemia.

Calcium is the mineral that is found in all organs of the human body (blood, muscles, heart, nerves, etc.), helps strengthen the immune system, strengthens of bones and teeth, and sustain the skeletal structure of the body, helps absorption of nutrients in the body and contributes to transportation to the organs (for example to carry iron to the cell membranes), contributes to muscle function, helps the optimal functioning of the CNS, regulates blood clotting.

Manganese is an essential trace element for the body, especially of the beneficial effects on memory and for removing the feeling of fatigue.

Manganese also helps to fix calcium and iron in the body, helps digestion, accelerates metabolism and has an important role in the endocrine and also the sexual glands. It helps the synthesis of collagen that maintains firmness and elasticity of skin.

This study highlights the comparative results regarding content in minerals iron, calcium, magnesium and manganese, in various vegetable organs (roots, stems, leaves, flowers) from organic farming marigold (*Calendula officinalis*), french marigold (*Tagetes patula*), nettle (*Urtica dioica*), echinacea (*Echinacea angustifolia*).

The organs of plants containing minerals iron, calcium, magnesium, manganese will be in Hofigal company as raw materials for making food supplements with therapeutic potential and for cosmetics development in order to prevent various diseases and improve quality of life.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Selected plants organs as roots, stems, leaves, flowers of marigold (*Calendula officinalis*), french marigold (*Tagetes patula*), nettle (*Urtica dioica*), echinacea (*Echinacea angustifolia*) from organic farming were harvested and dried under

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temperature and humidity controlled conditions, after that chopped, crushed and analyzed for determination of mineral salts (iron, calcium, magnesium, manganese) using in flame atomic absorption spectrometry technique with a GBS Avanta PM spectrophotometer. The same conditions were analyzed for the soil culture from Hofigal greenhouses. The samples were processed ready to be analyzed by digestion with nitric acid, hydrogen peroxide and hydrochloric acid using a Berghof MWS-2 microwave digestion system with pressure.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Vegetable materials as root, stem, leaves, flowers, surveyed composition in minerals (iron, calcium, magnesium and manganese) from organic crops and soil culture and were characterized using absorption spectrometry technique in flame air- with acetylene. The results for all the organs of plant material (marigold, french marigold, echinacea and nettle) are shown in Figure 1 and soil mineral content characterization from the Hofigal greenhouses are in Table 1.

Table 1 Minerals content of the soil culture

Culture	soil	Fe [mg/100g]	Ca [mg/100g]	Mg [mg/100g]	Mn [mg/100g]
(Hofigal greenhouses)		1100.0	170.0	340.0	58.0

Fig. 1 The content of Fe, Ca, Mg and Mn from roots, stems, leaves, of marigold, french marigold, echinacea flowers and nettle

Analyzing the graphs from Figure 1 is observed a preferential distribution of iron in

root studied, followed by localization of the leaves, flowers and stems. The largest amount of calcium was found in nettle leaves (2800 mg

/ 100g), followed by marigold leaves (2000 mg / 100g), echinacea and calendula leaves with lower concentrations. For all plants studied calcium accumulation in various plant organs was done in the order: leaves > flowers > roots > stems. The largest amount of magnesium is found in the leaves and stems of marigold flowers and marigold and echinacea and nettle. Manganese has accumulated preferentially in marigold leaves and french marigold, the nettle flowers and echinacea root. The soil is rich in culture analyzed roll, followed by magnesium, calcium and manganese

CONCLUSIONS

In order to obtain dietary supplements with potential therapeutic and natural cosmetics has conducted a comparative study on the the minerals composition (iron, calcium, magnesium, manganese) of different plant organs (roots, stems, leaves, flowers) using the spectrometry flame atomic absorption technique.

Experimental study showed different distribution of mineral salts beneficial to the human body depending on the plant organ.

Based on extensive documentation of traditional and modern herbal medicine, and based on its own research on the minerals composition in these plants will develop new food supplements and cosmetics with high bioavailability.

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PHYTASE ACTIVITY OF MICROORGANISMS

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Abstract: Screening of microorganisms with phytase activity was executed among different species of bacteria and molds. It was found that molds mobilize phosphates from phytin more effectively than bacteria. As a result of multistage screening *A.niger* van Tieghem TI 12 was selected which produce extracellular phytase and dephosphorylate phytin up to 66,9 %.

Keywords: phytase, hydrolysis of phytic acid, microorganisms

1. Introduction

Phytases (*myo*-inositol hexakisphosphate 3-phosphohydrolase, EC 3.1.3.8, *myo*-inositol-hexakisphosphate 4-phosphohydrolase, EC 3.1.3.26, *myo*-inositol hexakisphosphate 5-phosphohydrolase, EC 3.1.3.72) are the group of phosphoric monoester hydrolases that catalyze hydrolysis of phytic acid (*myo*-inositol-hexakisphosphate) and generate *myo*-inositol phosphates and phosphates (Mullaney, 2000). Phytic acid is widespread in nature. It is present in all seeds and performs the function of the primary storage of phosphates in plants. Phosphate groups of phytic acid easily form insoluble metal-phytate chelate complexes with nutritionally important cations such as Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Fe³⁺, Zn²⁺ (Frossard, 2000).

It does metals inaccessible for absorption from intestinal path of human and animals. Sandberg et al. demonstrated that the addition of phytase (285 units/kg) with citric acid (3.125 g/kg) to leavening bread can enhance total iron bioavailability 15-fold. Therefore the aim of the use of phytase in the food industry - to remove phytic acid which acts as an antinutritional factor.

Screening of new fungal phytase with high specific activity or improved thermostability is actual for the food-processing industry (Bohn, 2008, Sanz-Penella, 2012).

2. Material and method

Screening of microorganisms was conducted among the cultures from collection of microorganisms of St. Petersburg State Technological Institute and from soil samples.

Screening of microorganisms was carried out on two phytin containing nutrient mediums:

- glucose-asparagine medium, g/l: glucose - 10, asparagine - 1, potassium sulphate - 0,2,

magnesium sulphate - 0,2, corn extract - 0,2, phytin - 10; agar - 20, pH 7,0;

phytin medium, g/l: phytin-10, ammonium sulphate - 1, magnesium sulphate - 0,2, potassium sulphate - 0,2, agar - 20, pH 7,0.

Phytase activity was detected by the presence of zones of phytin hydrolysis around the colonies of microorganisms on agar plates after 6-14 days of incubation at 30⁰C. Quantities of mobilized phosphates were defined at cultivation of investigated microorganisms on liquid phytin containing nutrient mediums of the same composition. The values of pH in the mediums were 7,0 for bacteria and 5,0 for fungi. Cultivation was carried out at 30⁰C in flasks on shaking apparatus (n=230 rpm). The volume of mediums in flask were 100 ml. The inoculum was (5,6 ±0,7) x 10⁶ CFU/ml and it was added to each flask in quantity 5 ml. The maintenance of free phosphates was measured every day during two weeks of cultivation by colorimetric method (Fiske, 1925). Determination of protein in culture liquids was performed by the method of Lowry (Lowry, 1951). Activity of acid phosphatase we measured by the speed of hydrolysis of phenolphthalein phosphate. In tube was added: 2 ml of 36 mM solution of phenolphthalein phosphate in 0,1 M acetate buffer (pH=4,0), 1 ml of cultural liquid. The mixture was incubated during 15 minutes at 30⁰C, than 1 ml of 1 M NaOH was added in the tube and measured at 540 nm against control. Control: 2 ml of 36 mM solution of phenolphthalein phosphate in 0,1 M acetate buffer (pH=4,0) was incubated for 15 minutes at 30⁰C, after that 1 ml of 1 M NaOH and 1 ml of cultural liquid were added in the tube. The enzyme activity was expressed as the number of micromoles of phenolphthalein which

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are cleaved during the hydrolysis of phenolphthalein phosphate for one minute at 30°C. The molar extinction coefficient was 4,1 mcM/ml.

For the definition of phytase activity in tube were added: 0,9 ml 0,05 M glycine buffer (pH+2,2), 0,1 ml 0,05 M Mg(NO₃)₂, 1 ml 0,005 M of phytic acid and 0,5 ml of cultural liquid. The mixture was incubated for 10 minutes at 30°C, than 0,5 ml of 5% TCA was added. Control was the same mixture but 0,5 ml of cultural liquid we added after addition of 0,5 ml of 5% TCA. The content of phosphates in the tubes was measured by colorimetric method (Fiske, 1925). Activity of phytase was expressed as the number of micromoles of phosphates which are cleaved during hydrolysis of phytic acid for one minute at 30°C (Skowronski, 1976).

3. Results and discussion

Screening of phytase producers was spent in some stages. At the first stage we selected the microorganisms which form zones of hydrolysis of phytin at growth on agar mediums. Microorganisms of 67 species from 29 genera were investigated. The majority of cultures used phytin as a source of phosphorus at growth on both mediums. *Aspergillus niger* van Tieghem TI 12, *Penicillium lignorum* Stolk, *Bacillus megaterium*, *Sarcina lutea*, *Streptomyces cinereoruber*, *Streptomyces ladakanum*, *Streptomyces violaceus* well-developed both on glucose-asparagine and phytin mediums. *Aspergillus melleus* Yukawia, *Aspergillus repens* De Bary, *Aspergillus terricola* Marchal, *Mucor mucedo* Linnaeus:Fries, *Penicillium urticae* Bainier, *Streptomyces bellus* grew more rapidly on phytin medium. Two species of genus *Penicillium* – *P.diversum* Raper and Fennel and *P.vulpinum* Seifert and Samson - developed only on glucose-asparagine medium.

Since growth on agar mediums does not allow to define quantity of mobilized phosphates, at the second stage the selection was carried out by the ability of microorganisms to accumulate phosphates at growth on liquid phytin-containing medium. Cultivation was carried out during two weeks. We investigated 38 species of micromycetes and 20 species of bacterial cultures which demonstrated ability to form zones of hydrolysis of phytin at growth on agar mediums.

For the majority of bacteria the maximum quantity of phosphates in the medium does not exceed 2% from theoretically possible and it was observed after 3-4 day of cultivation. Three

bacterial cultures *Micrococcus lysodeikticus*, *Azotobacter chroococcum*, *Enterobacter cloacae* were not capable to mobilize phosphates from phytin. The maximum quantity of mobilized phosphates was observed at cultivation of *Bacillus polymyxa* – 5,2 %, *Mycobacterium lacticolum* – 3,9 %, *Bacillus mycoides* – 2,7 %. Among nine species of actinomycetes only *Nocardioopsis dassonvillei* did not accumulate phosphates on liquid phytin medium. The most active culture was *Streptomyces violaceus* which mobilized 5,9 % of phosphates from phytin. The maximum quantity of phosphates in the medium by the actinomycetes were accumulated on the 7-8 days of cultivation. Among investigated micromycetes only *Penicillium vulpinum* mobilized less than 2 % of phosphates from phytin. The best results by the quantity of mobilized phosphates are received with cultures *Penicillium glaucum* - 8,2 %, *Verticillium fungicola* - 10,2 %, *Aspergillus niger* - 11,8 %. It is worth noting that the species of one genus significantly differ on this parameter. Time of achievement of the maximum growth of phosphates in the medium varied for different micromycetes. For the majority of species this time was 11 days, and for the most active culture - *Aspergillus niger* - 7 days.

Attracts attention the fact that both species of genera *Penicillium* - *Penicillium diversum* and *Penicillium vulpinum*, which did not grow on agar phytin-containing medium, grew and mobilized phosphates on liquid phytin medium. Probably, it testifies that agar phytin medium is not optimum for screening microorganisms with phytase activity, and this stage of screening may be omitted. It is known that presence in nutrient medium of readily available source of carbon may influence on hydrolysis of phytin by microorganisms (Ebune, 1995). Therefore at a third stage of screening the ability of micromycetes to accumulate phosphates at growth on liquid glucose-asparagine medium with phytin was investigated. For this purpose the micromycetes belonging to different genus and species with differing levels of accumulation of phosphates at growth on liquid phytin medium have been chosen. For the majority of cultures it was observed the increase of accumulation of phosphates at growth on the medium with glucose. Most considerably the concentration of phosphates increased in culture liquids of *Aspergillus melleus* (in 10 times) and *Penicillium vulpinum* (in 8 times). However four cultures (*Penicillium cyclopium*, *Penicillium glaucum*,

Penicillium notatum, *Verticillium fungicola*) showed the decrease of concentration of phosphates in 1,5-2,5 times. Thus, the reaction of micromycetes for the presence of easily accessible source of carbon (glucose) in the medium is unique. Concentration of protein is an indirect indicator of synthesis of extracellular enzymes. On the next step the quantity of phosphates in the liquid glucose-asparagine medium was compared with the synthesis of extracellular protein. It was established that the degree of hydrolysis of phytin by representatives of genus *Aspergillus* in 2-3 times above that of others micromycetes. Especially allocated *Aspergillus niger* van Tieghem *TI 12* which dephosphorylate phytin up to 66,9 %. The concentration of protein in culture liquids of the investigated cultures including *Aspergillus niger* is insignificant - from 0,16 to 0,27 mg/ml. Only in the case of *Aspergillus repens* the protein content in the culture liquid was 0,42 mg/ml.

At the closing stage of screening we determined the activity of acid phosphatase and phytase in culture liquids of *A.niger* and *A.repens*. Fermentation was conducted on glucose-asparagine medium with the maintenance of phytin 10 g/l and on glucose-asparagine medium without phytin. Yeast extract in nutrient medium contains a small amount of phosphates and this makes possible the growth of fungi in the medium without phytin. At growth on the medium with phytin *A.niger* synthesized more active acid phosphatase than *A.repens*. The maximum activity of enzyme *A.niger* (0,3 E/mg) was observed on eighth day of fermentation. It in 2,5 times above the maximum activity of acid phosphatase of *A.repens* (0,12 E/mg) on the sixth day of growth. Absence of phytin in the mediums has various impacts on biosynthesis of extracellular acid phosphatase of selected cultures of micromycetes. Activity of acid phosphatase in culture liquid of *A.niger* has increased 3,3 times and achieved 0,98 E/mg on the sixth day of cultivation. At the same time acid phosphatase has not been found in culture liquid of *A.repens* at all. So it can be assumed that the acid phosphatase of *A.repens* is inducible enzyme. Growth of *A.niger* on glucose-asparagine medium without phytin was accompanied by an increase not only of acid phosphatase activity, but also by phytase activity. The maximum of phytase activity was observed in the stationary growth phase at ninth day of

fermentation. Perhaps the synthesis of acid phosphatase and phytase by *Aspergillus niger* van Tieghem *TI 12* is subjected to negative regulation by phosphates of the medium.

Conclusion

Thus as a result of multistage screening the new producer of phytase – micromycetes *Aspergillus niger* van Tieghem *TI 12* was selected. This micromycetes produce extracellular phytase in liquid medium in the absence of a source of phosphorus. At the same time its produce extracellular acid phosphatase in liquid mediums with and without source of phosphorus. This combination of enzymatic activities make *Aspergillus niger* van Tieghem *TI 12* an interesting object for further investigation.

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APPLICATION OF EDI TECHNOLOGIES IN THE FOOD SUPPLY CHAINS

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Abstract: Due to globalisation, the complexity of food supply chains are increasingly becoming more complex. The consumers' trust in food, triggered and affected by a number of food crises, is low. Today, consumers expect safe and high quality food and demand information about the origin of their food. Food safety and traceability are keys to companies' business survival and great efforts and resources are devoted to them. The ever increasing requirements for the level of tracking and tracing in turn require even more advanced IT techniques. The speed of a tracing operation is often the reason to store information about lots and tracing in an ERP system, but such a system can also be used to support RF scanning, to read barcodes and for EDI to communicate with clients and suppliers. Besides speed this also increases the efficiency of registration and this ensures that the data stored is correct and complete. In this paper we discuss the criteria for efficient and effective application of EDI technologies in the food supply chains.

Keywords: EDI, traceability, food supply chain

1. Introduction

Increasing pressure by consumers, provoked by numerous food scandals, forced the European Union and national authorities to strengthen the regulations on food safety and traceability along food supply chains.

Commercial members of food chains are only partially prepared to implement such regulations and to fulfil the requirements. Major impediments are that existing IT-solutions are in most cases limited to single enterprises. There is an absence of authorities that control whole chains, small-scale enterprises at the supply and primary production level have to interact with large, (sometimes) multi-national groups of companies and food chains show significant fractures in data flows. A coordination and motivation problem crystallized as a key challenge in the provision of traceability and quality management. The coordination problem results from the division of labour in the value-added chain of agribusiness.

This leads to the development of organizational intersections, which act as fractures in the information flow, with the result that the information flow is interrupted. The motivation problem is also a result of the division of labour.

Diverse people and enterprises with differing goals are involved in the production, processing and distribution of food stuffs. The diverse actors must be motivated to ensure the complete and correct gathering and sharing of information needed to guarantee traceability, even if this does not contribute directly to their own interests (Theuvsen, 2003). There is no blank before punctuation marks (comma, full stop, colon, etc.); after punctuation marks a blank space is inserted.

Information technologies (IT) have the potential to support the agri- food sector in coping with the challenges but they are also key enablers for some of the developments to take place (Herdon et al., 2014).

Today's drive towards globalisation builds on modern communication technology, but it is also accelerated by the technology's communication ability. From this dual perspective, the adoption of IT by members of the agri- food sector is no longer a question of choice but of survival (Schiefer & Zazueta, 2003). The exchange of business documents does not work well if the business partners do not integrate the related business processes. Automation often requires business process re-engineering (Riggins & Mukhopadhyay, 1994) and enterprise application

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integration (Gulledge, 2006). For example, business rules for automatic order processing have to be defined and a middleware system or a web portal has to be integrated with an ERP system before online sales can be supported (Nurmilaakso, 2008).

1.1. EDI (Electronic Data Interchange)

There would be fewer problems in supply chain integration if all companies used the same information systems, similar meanings for terms and similar modes of operations. Organizational units within a company may also face integration problems (Herdon et. al., 2015). Although many differences between business partners are inevitable, standards can bring order by reducing the complexity and uncertainty. Standardization of business documents, business processes and messaging leads to harmonization of meanings for terms, modes of operations and messaging interfaces (Nurmilaakso, 2008).

An e-business framework is a standard for information sharing within and between companies that enables the exchange of standardized data, e.g. in the Electronic Data Interchange (EDI) or Extensible Markup Language (XML) formats (Nurmilaakso & Kotinurmi, 2004).

Electronic Data Interchange (EDI) is the process of using computers to exchange business documents and data between companies. Previously, fax machines or traditional mail was used to exchange documents. Mailing and faxing are still used in business, but EDI is a much quicker way to do the same thing. EDI is used by a huge number of businesses.

As shown in Figure 1, during 2014, 81 % of EU enterprises selling electronically used a website or "apps", while 33 % used EDI-type sales.

Fig. 1. E-sales broken down by web and EDI-type sales, (% enterprises with e-sales) (Eurostat, 2014 (isoc_bde15dec))

The following components and tools are necessary for performing EDI:

- Trade Agreement - a legally binding trade agreement between you and your trading partner.
- Standard Document Format - the standard agreed upon format for the document to be electronically transmitted.
- EDI Translation Management Software - software used to convert the document your application's format into the agreed upon standard format. For optimum performance the translation software should be on the same platform as your business application.
- Communications Software - a programming tool that enables you to write communications

protocols, or a separate application. It can be a module to the translator or a separate software application.

- Point-to-Point - a direct communication link from one computer to another. Some trading partners offer a direct connection to their EDI computer. Trading partners may opt for this method of communication instead of using internet.

Companies can more easily use different information systems as long as they use the same e-business frameworks in the same way. Nowadays, it is clear that EDI is no longer limited to the VANs (value-added network) but it can also be implemented over the Internet (Angeles, 2000).

1.2. Editing and printing the paper

For more than 20 years, companies have been using electronic data interchange to transmit structured business documents like orders or invoices electronically. As opposed to paper-based communication, EDI is designed to make communication between different systems. But although there undoubtedly is large savings potential, the use of EDI is by far not as widespread as one could expect.

Forrester Research (2011) estimates that only about 5% of the companies which could profit from its use actually use EDI. The main reason is that especially small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) try to avoid the considerable setup- and operating costs of traditional EDI solutions (Segev et. al. 1997) Therefore, the use of EDI is mainly reserved for large companies, and one of the main reasons for the introduction of EDI is usually pressure from larger business partners.

A first step to the reduction of costs of EDI solutions is the use of the Internet with its existing communication infrastructure as a means of transportation for EDI messages. A number of different communication protocols can be used for the transfer of EDI messages over the Internet. Depending upon the task, the exchange can be made via FTP (File Transfer Protocol), HTTP (Hypertext Transfer Protocol) or SMTP (Simple Mail Transfer Protocol), while the data are encoded either with PGP (Pretty Good Privacy), S/MIME (Secure Multipurpose Internet Mail Extension) or SSL (Secure Socket Layer). Low cost in combination with the large number of emerging technologies for the Internet may now make a considerable contribution to the increase of EDI users and especially allow SMEs to participate in EDI networks.

The obvious advantage of using the Web as a medium for EDI communication is that the only (client side) prerequisite is an Internet connection and a web browser (Curtis, 1996). All communication uses the ubiquitous HTTP-protocol. Security issues can be addressed by using SSL, for example (Westarp et al. 1999). Thus, all required infrastructure is most probably almost anywhere available without forcing the partners to invest hefty amounts of money. In this context, form-based EDI proves to be a good idea for large companies seeking ways of having their small customers send their data in a standardized format.

The eXtensible Markup Language XML has the potential to be the data format of choice used together with the programming language of choice for the Web, Java, to enable the next step in the evolution of EDI. The use of open standards can considerably reduce the time and money spent on implementing a solution. By avoiding proprietary formats, the danger of investment ruins is decreased and future-oriented solutions can be developed. Especially XML can contribute to the opening of EDI networks. While traditional EDI relationships are often long-term and highly integrated relationships, which are worthwhile only with a large number of transactions and for a long term, the willingness to invest into open, compatible IT-infrastructures is stronger at any point of the value chain, especially for smaller partners. Traditionally, the establishment of compatibility between different EDI solution-systems was achieved through deep integration of the EDI standard into the applications of the communication partners.

1.3. EDI Standards

All of EDI standards first appeared in the early to mid 1980s. The standards prescribe the formats, character sets, and data elements used in the exchange of business documents and forms. The EDI standard says which pieces of information are mandatory for a particular document, which pieces are optional and give the rules for the structure of the document. Standards are generally updated each year.

Since business partners have to know what, when and how information should be shared (Herdon et al., 2012), data formats, such as XML, are useful in syntactic interpretation but insufficient in semantic interpretation (Nurmilaakso & Kotinurmi, 2004). Full-automation in supply chain integration requires standards that answer the questions what, when and how. Before the late 1990s, these standards were called EDI standards.

There are four major sets of EDI standards:

- The UN-recommended UN/EDIFACT is the only international standard and is predominant outside of North America.
- The US standard ANSI ASC X12 (X12) is predominant in North America.
- The TRADACOMS standard developed by the ANA (Article Numbering Association) is predominant in the UK retail industry.
- The ODETTE standard used within the European automotive industry

Shim et al. (2000) have used the term B2B frameworks, Medjahed et al. (2003) B2B interaction standards and Nurmilaakso & Kotinurmi (2004) e-business frameworks. An e-business framework is a standard that limits the syntax but extends the semantics of the data format in the business context. The e-business frameworks specify business documents, business processes and messaging for exchange of standardized data (Nurmilaakso & Kotinurmi, 2004)

1.4. Cost of EDI

Prices for EDI applications vary from free (for very simple one-function products) to several thousands of dollars for full-function applications. The final price you pay depends upon several things:

- The Expected Volume of Electronic Documents. Generally speaking, PC products cost less, but handle only a few documents and trading partners. Midrange EDI packages can be a little more expensive, but handle a much larger volume of EDI. If you anticipate multiple documents or trading partners, a midrange EDI system is a much better choice.
- The Conformance of the EDI Translation Software. Some products look like a bargain, but as your EDI needs grow, hidden costs (such as having to purchase new transaction sets) suddenly appear. You may pay more for a program with an integrated mapper, but you'll avoid purchasing overlays and maps in the future.
- Implementation Time. Some applications are easier to learn and use than others. The more time you spend in training, the more time it takes to get into production mode. If your time frame is tight, look for a translator that doesn't require training before implementation.
- Maintenance Fees. Most companies charge an annual maintenance fee that is usually a percentage of the translator's list price. This fee should include software updates, standards updates, technical support, and customer service.

1.5. Advantages of EDI

The Save Money. The cost of paper and paper processing is incredibly high compared to a properly implemented EDI program.

- **End Repetition.** If your trading partner wants a copy of a document, instead of calling you they simply check their mailbox. This results in a

great time savings from not having to copy and fax/mail copies of business documents.

- **Save Time.** EDI also saves time over paper processing since the transfer of information from computer to computer is automatic.
- **Improve Customer Service.** The quick transfer of business documents and marked decrease in errors allow you to do business faster and more efficient.
- **Expand Your Customer Base.** Thus with improved customer service, you can ultimately expand your customer base. Many large manufacturers and retailers are ordering their suppliers to institute an EDI program. So, when evaluating a new product to carry or a new supplier to use, the ability to do EDI is a big plus.

1.6. Disadvantages of EDI

Too Many Standards. There are too many standards bodies developing standard documents formats for EDI. For example your company may be following the X12 standard format, while your trading partner follows the EDIFACT standard format.

- **Changing Standards.** Each year, most standards bodies publish revisions to the standards. This poses a problem to EDI users. You may be using one version of the standard while your trading partners are still using older versions.
- **EDI is Too Expensive.** Some companies are only doing business with others who use EDI. If a company wants to do business with these organizations, they have to implement an EDI program. This expense may be very costly for small companies.
- **Limit Your Trading Partners.** Some large companies tend to stop doing business with companies who don't comply with EDI. For example Wal Mart is only doing business with other companies that use EDI. The result of this is a limited group of people you can do business with (StudyZones.com).

2 . EDI technologies in the agri-food industry

The ever increasing requirements for the level of tracking and tracing in turn require even more advanced IT techniques. Increasing the speed of a tracing operation is often the reason to store information about lots and tracing in an ERP system, but such a system can also be used to support RF scanning, to read barcodes and for EDI to communicate with clients and suppliers.

Besides speed this also increases the efficiency of registration and this ensures that the data stored is correct and complete. Furthermore, an information system which has been set up well will also reduce dependency on people, because some of the knowledge is stored in the information system itself. There are three main aspects of the provision of information:

- Identification of the lot which is to be monitored. A lot has a unique identity created by the combination of item number and lot number.
- Registration and administration of the lot history: when was the raw material received from a supplier, when was this used in production, etc.
- Communication about the lot with other links in the chain. An important roll in this communication is played by the EAN standards for barcodes and EDI.

2.1. AGRO EDI Europe (AEE)

Since 1992, Agro EDI Europe is working on organization and standardization of electronic data interchanges on the agricultural and agro-industrial sectors. Today the association gathers about 280 members coming from several sectors (agricultural input, agro equipment, software editors, accounting centers, bank, insurance, logistics, storage, analysis laboratories, etc.).

Since 2001, within the Agro EDI Europe association, the economic partners of the farm, agreed to define a standard data-processing format of exchange for the feedback related to the data crop sheet: the DAPLOS message. When developing this "plot message", AEE works addressed the problems of follow-up of cultivation operations and computation of gross margin, and benchmarking of crop husbandry techniques. Later, AEE members turned to the domain of traceability, all tools enabling farm production management being marketed today as traceability solutions. AEE created the "plot message" (DAPLOS: Data Plot Sheet) which is a standard for describing information related to a specific cultural plot, in order to facilitate data exchange between various information systems.

Software editors in France make many efforts to stick to this standard while developing programs and databases, mainly by implementing some export / import functions for writing or reading data according to AEE message. AEE DAPLOS message has focused attention on the relationships between the producer and service suppliers, and it does not especially address the Administration. If compared with AgroXML (see below) the data description is not included since it is an EDIFACT message. But the recent submission of the DAPLOS message to ISO authorities is an important step forward.

AGRO EDI EUROPE participates to the adaptation and the evolution of existing standardized messages (invoice, orders, despatch advice...). Working groups take part in new messages development, adapted to food industries needs, in close connection with standardization organizations. Sectoral rules of use, codification & legal aspects are also studied in their food applications (AGRO EDI EUROPE, 2016).

2.2. agriXchange

agriXchange is a EU-funded coordination and support action to setup a network for developing a system for common data exchange in the agricultural sector. The project consortium consists of 15 partners from 11 countries covering different disciplines, stakeholder views and experiences with information management and standardization.

aXTool is the practical implementation of the Reference Framework design within the agriXchange project. The agriXchange Reference Framework supports and enhances information sharing of existing data exchange standards, best practices and proven solutions to the agriXchange community members in a context-aware way. aXTool contains functionalities such as search, contribute, discussion and evaluation by user experience, and also a mechanism for quality management.

Fig. 2. aXTool (agrixchange.org, 2016)

2.3. agroXML

Farmers are subject to a multitude of obligations concerning documentation of agricultural practices. agroXML is the result of a tight cooperation with producers of agricultural software and online service providers, which integrate agroXML into their software and. agroXML introduces a standard, which facilitates data storage and exchange. agroXML is based on the international standard XML and consists of the agroXML-Schema and several content lists. agroXML is a language that enables the description of agricultural data that will then enable a complete documentation of agricultural production processes. The objective of agroXML is to allow information exchanges without redundancy between the different actors: land owners, farmers, advisory services, food industry, etc.

An XML Schema defines electronic documents for data exchange. The agroXML schema is based on a model of the real-world processes in agricultural production. They are represented in a tree-like hierarchy. With agroXML unproblematic data communication can be possible along the production and supply chain and with the agricultural administration (Fig. 2), with the advantage that farmers or other users need not to prepare and put already determined data separately into the system. An additional objective of agroXML is to enable the use of already determined data for several purposes without having to repeated data input or data processing (Doluschitz & Kunisch, 2004; <http://agroXML.de>).

Fig. 3. Communication enabled by agroXML (Doluschitz & Kunisch, 2004)

Potential users of agroXML include anyone along the production and supply chain in the agricultural sector.

1. Farmers. In future farmers will not be tied to a specific collection or processing of data during the extensive conversion of documentation duties. There is no need any more to register data. agroXML facilitates an obstacle free communication with the agricultural administration, consulting services and software companies possible, without requiring an extra data input. Any already determined and documented data for production processes, which has been stored in any software, e.g. in a file for different types, are available at any time for further use.

2. Consulting services. Integrated plant production requires that agronomic measures have to be adapted to the habitat conditions of the single type as well as to the needs of the plant. For conversion there are many instruments, which are partly available at the place of business, or have to be purchased (soil testing, monitoring of stock, weather station, warning system, models for prognosis, etc.) The potential of the integrated plant production may be fully and most effectively used by the farmer, if consultants and extension specialists will in future provide access to individual and type oriented choice with the help of internet technologies. This way of acquiring consulting services makes precision farming particularly interesting (Doluschitzund et al., 2005).

3. Software companies. The need of a standardized data exchange language like agroXML will increase and accelerate the development progress for agricultural software companies. Agricultural software is increasingly dependent on the data input from outside the place of business. On the one hand this concerns the updating and care of forms and demands for application of subsidies, and on the other hand the use of information concerning the means of the business. The corresponding updates require more staff and cause higher costs, which can be reduced substantially if this information will be available in a standardized data format via the internet. Increasingly the customers will also expect that the software with systems for the business und type oriented online consulting services can communicate without problems, which will be much easier when applying

agroXML. (Doluschitz, 2004; <http://www.agroXML.de>).

2.4. Trace2p2

The P2P Project, co-founded by the European Community, aims to study, develop and test different methodologies and tools supporting the quick collection of information from different traceability systems, in order to define and develop a unified way to collect information automatically from the various traceability systems operating at the different companies. In this way each company can choose its own traceability system that best fits and on the other side customers, citizens and authorized persons will have a unified approach to inquire automatically for product details via Internet.

The main goals of the P2P project are to define a Methodology (Trace Methodology) and a Software Architecture that is the base to solve the key issues of integration. It means to conceive and develop a solution aimed at supporting quick collection of information from different traceability systems of companies belonging to a given agri-food value chain, giving reason to the whole value chain traceability. A pilot system will be developed for the swine value chain.

Technically the most important part of the software is a communication protocol to share the information, the TRACE-XML protocol. The TRACE-XML protocol defines the minimum set of information to trace each product batch.

The TRACE-XML protocol will represent the first step to define a standard to automatically access traceability information and documents of each company belonging to the agri-food sector. As for example, it could contain a subset of information and rules of the ebXML standard. The TRACE-XML protocol could represent an open standard that could address not only the swine, but also the whole agri-food sector.

For summarizing the main expected results from the project are:

- Trace Methodology: a methodology supporting traceability information collection in the companies (in particular how and what information);
- Trace-XML protocol: a minimum set of information to trace each batch and the related communication protocol;
- Trace-SW: a software tool supporting collection, archiving and management of information and documents related to the traceability;

3. Conclusion

Food quality and traceability became an important issue in the last decade. That was primarily the result of a number of major food crises such as BSE and dioxin crisis that damaged seriously consumer's confidence on food industry. These striking examples of food deficiency had shown not only the vulnerability of food industry upon food quality but also revealed serious economic implications. It was clear cut that food crisis can not only affect consumer's health, but also food business's economic results and financial stability. While EDI in itself is not new, its technological standardization based on the internet technology and the communication language XML opens the way for a broad based acceptance and implementation. Initially, the primary focus of EDI was efficiency improvement. However, it is a necessary requirement for the intensification of information flows in quality and food safety management between enterprises in the food supply chain. (Schiefer, 2003)

While most firms used EDI for the frequent and routine transactions, invoices and purchasing

orders, they were not using EDI as often for the transactions that are more coordinating, such as transferring traceability data, production, and sales activities. This suggests that firms may see EDI as a tool for improving efficiencies rather than a tool for developing SCM.

EDI decreases coordination costs because the essence of coordination involves communicating and processing information. The electronic integration effect saves time and avoids errors. This shifts economic activities from companies to markets (Nurmilaakso, 2008). Although EDI does not necessarily increase sales, its use can reduce operating costs as computer to computer exchange is much less expensive than traditional methods of document exchange. The use of EDI can also speed up and reduce errors in information sharing. However, the use of EDI has mainly concentrated on larger companies, smaller companies often use EDI only because of pressure from their business partners or competitors.

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A NEW PHYTOTHERAPEUTIC PRODUCT INVESTIGATED FOR ITS ACTION IN CERTAIN ALLERGIC DERMOPATHIES FOR FELINES

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Abstract: *The authors present a study on a phytotherapeutic, indigenous product with high potential for use in veterinary medical practice. This product has a complex action and proves effectiveness even in some of the allergic dermopathies at felines. For this reason, the authors chose to certify the action of their new phytotherapeutic product, namely Arsutrat-Plagotrat by testing in the veterinary clinics of the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest. Studies are concerned with revealing its reliability in the cases of different allergic dermatitis, both as adjuvant in therapy and independent product.*

Keywords: *veterinary medical practice, phytotherapeutic product, feline eosinophilic complex*

1. Introduction

The phytotherapeutic product Arsutrat-Plagotrat gel has been designed for use in veterinary practice on the strength of its wealth in natural ingredients with synergistic activity conferring decongestants, anti-inflammatory, healing, analgesic properties and supporting the regeneration of damaged skin tissue.

This new natural product has proven efficacy in numerous pathologies especially in surgical vet pathology. On the other hand, we have decided to emphasize its action in dermatologic pathologies on the basis of the priority that dermopathies deal in feline disease occurrence, the most common forms being the allergic dermopathies.

In this category, several cases of Allergic dermatitis were studied, clustered under the universal heading of "feline eosinophilic complex" with different etiologies: food allergic dermatitis, atopic dermatitis, contact dermatitis caused by hypersensitivity to stings of haematophagous insects. For each category, therapeutic allopathic protocols do exist, used with more or less effectiveness in curing such cases.

For this reason, the authors chose to certify the action of their new phytotherapeutic product, Arsutrat-Plagotrat by testing in the veterinary clinics of the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest. Studies are concerned with revealing its reliability in the cases of different allergic dermatitis, both as adjuvant in therapy and independent product.

The administration of Arsutrat-Plagotrat gel to cats within the survey was decided on the basis of

establishing a positive and differential diagnosis by clinical and paraclinical examination in comparison with other diseases (skin parasitosis, autoimmune diseases, bacterial and fungal diseases), which clinically display by the same signs, namely: itching and localized or diffuse hypotrichosis.

2. Materials and working procedure

During 2015, a total of 30 cats with various allergic dermatitis were taken into the study, and treated with Arsutrat-Plagotrat gel following the diagnosis. Among all, 12 cases were chosen for presentation (the most representative in revealing the efficacy of treatment). Those cats were of different breeds and different ages and brought by their owners to the veterinary clinics of Faculty of Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest since suffering from various skin diseases.

After selection, the cases taken into study reached the dermatologic clinic where owners were questioned to obtain a thorough history of the space where the animals lived, were fed, of the antiparasitical treatment carried along time, etc. They were then passed to a detailed clinical examination, with high care on the aspect and topography of wounds.

In order to obtain each dermatological diagnosis, compulsory laboratory tests were conducted (biochemical and hematological). Also, they were submitted to the cytomorphological exam of skin lesions (either by biopsy or by scraping or footprint) where skin samples were displayed on slides, and stained panoptic MGG after drying.

To exclude a dermatophytosis, Wood's lamp examination was performed and eventually mycological examination by sowing hairs and scraped skin on Sabouraud media with Chloramphenicol.

Moreover, a bacteriologic test with antibiogram was carried out when lesions got over infected for starting the treatment with antibiotics.

To avert a food allergy, an exclusion diet was established using industrial food with hydrolyzed protein, hypoallergenic or non-allergenic and monoproteic, classic food.

From the 12 studied cases of allergic dermopathies framed in the "feline eosinophilic complex", 6 cases were diagnosed with atopic dermatitis: 5 cases of food dermatitis, 1 case of dermatitis caused by insect stings (fleas).

For each of the 12 cases, details upon the clinical signs presented by the subjects, as well as the performed laboratory investigations are centralized in Table 1. It also includes the diagnostic, the applied treatment and some useful remarks for each subject.

3. Results and discussions

Table 1

No	Subject	Clinical signs	Laboratory Investigations	Diagnosis	Treatment	Remarks
1	Feline Mixed breed Male 5 years	Single nodular lesion with exudate Coalescent papules and plaques Pruritus	Citologic examination Trichoscopic examination Parasitological examination by repeated dermal scraping Direct examination Hemoleucogram	Eosinophilic granuloma at abdominal level Atopic dermatitis	Anti-biotherapy Cephalexin; Local: Arsutrat-Plagotrat, 26 days	An Elizabethan collar was applied Total healing in 26 days
2	Feline European Male 5 years	Erythema, erosion, scaling, scratching lesions, hypotrichosis located on the external pinna of the left ear, pruritus	Parasitological examination Direct examination Skin cytological examination Wood lamp test Microbiologic examination Hemoleucogram	Atopic dermatitis	Anti-biotherapy Cephalexin Local: Arsutrat-Plagotrat, 4 weeks	An Elizabethan collar was applied Total healing in 30 days
3	Feline Angora Mixed breed Female 11 years	Localized hypotrichosis, scabs, scratching lesions Pruritus	Parasitological examination Direct examination Skin cytological examination Trichoscopic examination Wood lamp test Hemoleucogram	Food allergic dermatitis	Diet: Z /D Hill's Ultra Allergen free Local: Arsutrat-Plagotrat, 3-4 weeks	Pruritus intensifying during first days, that was succumbed after 5 days An Elizabethan collar was applied
4	Feline Mixed breed Female 3 years	Localized hypotrichosis, scratching lesions, scabs on the pinna Ulcers in the lower abdomen	Parasitological examination Direct examination Cytological examination Trichoscopic examination Wood lamp test Mycological examination Hemoleucograma	Food allergic dermatitis	Non-allergenic diet with hydrolyzed protein Antibiotic: Cephalexin Local: Arsutrat-Plagotrat	Total healing after 4 weeks of treatment
	Feline European	Ulcerations on ventral cervical region Crusts on the inner	Direct examination Parasitological examination Wood lamp test Skin cytological		Non-allergenic diet with hydrolyzed protein Antibiotic:	An Elizabethan collar was applied Slow healing in 46 days, because of the

5	Male 14 years	pinna Pruritus	examination Biochemistry test: Kidney failure Hematologic examination Peripheral blood cytological examination	Food allergic dermatitis	Pradofloxacin Local: Arsutrat-Plagotrat, 46 days	need to follow the renal diet and because pruritus appeared after changing hydrolyzed protein diet resulting in new lesions.
6	Feline Mixed breed Male 5 years	Hypotrichosis and Scratching lesions on the external side of thighs Intense pruritus	Parasitological examination Hemoleucogram Peripheral blood cytological examination Skin cytological examination	Hypersensitivity reaction to flea bites	External disinfestation and habitat disinfestation dermatological diet Local: Clorhexidine Solution Arsutrat-Plagotrat, 22 days	Healing after 3 weeks
7	Feline European 2 years	Crusts and hypotrichosis localized at shoulders	Parasitological examination Direct examination Skin cytological examination	Atopic dermatitis	Non-allergenic diet with hydrolyzed protein Local: Arsutrat-Plagotrat, 18 days	Healing after 18 days
8	Feline European Female 6 years	Localized hypotrichosis and pruritus at lower abdominal level	Wood lamp test mycological examination Parasitological examination Skin cytological examination Hemoleucogram Peripheral blood cytological examination	Food allergic dermatitis	Non-allergenic diet with hydrolyzed protein Local: Arsutrat-Plagotrat, 4 weeks	An Elizabethan collar was applied Improvements in 14 days, healed in 4 weeks.
9	Feline British Short Hair Male 8 months	Erythematous lesion with ulcerative areas, dark brown scabs on the muzzle (cheeks) Intense pruritus.	Wood lamp test Parasitological examination Direct examination Cytological examination Bacteriological examination Hemoleucogram	Atopic dermatitis	Non-allergenic diet Pradofloxacin, intern Ciprofloxacin, locally, first 7 days of treatment, followed by applying only Arsutrat-Plagotrat for 46 days	An Elizabethan collar was applied Nail protection for claws A relapse at the chin level after 2 weeks of treatment. Healing for both injuries 46 days
10	Feline European Male 2 years	Scratching lesions, erythema, hypotrichosis of the face	Wood lamp test Parasitological examination Direct examination Cytological examination Hemoleucogram	Food allergic dermatitis	Non-allergenic diet with hydrolyzed protein Local Arsutrat-Plagotrat	An Elizabethan collar was applied Relapse after 3 weeks in the cervical area because of accidental deviation from hydrolyzed protein diet. Cured in 5 weeks.
11	Feline European Female 3 years	Hypotrichosis located in the lower limbs, abdomen and right forelimb	Wood lamp test Mycological examination Parasitological examination Direct examination Cytological examination from scraped skin Hemoleucograma	Atopic dermatitis	Non-allergenic diet with hydrolyzed protein Local: Arsutrat-Plagotrat	An Elizabethan collar was applied Cured in 4 weeks.

12	Feline European Female 5 years	Partial trimming at abdominal level and in the upper half of the hind legs (caused by excessive licking)	Wood lamp test Mycological examination Parasitological examination Direct examination Skin cytological examination Hemoleucogram	Atopic dermatitis	Non-allergenic diet with hydrolyzed protein Local: Arsutrat-Plagotrat	An Elizabethan collar was applied Cured in 27 weeks
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According to the established dermatological diagnosis, several types of therapies were used:

- In over-infected allergic dermatitis, after realizing the antibiogram exam, it was necessary to administer antibiotics, followed by topical application of the Arsutrat-Plagotrat gel.
- Both for food allergic dermatitis and atopic dermatitis, a certain diet was established simultaneously with local application gel of Arsutrat-Plagotrat gel.
- In case of allergic dermatitis caused by haematophagous insect bites, an external delousing was repeatedly conducted both for the affected animals and of potentially of cohabiting animals and repeated disinfection of their habitat.
- In some cases, due to increased itching and after applying the gel, it was necessary to put a collar around the cat's neck to limit head movements and to prevent licking.

The location of allergic dermatitis lesions was varied; anatomic clinical issues were also very different: redness, scratching lesions, erosions, ulcers, nodular formations, eventually with purulent exudate etc.

In feline dermatopathies and especially those that are allergic, in order to establish a positive and differential diagnosis, a very laborious investigation was required, namely the use of numerous laboratory tests to exclude other diseases that clinically manifest by itching, scratching, hypotrichosis/alopecia.

Results are also presented by the means of pictures showing the evolution of the most representative cases.

4. Conclusions

As generally known, "feline eosinophilic complex" includes allergic diseases often seen in feline pathology. In our study, atopic dermatitis and food allergies were the most common.

For the diagnosis of allergic dermapathies, the serological tests for IgE and intradermal tests were not employed as considered irrelevant diagnostic methods for cats.

In allergic dermatitis belonging to "feline eosinophilic complex", for the cytological examination of peripheral blood, eosinophilia was observed not to be constant; differently, for the cytological test, the diagnosis was always confirmed.

The studied product, Arsutrato-Plagotrat gel, has proven very good results, both used as adjunct in the treatment of complicated dermapathies and independent product, but always resorting to a diet for the subject.

The most important therapeutic value of the new product was found to be the possibility of use where corticotherapy could not be established, due to conditions such as kidney failure, etc.

Another observation was that, in the first days after applying the product, for some cats itching was intensified, imposing the use of "Elizabethan

collar". In most cases, itching subsided after 3-5 days of treatment.

Re-epithelialization occurred in the first 3-5-7 days of treatment, followed by total remission in 3-4 weeks due to the difficulty of controlling the itching.

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PHYSICAL AND MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF EXTRACTION FROM GRAPE MARC BY SUBCRITICAL WATER

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Abstract: *The article deals with physical and mathematical model of extraction from grape marc by subcritical water. The full model takes into account the heterogeneity of grape marc porosity structure (frameworks of grape bunch, seeds, skin, pulp residue), turbulent parameters, kinetic energy of turbulence and dissipation rate. It is obtained as a result of modification for RNG $k - \varepsilon$ of turbulence model.*

Keywords: *grape marc, subcritical water, extraction, physical and mathematical model.*

1. Problem

The Polyphenols of grapes, concentrated in its peel, seeds and frameworks of grapes bunch have hygienic and medicinal properties, which are determined mainly by antioxidant, antimutagenic, antibacterial, P-vitamin activity, i.e. have complex biological activities. Technology stock of grapes polyphenols in Ukraine is more than 500 tons of total polyphenols per year.

Polyphenols in grape native form are mainly flavonoids - poorly water-soluble substances. However, their distribution in grapes marc is: 12-20% in grapes peel, 1% in pulp, 60% in seeds, 19-24% in combs of grapes bunch [1].

Numerous studies have found that when creating biologically active products from grapes marc it is preferable to obtain the aggregate polyphenols dissolved in the liquid phase.

Due to the fact that the flavonoids are poorly soluble in water in its conventional state by using conventional processes of extraction, for solving the problem - extracting polyphenols from grapes marc with water extraction - fluid technology has been proposed, when the extraction is carried out with water in a subcritical condition [2, 3], and undergoes more severe changes than most other liquids - it is transformed from polar liquid into practically non-polar medium.

At 200⁰C the density of water drops to 0.8 g / ml, and at T_k it becomes miscible with organic solvents and gases. The rate of diffusion increases and so does its oxidizing ability. These circumstances allow you to position the subcritical water as the most effective solvent that should be used in the process of extracting polyphenols from grapes marc.

2. Researches and publications

Currently, there are quite a number of works and models that describe the process of extracting from different plant raw materials in order to extract the desired component, including dietary supplements [4].

Unfortunately, there are no models that adequately describe the process of extraction by subcritical water, which would take into account the heterogeneity of grapes marc structure porosity, specificity properties of water in the subcritical state, ensure the effective extraction of biologically active substances from the grapes marc, which determines the relevance of the work.

3. The aim of the work

The aim of the work is to develop a physical and mathematical model that takes into account the heterogeneity of grapes marc porosity structures (frameworks of grapes bunch, seeds, skin), turbulent parameters, kinetic energy of turbulence, dissipation rate and the properties of water in the subcritical state.

4. The research material

Fig. 1 shows the structure of a grape after being pressed and it is the object of the study – grapes marc consisting of grapes bunch frameworks, skin, seeds and pulp residues [5].

Fig. 1. The structure of a grape [5]

A – grape: 1 – stalk. B – longitudinal section: 1 – fruitstalk; 2 – pad; 3 - vascular bundles; 4 - seeds; 5 - peel; 6 - pulp; 7 - heart; 8 - epidermis. C - vascular bundles in the pulp. D – grapes stalks: 1 - stalk; 2 - pad; 3 - brush; 4 - tubercles (warts). E – cross section of the seed: 1 - exocarp; 2 - mesocarp with bundles of needle crystals; 3 - endocarp; 4 - endosperm with drops of fat oil, aleurone grains and druses of calcium oxalate. F - a cross section of frameworks of grapes bunch: 1 - epidermis; 2 - parenchyma; 3 - sclerenchyma; 4 – clusters of sclerenchyma cells; 5 - accrete vascular bundles; 6 - marrow parenchyma with starch grains.

The physical model of the process is represented by the capacity, the upper part of which is filled with water, which can be transformed into a supercritical fluid (Molecular weight - 18.015 g / mole, critical temperature - $T_{crit} - 647,096^{\circ}\text{K}$, critical pressure - $P_{crit} - 22,064$ MPa, critical density - $\rho_{crit} - 0,322$ g/cm³); lower part – grapes marc, which is porous media with different structures of dispersion with different physical and mechanical properties and nutritional value. Interaction of media takes place at the interface between water and marc: $z=H_p$, when H_p - height of marc layer.

Mathematical model is represented by the equations system of hydrodynamics and heat and mass transfer for the combined area (clean medium – porous medium). Each area is described by its own system of equations. The system includes the equation of continuity, motion (Navier–Stoke – for laminar-flow conditions and Reynolds – for turbulent conditions), the energy equation (Fourier -

Kirchhoff), mass transfer equation (Fick). For turbulent conditions the system is closed with RNG $k - \varepsilon$ - turbulence model, which does not include empirical constants. Hydrodynamic interaction between these areas is modeled on the surface $z=H_p$ based on the empirical relationship Beavers - Joseph (47) - (49). The following fields of process existence were reviewed.

Clean medium – $z > H_p$

Equation of continuity

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \text{div}(\rho \mathbf{v}) = 0, \quad (1)$$

where ρ – density, \mathbf{v} - velocity vector, t – time.

Equation of motion

$$\rho \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + s \underbrace{\frac{\partial \nabla(\mu_t / \rho)}{\partial t}}_I + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} \right] = \rho \mathbf{g} + \text{grad}(p) + \text{Div}(\Pi), \quad (2)$$

where

$$\nabla = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \mathbf{i} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \mathbf{j} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \mathbf{k} \quad (3)$$

$$A_d = \tilde{A}_d \frac{S_d}{(2\pi)^d}, \quad \tilde{A}_d = \frac{d^2 - d}{2d(d+2)}, \quad S_d = \frac{2\pi^{d/2}}{\Gamma(d/2)}, \quad B_d = \frac{S_d}{(2\pi)^d} \frac{d^2 - d - 2}{4d(d+2)}, \quad (5)$$

renormalization parameters (d - space dimension), μ_t - turbulent viscosity, \mathbf{g} - acceleration vector of free fall, p - pressure

$$\Pi = \begin{pmatrix} \tau_{xx} & \tau_{xy} & \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{yx} & \tau_{yy} & \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{zx} & \tau_{zy} & \tau_{zz} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

- stress tensor,

$$\text{Div}(\Pi) = \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_i} = \tilde{\nabla} \cdot \Pi \quad (7)$$

- tensor divergence of stress tensor (transforms tensor into vector), tensor components in Cartesian coordinate system:

- nabla operator (for Cartesian coordinate system),

$$s = B_d \left(\frac{8S_d}{(2\pi)^d 3A_d^3 1.575} \right)^{1/2}, \quad (4)$$

$$(\text{Div}\Pi)_x = \frac{\partial \tau_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yx}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{zx}}{\partial z}$$

$$(\text{Div}\Pi)_y = \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{zy}}{\partial z}, \quad (8)$$

$$(\text{Div}\Pi)_z = \frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yz}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{zz}}{\partial z}$$

$$\tilde{\nabla} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial z} & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

- differential dyad.

Voltages of friction are determined by Stokes' model:

$$\tau_{ij} = \mu_{eff} \left[(\text{Grad}(\mathbf{v})) + (\text{Grad}(\mathbf{v}))^T - \delta \frac{2}{3} \text{div}(\mathbf{v}) \right], \quad (10)$$

where δ - unit tensor (Kronecker tensor), μ_{eff} - effective viscosity,

- tensor gradient of velocity vector,

$$\tilde{\nabla} \mathbf{v} = \text{Grad}(\mathbf{v}) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} & \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} & \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

$$(\text{Grad}(\mathbf{v}))^T = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} \\ \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (12)$$

- transposed tensor gradient of velocity vector.

Energy equation

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + s \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\mu_t / \rho}{\sqrt{2S}} \nabla h \right)}_I + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) h \right) = \nabla \cdot \left(\lambda_{eff} \nabla T + \rho_p c_p \sum_{n=1}^4 D_{eff\ n}^{TC} \nabla C_n \right), \quad (13a)$$

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + s \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\mu_t / \rho}{\sqrt{2S}} \nabla h \right)}_I + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) h \right) = \nabla \cdot \left(\lambda_{eff} \nabla T + \rho_p c_p D_{eff}^{TC} \nabla C \right), \quad (13b)$$

where $h = cT$ - enthalpy, T - temperature, c - specific heat of fluid,

- the concentration of the extracted substances, $\rho_p c_p$ - density and specific heat of the extracted substance, $D_{eff\ n}^{TC}$ - Dufau effective coefficients on which a diffusion thermal effect is calculated (Dufau effect).

$$S = \sqrt{2S_{ij} S_{ij}}, \quad (14)$$

$$S_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (15)$$

Mass transfer equation for the total concentration of the extracted substances.

- tensor of deformation velocities λ_{eff} - effective thermal conductivity (see. below), C_n

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + s \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\mu_t / \rho}{\sqrt{2S}} \nabla C \right)}_I + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) C = \nabla \cdot \left(D_{eff} \nabla C + D_{eff}^{CT} \nabla T \right), \quad (16)$$

where D_{eff} , D_{eff}^{CT} - effective diffusion and thermal diffusion coefficients (Soret coefficients). Effective transfer coefficients are defined as the sum of turbulent and molecular coefficients:

$$\lambda = (1 - C)\lambda_f + C\lambda_p, \quad (19)$$

$$\rho = (1 - C)\rho_f + C\rho_p, \quad (20)$$

$$\rho c = (1 - C)(c\rho)_f + C(c\rho)_p, \quad (21)$$

$$\mu_{eff} = \mu_t + \mu,$$

$$\lambda_{eff} = \lambda_t + \lambda,$$

$$D_{eff\ n} = (D_t)_{eff\ n} + D_n, \quad (17)$$

$$D_{eff\ n}^{TC} = (D_t)_{eff\ n}^{TC} + D_n^{TC},$$

$$D_{eff\ n}^{CT} = (D_t)_{eff\ n}^{CT} + D_n^{CT}.$$

Molecular transfer coefficients - a function of concentration:

$$\mu = \frac{\mu_f}{(1 - C)^{2.5}}, \quad (18)$$

where index «f» relates to fluid, index «p» - to extracted substance.

The system of equations (1) - (18) is closed with RNG $k - \varepsilon$ turbulence model [6] which does not include empirical coefficients. Since the unsteady processes are analyzed in a combined media (clean fluid and porous medium), the turbulence model takes into account these effects. Unsteady effects are taken into account by the Roman numeral - I [7,8], the effects of porosity - by the Roman numeral - II [8-10], the effects of porosity - by the Roman numeral - II [8-10]. According to this model, this turbulent viscosity is determined by the formula

$$\mu_t = \frac{1}{24\sqrt{15}} \left[\frac{(4k + 3\sqrt{6\pi C_K^3 \varepsilon \mu / \rho})^2}{C_K^{3/2} \varepsilon} - 216 C_K^{3/2} \mu / \rho \right], \quad (22)$$

where $C_K = 1.605$ - renormalization group value of Kolmogorov constant.

$$\rho \left[\frac{\partial k}{\partial t} + s \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\mu_t / \rho}{\sqrt{2S}} \nabla k \right)}_I + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) k \right] = \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\mu_{eff}}{\text{Pr}_K} \nabla k \right) + S_K, \quad (23)$$

where

$$S_K = \rho(G_K - \varepsilon) \quad (24) \quad - \text{source term}$$

$$G_K = \mu_t \left[(\text{Grad}(\mathbf{v}) + (\text{Grad}(\mathbf{v}))^T) - \delta \frac{2}{3} \text{div}(\mathbf{v}) \right]^2, \quad (25)$$

- turbulence generation rate.

$$\rho \left[\frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial t} + s \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\mu_t / \rho}{\sqrt{2S}} \nabla \varepsilon \right)}_I + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \varepsilon \right] = \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\mu_{eff}}{\text{Pr}_\varepsilon} \nabla \varepsilon \right) + S_\varepsilon - R_\varepsilon, \quad (26)$$

where

$$S_\varepsilon = \rho \frac{\varepsilon}{k} (C_1 G_K - C_2 \varepsilon), \quad (27)$$

Equation for dissipation rate includes a summand

$$R_\varepsilon = \frac{C_\mu \eta_\varepsilon^3}{1 + \beta_\varepsilon \eta_\varepsilon^3} \left(1 - \frac{\eta_\varepsilon}{\eta_{\varepsilon 0}} \right) \frac{\varepsilon^2}{k}, \quad (28)$$

which plays a significant role at low Reynolds' number, when turbulence is substantially anisotropic. When Reynolds' number is big, and there is hypothesis of the local isotropy and correction (28) can be neglected. In this case, the summand must be taken into account (28), since the processes generally occur at undeveloped turbulence. For receiving such an expression

$$a = \frac{1}{2} \left(\sqrt{4 \frac{d-1}{d} \tilde{A}_d^{-1} + 1} - 1 \right), \quad b = \frac{1}{2} \left(\sqrt{4 \frac{d-1}{d} \tilde{A}_d^{-1} + 1} + 1 \right), \quad (31)$$

For a fully developed turbulence $\mu/\mu_t \rightarrow 0$ from (30) it can be concluded that for three-dimensional flow ($d=3$)

$$\text{Pr}_t^{-1} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\sqrt{4 \frac{d-1}{d} \tilde{A}_d^{-1} + 1} - 1 \right) = 1,3929 \quad (32)$$

For similar dependencies there are calculated turbulent diffusion coefficients through the turbulent Schmidt number.

For Pr_K transcendental equation has the form

The equation for the kinetic energy of turbulence.

Equation for energy dissipation rate

there was used renormalization procedure and epsilon - decomposition using Navier - Stokes equation [11.12]. In (29) $\eta_{\varepsilon 0} = 4,38$,

$$\eta_\varepsilon = \frac{Sk}{\varepsilon}, \quad (29)$$

The work suggests acquiring the value $\beta_\varepsilon = 0,012$, which corresponds to classical value of Karman constant $\chi = 0,4$. $C_1 = 1,42$ и $C_2 = 1,68$ RG values of turbulence model constants.

The coefficient of turbulent heat transfer is determined by the transcendental equation

$$\left| \frac{\text{Pr}_t^{-1} - a}{\text{Pr}_t^{-1} - a} \right|^{\frac{a+1}{a+b}} \left| \frac{\text{Pr}_t^{-1} + b}{\text{Pr}_t^{-1} + b} \right|^{\frac{b-1}{a+b}} = \frac{\mu}{\mu_t}, \quad (30)$$

through the turbulent Prandtl number Pr_t . B (31)

$$\left| \frac{\text{Pr}_K^{-1} - a}{1 - a} \right|^{\frac{a+1}{a+b}} \left| \frac{\text{Pr}_K^{-1} + b}{1 + b} \right|^{\frac{b-1}{a+b}} = \frac{\mu}{\mu_t}, \quad (33)$$

Besides it is accepted that $\text{Pr}_K = \text{Pr}_\varepsilon$.

The porous medium - $z < H_p$

Equation of continuity

$$\varphi \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \text{div}(\rho \mathbf{v}) = 0, \quad (34)$$

when φ - porosity.

Equation of motion

$$\rho \left[\frac{1}{\varphi} \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + s \underbrace{\frac{\partial \nabla(\mu_t/\rho)}{\partial t}}_I + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} \right] = \rho \mathbf{g} + \text{grad}(p) + \frac{1}{\varphi} \text{Div}(\Pi) \quad (35)$$

$$- \frac{\mu}{K} \mathbf{v} - \frac{c_F \rho}{\sqrt{K}} |\mathbf{v}| \mathbf{v} + 4 \underbrace{\frac{c_F}{\sqrt{K}} \frac{d^2 - 2}{d^2 - d} \mu_t \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{v}}{|\mathbf{v}|} \right)}_{II},$$

where $c_F = 0,55$ – Forhaymer coefficient,
 $\mathbf{v} \otimes \mathbf{v}$ - tensor composition of velocity vectors, K
 permeability, which can be calculated by Kozeny
 equation [13].

$$K = \frac{d_0^2 \varphi^3}{(1 - \varphi^2)}, \quad (36)$$

d_0 - equivalent particle diameter, simulating a
 porous medium.

The energy equation.

$$\rho_m \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + \rho \left(\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + s \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{(\mu_t/\rho)}{\sqrt{2S}} \nabla h \right)}_I + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) h \right) = \nabla \cdot \left(\lambda_{eff} \nabla T + \rho_p c_p \sum_{n=1}^4 D_{eff\ n}^{TC} \nabla C_n \right), \quad (37)$$

Where

$$\lambda_{eff} = \lambda_t + \lambda_m, \quad (38)$$

$$\lambda_m = (1 - \varphi) \lambda_s + \varphi \lambda \quad (39)$$

$$\rho_m = (1 - \varphi) \rho_s + \varphi \rho, \quad (40)$$

index "s" relates to a solid phase.

Mass exchange equation for each type of wastes:

$$\varphi \frac{\partial C_n}{\partial t} + s \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{(\mu_t/\rho)}{\sqrt{2S}} \nabla C_n \right)}_I + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) C_n = \nabla \cdot (D_{eff\ n} \nabla C_n + D_{eff\ n}^{CT} \nabla T) + k_n C_n^{m_n}, \quad (41)$$

$n = 1, 2, 3, 4$. (frameworks of grapes bunch, seeds, peel, pulp)

The total concentration of the extracted
 substance is determined by the formula

$$C = \sum_{i=n}^4 C_n, \quad (42)$$

The equations for the turbulent kinetic energy
 and energy dissipation rate include terms include
 porosity medium:

$$\rho \left[\frac{\partial k}{\partial t} + s \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{(\mu_t/\rho)}{\sqrt{2S}} \nabla k \right)}_I + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) k \right] = \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\mu_{eff}}{\text{Pr}_k} \nabla k \right) + S_k - 2\mu \frac{\varphi}{K} k -$$

$$- 2\varphi^2 \frac{c_F}{\sqrt{K}} |\mathbf{v}| k + 8\varphi^2 \underbrace{\frac{c_F}{\sqrt{K}} \frac{d^2 - 2}{d^2 - d} \mu_t k \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\frac{u_i u_j}{|\mathbf{v}|} \right)}_{II}, \quad (43)$$

$$\rho \left[\frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial t} + s \underbrace{\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{(\mu_t/\rho)}{\sqrt{2S}} \nabla \varepsilon \right)}_I + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \varepsilon \right] = \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\mu_{eff}}{\text{Pr}_\varepsilon} \nabla \varepsilon \right) + S_\varepsilon -$$

$$- 2\mu \frac{\varphi}{K} \varepsilon - 2\mu \varphi^2 \frac{c_F}{\sqrt{K}} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{u}_i) - 8\mu \varphi^2 \underbrace{\frac{c_F}{\sqrt{K}} \frac{d^2 - 2}{d^2 - d} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\frac{\mu_t}{\rho} J \frac{\partial u_j u_i}{|\mathbf{v}|} \right)}_{II} - R_\varepsilon, \quad (44)$$

The formulas (32) and (33) are of the following type

$$a = \frac{1}{2} \left(\sqrt{4 \frac{d-1}{d} \tilde{A}_d^{-1} \varphi + 1} - 1 \right), \quad b = \frac{1}{2} \left(\sqrt{4 \frac{d-1}{d} \tilde{A}_d^{-1} \varphi + 1} + 1 \right), \quad (45)$$

$$\text{Pr}_r^{-1} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\sqrt{4 \frac{d-1}{d} \tilde{A}_d^{-1} \varphi + 1} - 1 \right), \quad (46)$$

The interface of clean and porous media – $z = H_p$

Hydrodynamic interaction between the clean and the porous media is modeled due to the surface $z = H_p$ based on the modified empirical

$$\left(\frac{\partial \rho u}{\partial z} - \frac{\alpha_{BJ}}{\sqrt{K}} \rho u \right)_{z \rightarrow H_p^+} = \left(-\frac{\alpha_{BJ}}{\sqrt{K}} \rho u \right)_{z \rightarrow H_p^-}, \quad (47a)$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial \rho v}{\partial z} - \frac{\alpha_{BJ}}{\sqrt{K}} \rho v \right)_{z \rightarrow H_p^+} = \left(-\frac{\alpha_{BJ}}{\sqrt{K}} \rho v \right)_{z \rightarrow H_p^-}, \quad (47b)$$

For the vertical component of the velocity, it follows from the continuity equation

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2 \rho w}{\partial z^2} - \frac{\alpha_{BJ}}{\sqrt{K}} \frac{\partial \rho w}{\partial z} \right)_{z \rightarrow H_p^+} = \left(-\frac{\alpha_{BJ}}{\sqrt{K}} \frac{\partial \rho w}{\partial z} \right)_{z \rightarrow H_p^-}, \quad (48)$$

In contrast to the classical correlation of Beavers - Joseph, the formulas take into account the variability of density. Beavers – Joseph coefficient $\alpha_{BJ} = 1,45$ [13].

For the clean liquid area there is considered one common field of concentration described by one common equation and transfer coefficients of this substance in the water, and for each

$$\left(-\lambda_a \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} - \rho_p c_p D_a^{TC} \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \right)_{z \rightarrow H_p^+} = \left(-\lambda_j \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} - \rho_p c_p D_j^{TC} \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \right)_{z \rightarrow H_p^-}, \quad (49)$$

where $j = 1 \dots 4$ – separate porous body (frameworks of grape bunch, seeds, skin, pulp residue).

The equation for the supercritical medium was used as the equation of state. When calculating there was used the equation of state due to Formulation IF-97. While modeling the fluid can be in areas 1, 2 and 3 (Fig.2)

In area 1 the basic equation is the equation for the specific Gibbs energy [14]

$$\frac{g(p, T)}{RT} = \gamma(\pi, \tau) = \sum_{i=1}^{34} n_i (7, 1 - \pi)^{l_i} (\tau - 1, 222)^{j_i} \quad (50)$$

where $\pi = p / p^*$ and $\tau = T^* / T$; $p^* = 16,53 \text{ MPa}$, $T^* = 1386 \text{ K}$.

The values of coefficients and exponents degree for the equation (50) are given in [14]. Coefficients n_3 и n_4 in the equation (50) are selected to satisfy the operating since 1954 “Agreement” about accepting the values equal to

correlation of Beavers - Joseph [13]. For the horizontal component of velocity, the correlation is the following.

component of the porous medium the equation with its transfer coefficients is used. If we know that on the surface of the liquid contacting with porous media each component takes its share of the area, then in each section of this area there is a need to set its own conditions for heat flow and mass flow connection. For the heat flow at the area occupied by the porous component j :

Fig. 2. The areas of Formulation IF - 97 equations

zero of specific internal energy and liquid entropy in the triple point ($T = 273,16 \text{ K}$, $p = 611,657 \text{ Pa}$).

In the area 2 - basic equation is the equation for the specific Gibbs energy divided into two parts:

ideal-gas portion γ^0 and real portion γ^r [14].

$$\frac{g(p, T)}{RT} = \gamma(\pi, \tau) = \gamma^0(\pi, \tau) + \gamma^r(\pi, \tau); \quad (51)$$

$$\gamma^0 = \ln \pi + \sum_{i=1}^9 n_i^0 \tau^{J_i^0}; \quad (52)$$

$$\gamma^r = \sum_{i=1}^{43} n_i \pi^{L_i} (\tau - 0.5)^{J_i} \quad (53)$$

where

$$\pi = p / p^*$$

$$\text{and } \tau = T^* / T; p^* = 1 \text{ MPa}, T^* = 540 \text{ K}$$

The values of the coefficients and exponents of equations (52) and (53) are described in [14]. The coefficients n_1^0 и n_2^0 are selected to satisfy the

values equal to zero of internal energy and entropy.

For the area 3 - basic equation is the equation for the specific Helmholtz energy.

$$\frac{f(\rho, T)}{RT} = \phi(\delta, \tau) = n_i \ln \delta + \sum_{i=2}^{40} n_i \delta^{L_i} \tau^{J_i} \quad (54)$$

where

$$\delta = \rho / \rho^* \text{ and } \tau = T^* / T;$$

$$\rho^* = 1 \rho_{cr}, T^* = T_{cr}$$

The values of coefficients and exponents for the equation (54) are given in [14].

The given isobaric heat capacity is calculated separately for the three subareas [15]. In the first subarea

$$\frac{c_p T_{\bar{n}1}}{p_{\bar{n}1} v_{\bar{n}1}} = \hat{O}_1 = -\theta \left(\frac{\partial^2 \zeta_1}{\partial \theta^2} \right)_\beta \quad (55)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{O}_1 = & \dot{\lambda}_0 - \sum_{v=0}^7 (v+2)(v+1) A_{v+3} \theta^{v+1} - \\ & - A_{11} \theta \left[\left(\frac{12}{19} z - Y \right) \left[z^{-5/17} \frac{d^2 z}{d\theta^2} - \frac{5}{17} z^{-22/17} (z')^2 \right] + \left(\frac{24}{29} z' - 2Y' \right) z^{-5/17} z' + \left(\frac{17}{29} z'' - \frac{17}{12} Y'' \right) z^{12/17} \right] - \\ & - \theta \beta \left[2 \dot{\lambda}_{14} + 90 \dot{\lambda}_{15} (\dot{\alpha}_6 - \theta)^8 + 7220 \dot{\lambda}_{16} (\dot{\alpha}_7 + \theta^{19})^{-3} - 3420 \dot{\lambda}_{17} (\dot{\alpha}_7 + \theta^{19})^{-2} \right] + \\ & + \left[2420 \dot{\lambda}_{21} (\dot{\alpha}_8 + \theta^{11})^{-3} - 1100 \dot{\lambda}_{22} (\dot{\alpha}_8 + \theta^{11})^{-2} \right] (\dot{\lambda}_{17} \beta + \dot{\lambda}_{18} \beta^2 + \dot{\lambda}_{19} \beta^3) + \\ & + A_{20} \theta^{17} (306 \dot{\alpha}_9 + 3800 \theta^2) \left[(\dot{\alpha}_{10} + \beta)^{-3} + \dot{\alpha}_{11} \beta \right] - 420 A_{22} \theta^{-21} \beta^4 + 342 (\dot{\lambda}_{23} + \dot{\lambda}_{24} \beta^3) \theta^{18}, \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

where

$$Y'' = -2a_1 - 42a_2 \theta^{-8}; \quad (57)$$

$$z' = Y' + (a_3 Y Y' - a_4) (a_3 Y^2 - 2a_4 \theta + 2a_5 \beta)^{-1/2}; \quad (58)$$

$$z'' = Y'' + a_3 (a_3 Y^2 - 2a_4 \theta + 2a_5 \beta)^{-1/2} \left[(Y'')^2 + Y Y'' \right] - (a_3 Y Y'' - a_4)^2 (a_3 Y^2 - 2a_4 \theta + 2a_5 \beta)^{-3/2}. \quad (59)$$

In the subarea 2 – the given isobaric heat capacity [15]

$$\frac{c_p T_{\bar{m}1}}{p_{\bar{m}1} v_{\bar{m}1}} = \hat{O}_2 = -\theta \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Psi_{\bar{A}}}{\partial \theta^2} \right)_\chi + \theta \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Psi_{\bar{A}}}{\partial \chi \partial \theta} \right)^2 / \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Psi_{\bar{A}}}{\partial \chi^2} \right)_\theta \quad (60)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Psi_{\dot{A}}}{\partial \theta^2}\right)_{\chi} &= -\dot{A}_{00} \theta^{-2} + \dot{A}_{10} \theta^{-1} + 2\dot{A}_{22} + 2\tilde{O}_2 \theta^{-3} + 30\tilde{O}_3 \theta^{-7} + \\ &+ \tilde{O}_4 \left[42F_{20} \theta^5 + \sum_{v=0}^7 (v-1)(v-2) F_{2v} \theta^{-v} \right] + \\ &+ \tilde{O}_5 \left(462F_{31} F_{32}^2 \theta^{20} - 1892F_{30} F_{32} F_{33} \theta^{42} - 2904F_{31} F_{32} F_{33} \theta^{64} + 1980F_{30} F_{33}^2 \theta^{86} + 506F_{31} F_{33}^2 \theta^{108} \right) \times \\ &\times (F_{32} + F_{33} \theta^{44})^{-3} + \tilde{O}_6 (552F_{40} \theta^{22} + 1260F_{41} \theta^{34}) - \theta^{205} (42642b_{80} - 43056\theta^{207}) (b_{80} + \theta^{207})^{-3} \tilde{O}_7. \quad (61) \\ \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Psi_{\dot{A}}}{\partial \chi^2}\right)_{\theta} &= I_1 \theta \left[\chi^{-2} + \sum_{v=0}^3 (v+1)(v+2) F_{1v} \chi^{-(v+3)} \right] + \end{aligned}$$

$$+ b_{81} \chi^{-3} \left[\begin{aligned} &\left(2X'_1 + b_{81} \chi^{-1} X''_1 \right) + \left(2X'_2 + b_{81} \chi^{-1} X''_2 \right) \theta^{-1} + \left(2X'_3 + b_{81} \chi^{-1} X''_3 \right) \theta^{-5} + \\ &+ \left(2X'_4 + b_{81} \chi^{-1} X''_4 \right) \left(F_{20} \theta^7 + \sum_{v=1}^7 F_{2v} \theta^{2-v} \right) + \\ &+ \left(2X'_5 + b_{81} \chi^{-1} X''_5 \right) (F_{30} + F_{31} \theta^{22}) (F_{32} + F_{33} \theta^{44})^{-1} + \\ &+ \left(2X'_6 + b_{81} \chi^{-1} X''_6 \right) (F_{41} \theta^{36} + F_{40} \theta^{24}) + \left(2X'_7 + b_{81} \chi^{-1} X''_7 \right) (b_{80} + \theta^{207})^{-1} \end{aligned} \right], \quad (62)$$

where

$$X''_{\mu} = \sum_{v=2}^{m(\mu)} b_{\mu v} v(v-1) (b_{82} + b_{81} \chi^{-1})^{v-2}; \quad (63)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \Psi_{\dot{A}}}{\partial \chi \partial \theta} &= -I_1 \chi^{-1} \left[1 + \sum_{v=0}^3 (v+1) F_{1v} \chi^{-(v+1)} \right] - \\ &- b_{81} \chi^{-2} \left\{ \begin{aligned} &-X'_2 \theta^{-2} - 5X'_3 \theta^{-6} + X'_4 \left[7F_{20} \theta^6 - \sum_{v=1}^7 (v-2) F_{2v} \theta^{1-v} \right] + \\ &+ X'_5 \left(22F_{31} F_{32} \theta^{21} - 44F_{30} F_{33} \theta^{43} - 22F_{31} F_{33} \theta^{65} \right) \times \\ &\times (F_{32} + F_{33} \theta^{44})^{-2} + X'_6 \left(24F_{40} \theta^{23} + 36F_{41} \theta^{35} \right) - \\ &- 207\theta^{206} (b_{80} + \theta^{207})^{-2} X'_7 \end{aligned} \right\}. \quad (64) \end{aligned}$$

In the subarea 3 – the given isobaric heat capacity [15]

$$\frac{c_p T_{\bar{n}1}}{p_{\bar{n}1} v_{\bar{n}1}} = \hat{O}_3 = -\theta \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Psi_{\bar{N}}}{\partial \theta^2} \right)_{\chi} + \theta \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Psi_{\bar{N}}}{\partial \chi \partial \theta} \right)^2 / \left(\frac{\partial^2 y_{\bar{N}}}{\partial \chi^2} \right)_{\theta} \quad (65)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Psi_{\bar{N}}}{\partial \theta^2}\right)_{\chi} &= -\dot{A}_{00} \theta^{-2} + \dot{A}_{10} \theta^{-1} + 2\dot{A}_{22} + \sum_{v=0}^4 (v+1)(25v+26) C_{0v} \theta^{-(25v+27)} + 2Y_2 \theta^{-3} + 30Y_3 \theta^{-7} + \\ &+ Y_4 \left[42F_{20} \theta^5 + \sum_{v=1}^7 (v-1)(v-2) F_{2v} \theta^{-v} \right] + \\ &+ Y_5 \left(462F_{31} F_{32}^2 \theta^{20} - 1892F_{30} F_{32} F_{33} \theta^{42} - 2904F_{31} F_{32} F_{33} \theta^{64} + 1980F_{30} F_{33}^2 \theta^{86} + 506F_{31} F_{33}^2 \theta^{108} \right) \times \\ &\times (F_{32} + F_{33} \theta^{44})^{-3} + Y_6 (552F_{40} \theta^{22} + 1260F_{41} \theta^{34}) + 40200 \left[\sum_{\lambda=0}^2 c_{7\lambda} z^{w(\lambda)} \right] \theta^{-202}; \quad (66) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\left(\frac{\partial^2 \Psi_{\tilde{N}}}{\partial \chi^2}\right)_\theta &= I_1 \theta \left[\chi^{-2} + \sum_{v=0}^3 (v+1)(v+2) F_{1v} \chi^{-(v+3)} \right] + \\
&+ c_{81} \chi^{-3} \left[\begin{aligned}
&\left(2Y_1' + c_{81} \chi^{-1} Y_1''\right) + \left(2Y_2' + c_{81} \chi^{-1} Y_2''\right) \theta^{-1} + \left(2Y_3' + c_{81} \chi^{-1} Y_3''\right) \theta^{-5} + \\
&+ \left(2Y_4' + c_{81} \chi^{-1} Y_4''\right) \left(F_{20} \theta^7 + \sum_{v=1}^7 F_{2v} \theta^{2-v}\right) + \\
&+ \left(2Y_5' + c_{81} \chi^{-1} Y_5''\right) \left(F_{30} + F_{31} \theta^{22}\right) \left(F_{32} + F_{33} \theta^{44}\right)^{-1} + \\
&+ \left(2Y_6' + c_{81} \chi^{-1} Y_6''\right) \left(F_{41} \theta^{36} + F_{40} \theta^{24}\right) + \\
&\left(2 \sum_{\lambda=0}^2 w(\lambda) c_{7\lambda} z^{w(\lambda)-1} + c_{81} \chi^{-1} \sum_{\lambda=0}^2 w(\lambda) [w(\lambda)-1] c_{7\lambda} z^{w(\lambda)-2}\right) \theta^{-200}
\end{aligned} \right], \tag{67}
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_\mu'' &= \sum_{v=2}^{n(\mu)} c_{\mu v} v(v-1) (c_{82} + c_{81} \chi^{-1})^{v-2}; \tag{68} \\
\frac{\partial^2 \Psi_{\tilde{N}}}{\partial \chi \partial \theta} &= -I_1 \chi^{-1} \left[1 + \sum_{v=0}^3 (v+1) F_{1v} \chi^{-(v+1)} \right] - \\
&- \tilde{n}_{81} \chi^{-2} \theta^{-201} \left\{ \begin{aligned}
&-Y_2' \theta^{-2} - 5Y_3' \theta^{-6} + \\
&+ Y_5' \left(22F_{31} F_{32} \theta^{21} - 44F_{30} F_{33} \theta^{43} - 22F_{31} F_{33} \theta^{65} \right) \times \\
&\times \left(F_{32} + F_{33} \theta^{44} \right)^{-2} + Y_6' \left(24F_{40} \theta^{23} + 36F_{41} \theta^{35} \right) - \\
&- 207 \left(\sum_{\lambda=0}^2 w(\lambda) c_{7\lambda} z^{w(\lambda)-1} \right)
\end{aligned} \right\}. \tag{69}
\end{aligned}$$

In this formulation of the problem RNG $k - \varepsilon$ - turbulence model, this model adequately describes laminar, transitional and turbulent flow regimes. When calculating, it is possible use this turbulence model for the whole range of Rayleigh (Ra) numbers, which is determined by the value of the hydrodynamic flow regime. The use of the full model, taking into account the equations for turbulent kinetic energy and dissipation rate, complicates modeling and increases time counting. For the known laminar flow you can use the system of equations which does not include the turbulent parameters and equations

for the turbulent kinetic energy and dissipation rate

5. Conclusions

The proposed model describes the process of extracting grape marc by subcritical water, it takes into account the heterogeneity of grape marc porosity structure (frameworks of grape bunch, seeds, skin, pulp residue), can be used if there are necessary characteristics of the original substrate components - marc, in solving problems of providing the predetermined output of target specific component, design of processing equipment.

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